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Abstract

Life sciences research in India is mapped based on papers published in 1998 and indexed in *Biosis Biological Abstracts*. The findings are compared with those of an earlier study covering the years 1992-1994. There were 8352 papers in all, and these were published in more than 1080 journals. About 55% of life science papers were published in 75 Indian journals and more than 82% of papers were published in journals of impact factor less than 1.0. The two areas in which the largest numbers of papers were published are Agriculture and Biochemistry and molecular biophysics. While most agriculture papers had appeared in journals of impact factor zero or less than 1.0, many Biochemistry and molecular biophysics papers were published in journals of moderate to high impact factors. There has been a tendency over the years to publish papers in journals of higher impact factor. Close to 59% of papers were published by academic institutions, much less than the 64.5% in 1992-1994. This decline in research in academic institutions needs to be addressed.

Life sciences research in India: A profile based on *Biosis* 1998

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Introduction

Life sciences now occupy the central stage and are attracting some of the best brains. In the advanced countries, life sciences research attracts much higher amounts of funds than other fields. With its close links to both agriculture and medicine, new biology is only bound to become even more important in the years to come. According the NSF, life science domains – biology, biomedicine and clinical medicine – accounted for 55% of the world's publications and 63% of US publications in science, technology and medicine in 1995.¹ It is against this background we wanted to see what is happening in this crucial field in India.

Using standard scientometric techniques we have mapped life sciences research in India as reflected by the journal literature of 1998. This is a macroscopic study at the institutional level. Apart from providing an estimate of the volume of work published by Indian researchers, we have identified (1) the contribution of different institutions, cities (or towns), and states, (2) the journals often used by Indian researchers and their standing as reflected by impact factors, and (3) subfields in which Indian researchers were active in 1998. Wherever possible, we have compared our results with those of our earlier study based on *Biosis* 1992-1994.^{2,3}

Methodology

The bibliographic data on all papers from India published in the year 1998 were downloaded from *Biosis Biological Abstracts 1998-2000* September (CD-ROM version). We used the MS-DOS based Silver Platter retrieving software SPIRSto retrieve bibliographic data from the database. As *Biosis* gives only the first author's address, we could download only those papers in which the first author had given an Indian address. Thus we have missed all papers in which Indian authors were not listed as the first

author. The fields downloaded were CS (Corporate source or author affiliation), SO (Source or Journal title), PY (Publication year), DT (Document type), AU (Authors), TI (Title), LN (Language.) and MC (subfield or major classification).

To download data, we made a search strategy, which had included names of more than 350 Indian cities/ towns. This was necessary because, unlike *SCI*, *Biosis* does not give country names in some of the entries. As the names of some Indian cities are shared by some foreign cities, we had to eliminate papers not belonging to India. We had done this work manually, after converting the data into a relational database using Visual-FoxPro. The names of institutions were standardized. Then names of states were added to all the cities found in the database. The country of publication of the journals and their impact factors were added from *Journal Citation Reports* 1997. We located the country of publication of journals that were not listed in *JCR* from *Serial Sources for the Biosis Previews Database* 1993 and *Publist* (on the Internet).

Findings

Biological Abstracts on CD (Silver Platter version) for the years 1998 – 2000 September had indexed 8352 papers from Indian addresses for the publication year 1998. Of these 8056 were journal articles and 188 literature reviews (Table 1). Except two papers in French and one in Chinese-English, all the rest were in English (Table 2).

Distribution by journal

These papers were published in 1085 journals (Table 3). *Indian Veterinary Journal* and *Indian Journal of Animal Sciences* had published more than 300 papers each, and *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology* and *Current Science* had published more than 200 papers each. Eight journals had published more than 100 papers but less than 200, and 24 journals had published 50 or more papers but less than 100. At the other extreme, 429 journals had published just one paper each, 207 journals two papers each, and 93 journals three papers each. The distribution of papers over journals is shown in Figure 1. Of the 1085 journals used by Indian life scientists to publish their work in 1998, only 23 were letters journals and they had published 226 papers (Table 4). Of these, the organic chemistry journal *Tetrahedron Letters* had published more than 60 papers from India.

There seems to be no urgency among Indian life scientists to use rapid communication channels. The situation is different in physics and to some extent in chemistry. Indian physicists and chemists use letters journal to publish a higher percent of their papers.

Distribution by subfield

The papers were assigned to 162 subfields (Table 5). Often a paper is classified under more than one subfield. In such cases we have assigned the paper to the category listed first. Agronomy tops the list with 978 papers, followed by Biochemistry and molecular biophysics (646 papers), Horticulture (336 papers), and Animal husbandry (315 papers). Indian researchers had published more than 200 papers but less than 300 in five subfields, and more than 100 papers but less than 200 in 14 subfields. *Biological Abstracts* has also indicated an intermediate level categorization for many journals. For example, the subfields Animal husbandry and Horticulture, among others, are grouped under Agriculture. At this level, there are 1675 papers in Agriculture, 1057 papers in Biochemistry and molecular biophysics, 357 papers in Population studies, 331 papers in Chemical coordination and homeostasis, 590 papers in Human medicine - medical sciences, and 207 in Environmental sciences.

Distribution by journal country

Indian life scientists publish their work in journals published in 46 countries (Table 6). We could not identify the journal country for 23 papers published in eight journals. The largest number of papers – 4630 or more than 55% - was published in 75 Indian journals. Indian authors have used 232 UK journals to publish 1,006 papers, 294 US journals to publish 844 papers, and 127 journals published in the Netherlands to publish 657 papers (Figure 3). They have published 311 papers in 86 German journals. Ten or more papers have been published in journals published in 25 countries. Of the 75 Indian journals, 12 have carried more than 100 papers each, and 20 journals between 50 and 100 papers (Table 7). Of these 75, only 15 journals were included in *Journal Citation Reports* 1997, but none has an impact factor greater than 0.4. *Biological Abstracts* covers a much larger number of Indian journals than *Science Citation Index*, as it aims to cover the literature of

life sciences comprehensively whereas *SCP*'s coverage is selective and restricted to the 'significant' journals.⁴

Distribution by journal impact factor

Of the 1085 journals in which Indian scientists have published their work in 1998, 241 carrying 3565 papers were not covered by *JCR* (Table 8). A further 3316 papers had appeared in 411 journals whose impact factors are less than 1.0. Only 40 Indian papers had appeared in journals with an impact factor greater than or equal to 5.0, and 175 papers in journals with an impact factor greater than or equal to 3.0. The distribution of papers over journals in different impact factor ranges is shown in Figure 4 and the distribution of journals used by Indian scientists over impact factors is shown in Figure 5.

Distribution by institution

India's output of life science literature in 1998 had come from more than 1300 institutional addresses (Table 9). The distribution of papers over institutions is depicted in Figure 6. We could not find institutional addresses for 479 papers. Eight institutions have published more than 100 papers each. These include two university-level medical institutions, three agricultural universities, a veterinary university, a central university and the Indian Institute of Science. 16 institutions had published between 50 and 100 papers. At the other extreme, 644 institutions have published just one paper each, and 186 institutions two papers each. Academic institutions – universities and colleges – accounted for 4879 papers or 58.4% of the total (Table 10). General universities and colleges had published 2345 or 28.1% of all papers. Agricultural universities and colleges had published 1761 papers or 20.1% of all Indian papers. Among the Central Government research organizations, ICAR had published 760 papers and CSIR 638 papers. The distribution of papers over institutional type is shown in Figure 7.

Distribution by city and state

In all, as seen from Table 11, papers have come from 426 cities/ towns. New Delhi (including Delhi) leads the list with 802 papers, followed by Bangalore (378), Mumbai (336), Lucknow (336), Chennai (336), Hyderabad (309), and Calcutta (301). Sixteen

cities have published more than 100 papers, 14 cities between 50 and 100 papers, and 33 cities between 25 and 50 papers. At the other extreme, 174 cities have contributed just one paper each and 41 cities two papers each. No city was assigned to 487 papers. The 8,352 papers from India have come from 30 states/ union territories (Table 12). Uttar Pradesh, Delhi, Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu are the states with the largest number of papers.

Distribution by institution and impact factor

In Table 13, we provide information on the use of journals of different impact factor ranges by some important institutions. Indian Institute of Science and All India Institute of Medical Sciences have published a much larger number of papers in high impact journals than other institutions. Jawaharlal Nehru University, Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, Christian Medical College, University of Delhi, and National Chemical Laboratory have also published a few papers in high impact journals.

Distribution of papers by subfield and impact factor

A matrix of subfields vs. impact factor ranges of journals (Table 14) reveals that Biochemistry and molecular biophysics (including molecular genetics, and enzymology), Cell biology, and Human medicine- Medical sciences are the fields that contribute most of the papers in high impact factor journals. This is to be expected as these are areas of higher impact than most classical biology and agricultural research fields.

The journals often used by many institutions to publish their work are shown in Table 15, and the subfields in which these institutions have published many papers are listed in Table 16. All India Institute of Medical Sciences, for example had published 24 papers in Cardiovascular medicine, 12 papers in Biochemistry and molecular biophysics and 10 papers in Infection. Indian Agricultural research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Punjab Agricultural University, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, and G B Pant University of Agriculture and Technology had published many papers in Agronomy. Indian Veterinary Research Institute is strong in Animal husbandry and Central Food Technological research Institute in Foods.

Conclusion

Biosis is a good source of information for such a study. It covers all areas of life sciences, including classical and new biology, agriculture and some areas of medicine. From a bibliometrician's point of view also, it is a good database as it gives journal titles in full. Journal country information is provided in the print version of the *Serial Sources*.⁵ One minor problem is that it may not cover papers published in Indian journals comprehensively. For example, for PY = 1998 it had indexed only 75 Indian journals. For the three years 1992-1994, it had covered 120 Indian journals. This is a problem with almost all databases. None will cover *all* Indian journals in its area of coverage. Especially, the citation index databases of ISI cover much smaller percentage of Indian journals. The reason for the poor coverage of Indian journals in international databases has to do, at least in part, with the poor quality of the papers published in Indian journals.

About 55% of Indian papers in life sciences have been published in Indian journals. There has not been much change from 1992-1994, when Indian journals accounted for 54% of all Indian papers indexed in *Biosis*. In agricultural research, a much larger proportion of Indian papers are published in home country journals (about 77% in 1990-1994 and greater than 78 % in 1998).⁶ In fish research in the six years 1994-1999, Indian researchers had published 69.9% of their journal papers in Indian journals.⁷ Arunachalam and Gunasekaran have shown that during the ten years 1990-1999 Indian researchers had published close to 40% of papers in tuberculosis,⁸ 36% of papers in diabetes research⁹ and 40.3% of papers in cardiovascular diseases research¹⁰ in Indian journals. In mathematics, during the 11 years 1988-1998, 38.5% of Indian papers were published in home country journals.

A high proportion of Indian papers in life sciences has been published in low impact factor journals: more than 82% of papers in 1998 and 84% in 1992-1994 have appeared in journals with impact factor less than 1.0. Less than 1.0% of papers have appeared in journals with impact factors of 4.0 or higher: 0.87% in 1998 and 0.69% in 1992-1994. Thus over the years there has been a shift, even if it is only marginal, towards publishing in higher impact journals. A point of concern is that even better known institutions publish a substantial proportion of their papers in low impact factor journals or even journals not indexed in *SCI* (Table 13). For example, Indian Institute of Science

where the entire thrust is in new biology (as distinct from classical biology) has published 48 of its 133 papers in journals of impact factor less than 1.0. In general, new biology journals have a higher impact factor than classical biology journals. All India Institute of Medical Sciences has published 123 of its 192 papers in low impact (IF < 1.0) journals.

In fish research during 1994-1999, Indian researchers had published 94.1% of their journal papers in journals with impact factor less than 1.0.⁷ Even in medical research, a very high proportion of Indian papers appear in low impact factor (IF < 1.0) journals. Arunachalam and Gunasekaran found that during 1990-1999 Indian researchers had published 74.3% of papers in tuberculosis research,⁸ 70.6% of papers in cardiovascular diseases research,¹⁰ and 69% of papers in diabetes research⁹ in such journals,

Another point that stands out is that the share of academic institutions has come down from 64.5% of all Indian papers in 1992-1994 to 58.4% in 1998. Is it because, recruitments to higher level teaching and research positions have been frozen in recent years? Or, are our universities unable to allocate or attract funds for research in life sciences?

Literature-based mapping can be used in framing policies for higher education and science. It can even be used, with abundant caution of course, in evaluation and monitoring institutional performance.

Acknowledgement

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References

1. National Science Board, Science and Engineering Indicators 1998, National Science Foundation, Alington, VA, USA, 1998 NSB-98-1.
2. Arunachalam, S. Mapping life sciences research in India: A profile based on *Biosis* 1992-1994. Report submitted to NISSAT-DSIR, New Delhi, November 1998.
3. Arunachalam, S. Mapping life sciences research in India: A profile based on *Biosis* 1992-1994. *Current Science*, **76** (1999) 1191-1203.
4. Garfield, E. Significant journals of science, *Nature*, **264** (1976) 609-615.
5. *Serials Sources for the BIOSIS Previews Database*, Vol. 1993, December 1993. Biological Abstracts Inc, Philadelphia, USA.
6. Arunachalam, S and Umarani, K. Mapping agricultural research in India: A profile based on *CAB Abstracts* 1998, *Current Science*, **81** (2001) 896-906.
7. Jayashree, B and Arunachalam, S. Mapping fish research in India, *Current Science*, **79** (2000) 613-620.
8. Arunachalam, S and Gunasekaran, S. Tuberculosis research in India and China today: From literature-based mapping to health care policy, Paper under submission, November 2001.
9. Arunachalam, S and Gunasekaran, S. Mapping diabetes research in India and China today, Paper under submission, November 2001.
10. Arunachalam, S and Gunasekaran, S. Cardiovascular diseases research in India and China in the 1990s, Paper under submission, November 2001.

TABLES

Table 1. Indian research papers classified by document type as seen from BIOSIS-1998

Document type*	No. of papers
Article-	8056
Literature-Review	188
Letter-	39
Article-; Letter-	25
Letter-; Article-	16
Meeting-	10
Editorial-	6
Article-; Article-Erratum	1
Article-; Letter-; Article-	1
Article-; Literature-Review	1
Article-; Meeting-	1
Bibliography-; Article-	1
Biography-	1
Biography-; Article-	1
Biography-; Bibliography-	1
Literature-Review; Article-	1
Meeting-; Article-	1
Meeting-; Standard-	1
Obituary-	1
Total	8352

***Document type as given in each entry in BIOSIS**

**Table 2. Indian research papers as seen from BIOSIS
classified by language**

No.	Language	No. of papers
1	English	8349
2	French; Non-English	2
3	Chinese; English	1
Total		8352

Table 3. Indian research papers classified by journal

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
1	Indian-Veterinary-Journal	INDIA	00.056	369
2	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Sciences	INDIA	00.080	322
3	Indian-Journal-of-Experimental-Biology	INDIA		232
4	Current-Science-Bangalore	INDIA	00.376	228
5	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Sciences	INDIA	00.043	185
6	Journal-of-the-Bombay-Natural-History-Society	INDIA		153
7	Crop-Research-Hisar	INDIA		152
8	Indian-Forester	INDIA		139
9	Advances-in-Plant-Sciences	INDIA		123
10	Indian-Journal-of-Agronomy	INDIA	00.020	118
11	Journal-of-Food-Science-and-Technology	INDIA	00.113	111
12	Indian-Veterinary-Medical-Journal	INDIA		103
13	Journal-of-Medicinal-and-Aromatic-Plant-Sciences	INDIA		93
14	Journal-of-Maharashtra-Agricultural-Universities	INDIA		93
15	Indian-Journal-of-Pharmaceutical-Sciences	INDIA		90
16	Agricultural-Science-Digest	INDIA		90
17	Journal-of-Mycology-and-Plant-Pathology	INDIA		81
18	Indian-Journal-of-Plant-Physiology	INDIA		78
19	Journal-of-Human-Ecology	INDIA		77
20	Indian-Journal-of-Genetics-and-Plant-Breeding	INDIA		77
21	International-Rice-Research-Notes	PHILIPPINES		73
22	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Nutrition	INDIA		73
23	Indian-Journal-of-Medical-Research	INDIA	00.318	72
24	Journal-of-Entomological-Research-New-Delhi	INDIA		65
25	Journal-of-Economic-and-Taxonomic-Biology	INDIA		65

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
	otany			
26	Indian-Journal-of-Marine-Sciences	INDIA	00.099	64
27	Tetrahedron-Letters	ENGLAND	02.500	62
28	Journal-of-Biosciences-Bangalore	INDIA	00.435	61
29	Indian-Journal-of-Pharmacology	INDIA		60
30	Geobios-Jodhpur	INDIA		60
31	Indian-Journal-of-Physiology-and-Pharmacology	INDIA		58
32	Journal-of-Environmental-Biology	INDIA	00.061	53
33	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	INDIA		52
34	Entomon-	INDIA		51
35	Medical-Science-Research	ENGLAND	00.367	50
36	Fitoterapia-	ITALY		50
37	Seed-Research-New-Delhi	INDIA		47
38	Phytochemistry-Oxford	ENGLAND	01.165	47
39	Journal-of-Phytological-Research	INDIA		46
40	Annals-of-Biology-Hissar	INDIA		46
41	Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biology-International	AUSTRALIA	00.578	45
42	World-Journal-of-Microbiology-and-Biotechnology	NETHERLANDS	00.746	41
43	Indian-Journal-of-Sericulture	INDIA		41
44	Phytomorphology-	INDIA		39
45	Journal-of-Nuclear-Agriculture-and-Biology	INDIA		38
46	Journal-of-Communicable-Diseases	INDIA		38
47	Indian-Journal-of-Ophthalmology	INDIA		37
48	Bioprocess-Engineering	GERMANY	00.528	34
49	National-Medical-Journal-of-India	INDIA		33
50	Indian-Journal-of-Physiology-and-Allied-Sciences	INDIA		32
51	Biochemical-and-Biophysical-Research-Communications	UNITED STATES	02.671	31
52	Plant-Cell-Reports	GERMANY	00.967	30
53	Bulletin-of-Environmental-Contamination-and-Toxicology	UNITED STATES	00.635	29
54	Indian-Journal-of-Cancer	INDIA		28
55	Crop-Improvement	INDIA		28
56	Tetrahedron-	ENGLAND	02.327	27
57	PKV-Research-Journal	INDIA		27
58	Journal-of-Biological-Control	INDIA		27
59	Indian-Journal-of-Pediatrics	INDIA		27

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
60	Bioresource-Technology	ENGLAND	00.632	27
61	Biochimica-et-Biophysica-Acta	NETHERLANDS	02.411	27
62	Molecular-and-Cellular-Biochemistry	NETHERLANDS	01.345	26
63	Journal-of-Veterinary-and-Animal-Sciences	INDIA		25
64	Journal-of-Agronomy-and-Crop-Science	GERMANY	00.225	25
65	Journal-of-Advanced-Zoology	INDIA	00.057	25
66	Uttar-Pradesh-Journal-of-Zoology	INDIA		24
67	Talanta-	ENGLAND	01.149	24
68	Journal-of-Ethnopharmacology	SWITZERLAND	00.578	24
69	International-Journal-of-Cardiology	NETHERLANDS	00.610	24
70	Indian-Journal-of-Poultry-Science	INDIA		24
71	Cancer-Letters	NETHERLANDS	01.440	24
72	International-Journal-of-Tropical-Agriculture	INDIA		22
73	Journal-of-Plant-Biochemistry-and-Biotechnology	INDIA	00.136	21
74	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Surgery	INDIA		21
75	Biologia-Plantarum-Prague	CZECH REPUBLIC	00.393	21
76	Tropical-Doctor	ENGLAND	00.234	20
77	Rheedea-	INDIA		20
78	Journal-of-the-Indian-Potato-Association	INDIA		20
79	Indian-Journal-of-Environmental-Health	INDIA		20
80	Fishery-Technology	INDIA		20
81	Proceedings-of-the-Zoological-Society-Calcutta	INDIA		19
82	Proceedings-of-the-National-Academy-of-Sciences-India-Section-B-Biological-Sciences	INDIA		19
83	Mutation-Research	NETHERLANDS	01.754	19
84	Journal-of-Biomolecular-Structure-and-Dynamics	UNITED STATES	01.283	19
85	Indian-Fern-Journal	INDIA		19
86	BJU-	ENGLAND		19
87	Crop-Science	UNITED STATES	00.801	18
88	Asian-Australasian-Journal-of-Animal-Sciences	SOUTH COREA		18
89	Plant-Science-Shannon	IRELAND	01.274	17
90	Journal-of-Clinical-Biochemistry-and-Nutrition	JAPAN	00.234	17

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
91	Indian-Journal-of-Malariology	INDIA		17
92	FEMS-Microbiology-Letters	NETHERLANDS	01.560	17
93	British-Journal-of-Neurosurgery	ENGLAND	00.502	17
94	Small-Ruminant-Research	NETHERLANDS	00.306	16
95	FEBS-Letters	NETHERLANDS	03.504	16
96	Euphytica-	NETHERLANDS	00.768	16
97	Burns-	ENGLAND	00.483	16
98	Annals-of-Applied-Biology	ENGLAND	00.494	16
99	Journal-of-Aquaculture-in-the-Tropics	INDIA		15
100	Indian-Journal-of-Natural-Rubber-Research	INDIA		15
101	Bionature-	INDIA		15
102	Acta-Physiologiae-Plantarum	POLAND	00.444	15
103	Acta-Cytologica	UNITED STATES	01.425	15
104	Transplantation-Proceedings	UNITED STATES	00.698	14
105	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-National-Science-Academy-Part-B-Biological-Sciences	INDIA		14
106	Pharmacy-and-Pharmacology-Communications	ENGLAND		14
107	Leprosy-Review	ENGLAND	00.607	14
108	International-Journal-of-Gynecology-and-Obstetrics	NETHERLANDS	00.402	14
109	Folia-Microbiologica	CZECH REPUBLIC	00.312	14
110	Cytobios-	ENGLAND		14
111	Biological-Memoirs	INDIA		14
112	Agricultural-Water-Management	NETHERLANDS	00.320	14
113	Veterinary-Research-Communications	NETHERLANDS	00.613	13
114	Theoretical-and-Applied-Genetics	GERMANY	02.040	13
115	Journal-of-the-Science-of-Food-and-Agriculture	ENGLAND	00.895	13
116	Journal-of-Agricultural-and-Food-Chemistry	UNITED STATES	01.502	13
117	Food-Chemistry	ENGLAND	00.812	13
118	Cytologia-Tokyo	JAPAN		13
119	Contraception-	FRANCE	00.194	13
120	Research-Bulletin-of-the-Panjab-University-Science	INDIA		12
121	Journal-of-the-Neurological-Sciences	NETHERLANDS	01.453	12
122	Journal-of-Plant-Physiology	GERMANY	01.179	12
123	Biotechnology-Letters	NETHERLANDS	00.848	12
124	Biochemistry-	CANADA	01.581	12
125	Southeast-Asian-Journal-of-Tropical-	THAILAND		11

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
	Medicine-and-Public-Health			
126	Plant-and-Soil	NETHERLANDS	01.193	11
127	Pharmacological-Research	ENGLAND	00.470	11
128	Mycotaxon-	UNITED STATES	00.405	11
129	Journal-of-the-American-Oil-Chemists '-Society	UNITED STATES	01.203	11
130	Journal-of-Genetics-and-Breeding	ITALY		11
131	Journal-of-Dermatology-Tokyo	JAPAN		11
132	International-Journal-of-Remote-Sensi ng	ENGLAND	00.771	11
133	International-Journal-of-Dermatology	UNITED STATES	00.676	11
134	Diagnostic-Cytopathology	UNITED STATES	01.154	11
135	Acta-Agronomica-Hungarica	HUNGARY		11
136	Water-Air-and-Soil-Pollution	NETHERLANDS	00.964	10
137	Tropical-Ecology	INDIA		10
138	Plant-Disease	UNITED STATES	00.717	10
139	Photosynthetica-Prague	CZECH REPUBLIC	00.941	10
140	Journal-of-Clinical-Microbiology	UNITED STATES	03.783	10
141	International-Journal-of-Food-Science s-and-Nutrition	ENGLAND	00.506	10
142	Biophysical-Chemistry	NETHERLANDS	01.596	10
143	Bioorganic-and-Medicinal-Chemistry- Letters	ENGLAND	01.628	10
144	Animal-Feed-Science-and-Technology	NETHERLANDS	00.587	10
145	Anesthesia-and-Analgesia	UNITED STATES	02.830	10
146	Analytical-Letters	UNITED STATES	01.000	10
147	Tropical-Animal-Health-and-Productio n	SCOTLAND	00.150	9
148	Pediatric-Hematology-and-Oncology	UNITED STATES	00.620	9
149	Mycoses-	GERMANY	00.524	9
150	Mycological-Research	ENGLAND	01.099	9
151	Journal-of-Laryngology-and-Otology	ENGLAND	00.408	9
152	Journal-of-Gastroenterology-and-Hepa tology	AUSTRALIA	00.954	9
153	Journal-of-Chromatography-B	NETHERLANDS	01.588	9
154	Journal-of-Chemical-Technology-and- Biotechnology	ENGLAND	00.766	9
155	Journal-of-Applied-Toxicology	ENGLAND	00.487	9
156	European-Journal-of-Biochemistry	UNITED STATES	03.136	9
157	Biomass-and-Bioenergy	ENGLAND	00.163	9
158	Agricultural-and-Biological-Research	INDIA		9
159	Soil-Biology-and-Biochemistry	ENGLAND	01.326	8
160	Pharmazie-	GERMANY	00.504	8

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
161	Nutrition-Research	UNITED STATES	00.627	8
162	Neurochemical-Research	UNITED STATES	01.310	8
163	Mycopathologia-	NETHERLANDS	00.525	8
164	Journal-of-Pharmaceutical-and-Biomed- ical-Analysis	ENGLAND	01.046	8
165	Journal-of-Food-Engineering	ENGLAND	00.697	8
166	Genetic-Resources-and-Crop-Evolutio n	NETHERLANDS	00.432	8
167	Gene-Amsterdam	NETHERLANDS	01.838	8
168	Fresenius'-Journal-of-Analytical-Che mistry	GERMANY	01.398	8
169	Carbohydrate-Research	NETHERLANDS	01.437	8
170	Biological-Trace-Element-Research	UNITED STATES	00.745	8
171	Asia-Pacific-Journal-of-Pharmacology	SINGAPORE		8
172	Acta-Psychiatrica-Scandinavica	DENMARK	01.588	8
173	Zeitschrift-fuer-Pflanzenkrankheiten- und-Pflanzenschutz	GERMANY		7
174	Water-Research	ENGLAND	01.512	7
175	Tropical-Medicine-and-International- Health	ENGLAND	00.980	7
176	Spectrochimica-Acta-Part-A-Molecular -and-Biomolecular-Spectroscopy	ENGLAND		7
177	Protein-Expression-and-Purification	UNITED STATES	01.341	7
178	Postgraduate-Medical-Journal	ENGLAND	00.496	7
179	Plant-Growth-Regulation	NETHERLANDS	00.803	7
180	Plant-Breeding	GERMANY	00.675	7
181	Oriental-Insects	INDIA	00.133	7
182	Leukemia-Research	ENGLAND	01.337	7
183	Lancet-North-American-Edition	ENGLAND	16.135	7
184	Journal-of-Planar-Chromatography - Modern-TLC	GERMANY		7
185	Journal-of-Endocrinology-and-Reprod uction	UNKNOWN		7
186	Journal-of-Applied-Animal-Research	INDIA	00.188	7
187	Journal-of-Agricultural-Science	ENGLAND	00.701	7
188	Food-and-Chemical-Toxicology	ENGLAND	01.217	7
189	Digestive-Diseases-and-Sciences	UNITED STATES	01.875	7
190	Current-Microbiology	UNITED STATES	01.011	7
191	Child's-Nervous-System	GERMANY	00.471	7
192	Canadian-Journal-of-Microbiology	CANADA	01.243	7
193	Biomedical-and-Environmental-Scienc es	UNITED STATES		7
194	Biochemical-Pharmacology	UNITED STATES	02.443	7

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
195	Aquaculture-Research	ENGLAND		7
196	Annals-of-Tropical-Paediatics	ENGLAND	00.411	7
197	Annals-of-Tropical-Medicine-and-Parasitology	ENGLAND	00.901	7
198	Toxicon-	ENGLAND	01.150	6
199	Psychopharmacology-	UNITED STATES	01.816	6
200	Protein-and-Peptide-Letters	UNKNOWN		6
201	Pharmaceutical-Biology	NETHERLANDS		6
202	Pesticide-Science	ENGLAND	00.798	6
203	Nephrology-Dialysis-Transplantation	ENGLAND	01.682	6
204	Malaysian-Applied-Biology	MALAYSIA		6
205	Journal-of-the-American-Mosquito-Control-Association	UNITED STATES	00.421	6
206	Journal-of-Peptide-Research	DENMARK	A	6
207	Journal-of-Neurology-Neurosurgery-and-Psychiatry	ENGLAND	03.041	6
208	Journal-of-Chromatography-A	NETHERLANDS	02.697	6
209	Journal-of-Biological-Chemistry	UNITED STATES	06.963	6
210	Journal-of-Bacteriology	UNITED STATES	03.639	6
211	International-Journal-of-Pharmaceuticals-Amsterdam	NETHERLANDS	00.898	6
212	International-Journal-of-Biometeorology	NETHERLANDS	00.609	6
213	Indian-Journal-of-Natural-Products	INDIA		6
214	In-Vitro-Cellular-and-Developmental-Biology-Plant	UNITED STATES	00.568	6
215	Immunology-Letters	NETHERLANDS	01.096	6
216	Grana-	SWEDEN	00.523	6
217	Free-Radical-Biology-and-Medicine	UNITED STATES	03.528	6
218	Forest-Ecology-and-Management	NETHERLANDS	00.837	6
219	Forensic-Science-International	IRELAND	01.322	6
220	Environmental-Pollution	ENGLAND	01.267	6
221	Diabetes-Research-and-Clinical-Practice	NETHERLANDS	00.959	6
222	Crop-Protection	ENGLAND	00.525	6
223	Comparative-Biochemistry-and-Physiology-A	UNITED STATES	00.748	6
224	Clinical-Nuclear-Medicine	UNITED STATES	00.340	6
225	Clinica-Chimica-Acta	NETHERLANDS	01.067	6
226	Cell-Biology-International	ENGLAND	01.124	6
227	Brain-Research	NETHERLANDS	02.119	6
228	Biotechnology-and-Applied-Biochemistry	UNITED STATES	00.885	6

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
229	Biology-and-Fertility-of-Soils	GERMANY	01.003	6
230	Biogenic-Amines	NETHERLANDS	00.466	6
231	Applied-Microbiology-and-Biotechnology	UNITED STATES	01.331	6
232	Annals-of-Thoracic-Surgery	UNITED STATES	02.053	6
233	Agroforestry-Systems	NETHERLANDS	00.559	6
234	Acta-Dermato-Venereologica	SWEDEN	01.091	6
235	Trace-Elements-and-Electrolytes	GERMANY		5
236	Theriogenology-	UNITED STATES	01.727	5
237	Seed-Science-and-Technology	NETHERLANDS	00.224	5
238	Scandinavian-Journal-of-Gastroenterology	NORWAY	01.641	5
239	Retina-	UNITED STATES	00.836	5
240	Protein-Engineering	ENGLAND	01.631	5
241	Ophthalmology-	UNITED STATES	02.408	5
242	Nutrient-Cycling-in-Agroecosystems	NETHERLANDS	00.333	5
243	Neuroscience-Letters	NETHERLANDS	01.768	5
244	Nephron-	SWITZERLAND	01.405	5
245	Neoplasma-Bratislava	SLOVAKIA	00.385	5
246	Microbiological-Research	GERMANY	00.544	5
247	Medical-and-Biological-Engineering-and-Computing	ENGLAND	00.653	5
248	Letters-in-Applied-Microbiology	ENGLAND	01.008	5
249	Journal-of-Pharmacy-and-Pharmacology	ENGLAND	00.771	5
250	Journal-of-Molecular-Biology	UNITED STATES	05.673	5
251	Journal-of-Genetics	INDIA	00.317	5
252	Journal-of-Diarrhoeal-Diseases-Research	BANGLADESH	00.300	5
253	Journal-of-Controlled-Release	NETHERLANDS	01.493	5
254	Journal-of-Applied-Microbiology	ENGLAND		5
255	Journal-of-Antibiotics-Tokyo	JAPAN	01.523	5
256	International-Journal-of-Pest-Management	ENGLAND	00.162	5
257	Infection-and-Immunity	UNITED STATES	03.713	5
258	Hepato-Gastroenterology	GERMANY	00.705	5
259	General-and-Comparative-Endocrinology	UNITED STATES	01.550	5
260	Field-Crops-Research	NETHERLANDS	00.687	5
261	Enzyme-and-Microbial-Technology	UNITED STATES	01.223	5
262	Environmental-Toxicology-and-Pharmacology	NETHERLANDS	00.467	5
263	Dermatology-Basel	SWITZERLAND	00.719	5

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
264	Contact-Dermatitis	DENMARK	01.130	5
265	Comparative-Biochemistry-and-Physiology-C-Pharmacology-Toxicology-and-Endocrinology	ENGLAND	00.813	5
266	Communications-in-Soil-Science-and-Plant-Analysis	UNITED STATES	00.430	5
267	Clinical-and-Experimental-Immunology	ENGLAND	02.506	5
268	Chemosphere-	ENGLAND	01.145	5
269	Biometals-	NETHERLANDS	00.854	5
270	Biomedical-Letters	ENGLAND		5
271	Biochemical-Journal	ENGLAND	03.579	5
272	Annals-of-Botany-London	ENGLAND	01.301	5
273	Andrologia-	GERMANY	00.388	5
274	Analytical-Biochemistry	UNITED STATES	02.017	5
275	Acta-Tropica	SWITZERLAND	00.891	5
276	Acta-Ophthalmologica-Scandinavica	DENMARK	00.465	5
277	Zeitschrift-fuer-Naturforschung-Section-C-Journal-of-Biosciences	GERMANY		4
278	Waste-Management	UNITED STATES	00.181	4
279	Veterinary-Parasitology	NETHERLANDS	01.147	4
280	Veterinarski-Arhiv	CROATIA		4
281	Vaccine-	ENGLAND	01.949	4
282	Tumori-	ITALY	00.408	4
283	Toxicology-Letters-Shannon	IRELAND	01.128	4
284	Texas-Heart-Institute-Journal	UNITED STATES	00.508	4
285	Symbiosis-	ISRAEL	00.918	4
286	Soil-and-Tillage-Research	NETHERLANDS	00.610	4
287	Science-of-the-Total-Environment	NETHERLANDS	00.947	4
288	Renal-Failure	UNITED STATES	00.387	4
289	Proteins-	UNITED STATES	04.161	4
290	Protein-Science	UNITED STATES	04.600	4
291	Prostaglandins-Leukotrienes-and-Essential-Fatty-Acids	SCOTLAND	01.250	4
292	Planta-Medica	GERMANY	01.430	4
293	Plant-Physiology-Rockville	UNITED STATES	04.311	4
294	Plant-Foods-for-Human-Nutrition-Dordrecht	NETHERLANDS	00.310	4
295	Plant-Cell-Tissue-and-Organ-Culture	NETHERLANDS	00.540	4
296	PINSA-B	UNKNOWN		4
297	Nucleic-Acids-Research	ENGLAND	04.188	4
298	Nordic-Journal-of-Botany	DENMARK	00.148	4
299	Neurochemistry-International	ENGLAND	01.705	4

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
300	Mutagenesis-	ENGLAND	01.802	4
301	Microbiology-Reading	ENGLAND		4
302	Methods-and-Findings-in-Experimental-and-Clinical-Pharmacology	SPAIN	00.237	4
303	Mechanisms-of-Ageing-and-Development	SWITZERLAND	01.143	4
304	Journal-of-Urology	UNITED STATES	02.719	4
305	Journal-of-Surgical-Oncology	UNITED STATES	00.774	4
306	Journal-of-Plant-Growth-Regulation	UNITED STATES	00.887	4
307	Journal-of-Plant-Biology	SOUTH KOREA		4
308	Journal-of-Photochemistry-and-Photobiology-B-Biology	SWITZERLAND	01.381	4
309	Journal-of-Inorganic-Biochemistry	UNITED STATES	01.342	4
310	Journal-of-Industrial-Microbiology-and-Biotechnology	ENGLAND	01.199	4
311	Journal-of-General-and-Applied-Microbiology	JAPAN	00.634	4
312	Journal-of-Fermentation-and-Bioengineering	JAPAN	00.798	4
313	Journal-of-Arid-Environments	UNITED STATES	00.570	4
314	Journal-of-Applied-Entomology	GERMANY	00.366	4
315	International-Journal-of-STD-and-AIDS	ENGLAND	00.724	4
316	International-Journal-of-Clinical-Pharmacology-and-Therapeutics	GERMANY	00.519	4
317	International-Journal-of-Biochemistry-and-Cell-Biology	ENGLAND	01.229	4
318	Insect-Science-and-its-Application	KENYA		4
319	In-Vitro-Cellular-and-Developmental-Biology-Animal	UNITED STATES	01.256	4
320	Human-Reproduction-Oxford	ENGLAND	02.421	4
321	Flavour-and-Fragrance-Journal	ENGLAND		4
322	Farmaco-Lausanne	SWITZERLAND	00.446	4
323	FEMS-Immunology-and-Medical-Microbiology	NETHERLANDS	01.096	4
324	European-Journal-of-Obstetrics-and-Gynecology-and-Reproductive-Biology	NETHERLANDS	00.549	4
325	Environmental-Technology	ENGLAND	00.670	4
326	Environmental-Geology-Berlin	GERMANY	00.325	4
327	Endocrine-Research	UNITED STATES	00.665	4
328	Electro--and-Magnetobiology	UNITED STATES	00.729	4
329	Clinical-Neurology-and-Neurosurgery	NETHERLANDS	00.613	4
330	Clinical-Hemorheology-and-Microcirculation	NETHERLANDS	00.270	4

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
	lation			
331	Caryologia-	ITALY	00.221	4
332	Carbohydrate-Polymers	ENGLAND	00.956	4
333	Cancer-Genetics-and-Cytogenetics	UNITED STATES	01.489	4
334	Bulletin-of-the-World-Health-Organiz ation	SWITZERLAND	01.702	4
335	Brain-Research-Bulletin	ENGLAND	01.708	4
336	Biotechnology-Techniques	NETHERLANDS	00.534	4
337	Biotechnology-Progress	UNITED STATES	01.431	4
338	Biophysical-Journal	UNITED STATES	04.332	4
339	Biological-Signals-and-Receptors	SWITZERLAND		4
340	Biological-Rhythm-Research	NETHERLANDS	00.716	4
341	Biologia-Bratislava	SLOVAKIA		4
342	Bioelectrochemistry-and-Bioenergetics	SWITZERLAND	01.049	4
343	Arid-Soil-Research-and-Rehabilitation	UNITED STATES	00.299	4
344	Archives-of-Virology	AUSTRIA	01.479	4
345	Archives-of-Biochemistry-and-Biophys ics	UNITED STATES	02.649	4
346	Aquaculture-	NETHERLANDS	00.996	4
347	Anti-Cancer-Drugs	ENGLAND	00.985	4
348	Analytica-Chimica-Acta	NETHERLANDS	01.778	4
349	American-Journal-of-Tropical-Medicin e-and-Hygiene	UNITED STATES	01.964	4
350	Acta-Virologica	CZECH REPUBLIC	00.454	4
351	Acta-Phytopathologica-et-Entomologic a-Hungarica	HUNGARY		4
352	Acta-Paediatrica	SWEDEN	00.810	4
353	Acta-Neurologica-Scandinavica	DENMARK	00.902	4
354	Acta-Geneticae-Medicae-et-Gemellolog iae	ITALY		4
355	Acta-Crystallographica-Section-D-Biol ogical-Crystallography	DENMARK	02.118	4
356	Acta-Botanica-Hungarica	HUNGARY		4
357	Zeitschrift-fuer-Lebensmittel-Untersu chung-und -Forschung-A	GERMANY		3
358	Yeast-	ENGLAND	02.442	3
359	Surgical-Neurology	UNITED STATES	00.328	3
360	Surgery-Today-Tokyo	JAPAN	00.233	3
361	Spinal-Cord	ENGLAND	00.330	3
362	Sleep-Rochester	UNITED STATES	01.678	3
363	Scientia-Horticulturae-Amsterdam	NETHERLANDS	00.414	3
364	Plant-Physiology-and-Biochemistry-Pa ris	FRANCE	01.613	3

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
365	Plant-Pathology-Oxford	ENGLAND	01.070	3
366	Plant-Molecular-Biology	NETHERLANDS	02.852	3
367	Pigment-Cell-Research	UNITED STATES	00.917	3
368	Phytoparasitica-	ISRAEL	01.000	3
369	Pediatric-Neurosurgery	SWITZERLAND	00.656	3
370	Nutrition-and-Cancer	UNITED STATES	02.024	3
371	Nucleosides-and-Nucleotides	UNITED STATES		3
372	New-Forests	NETHERLANDS		3
373	Neurosurgery-Baltimore	UNITED STATES	01.113	3
374	Mycorrhiza-	UNITED STATES	00.683	3
375	Molecular-and-General-Genetics	GERMANY	02.749	3
376	Molecular-and-Chemical-Neuropathology	UNITED STATES	00.780	3
377	Molecular-Reproduction-and-Development	UNITED STATES	02.189	3
378	Milchwissenschaft-	GERMANY	00.626	3
379	Life-Sciences	ENGLAND	02.275	3
380	Land-Degradation-and-Development	ENGLAND	00.574	3
381	Journal-of-Theoretical-Biology	UNITED STATES	01.409	3
382	Journal-of-Psychosomatic-Research	ENGLAND	01.006	3
383	Journal-of-Plant-Nutrition	UNITED STATES	00.385	3
384	Journal-of-Oral-Pathology-and-Medicine	DENMARK	00.918	3
385	Journal-of-Obstetrics-and-Gynaecology-Abingdon	ENGLAND		3
386	Journal-of-Neurosurgery	UNITED STATES	02.999	3
387	Journal-of-Microbiology-and-Biotechnology	SINGAPORE	00.226	3
388	Journal-of-Invertebrate-Pathology	UNITED STATES	01.069	3
389	Journal-of-Herpetology	UNITED STATES	00.404	3
390	Journal-of-Epidemiology-and-Community-Health	ENGLAND	01.531	3
391	Journal-of-Environmental-Science-and-Health-Part-B-Pesticides-Food-Contaminants-and-Agricultural-Wastes	UNITED STATES	00.612	3
392	Journal-of-Endocrinology	ENGLAND	02.250	3
393	Journal-of-Cereal-Science	ENGLAND	01.496	3
394	Journal-of-Cardiovascular-Surgery	ITALY	00.685	3
395	Journal-of-Biotechnology	NETHERLANDS	01.111	3
396	Journal-of-Biosocial-Science	ENGLAND		3
397	JPGN-	UNITED STATES		3
398	Israel-Journal-of-Plant-Sciences	ISRAEL	00.441	3
399	International-Pest-Control	ENGLAND		3

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
400	International-Ophthalmology	NETHERLANDS	00.300	3
401	International-Journal-of-Pediatric-Oto rhinolaryngology	NETHERLANDS	00.309	3
402	International-Journal-of-Food-Science- and-Technology	ENGLAND	00.545	3
403	International-Journal-of-Food-Microbi ology	NETHERLANDS	01.160	3
404	International-Journal-of-Cancer	SWITZERLAND	03.362	3
405	International-Journal-of-Biological-Ma cromolecules	NETHERLANDS	01.145	3
406	Injury-	ENGLAND	00.257	3
407	Immunology-and-Cell-Biology	AUSTRALIA	00.909	3
408	Hydrobiologia-	NETHERLANDS	00.526	3
409	Histopathology-Oxford	ENGLAND	01.544	3
410	Herpetological-Review	UNITED STATES		3
411	Geoderma-	NETHERLANDS	00.839	3
412	Fundamental-and-Applied-Nematolog y	FRANCE	00.589	3
413	Food-Research-International	UNITED STATES	00.630	3
414	Feddes-Repertorium	GERMANY		3
415	European-Journal-of-Pharmacology	NETHERLANDS	01.960	3
416	Epidemiology-and-Infection	ENGLAND	01.480	3
417	Environmental-Conservation	ENGLAND	00.610	3
418	Entomologia-Generalis	GERMANY	00.283	3
419	Electroencephalography-and-Clinical- Neurophysiology	NETHERLANDS	02.400	3
420	Ecotoxicology-and-Environmental-Safe ty	ENGLAND	00.959	3
421	Ecological-Modelling	NETHERLANDS	00.668	3
422	Drug-and-Chemical-Toxicology-an-Int ernational-Journal-for-Rapid-Commun ication	UNITED STATES	00.526	3
423	DNA-and-Cell-Biology	UNITED STATES	02.128	3
424	Chemical-Speciation-and-Bioavailabili ty	ENGLAND	00.429	3
425	Cancer-Biotherapy-and-Radiopharmac euticals	UNITED STATES	00.792	3
426	Cancer-	UNITED STATES	03.296	3
427	Canadian-Journal-of-Anaesthesia	CANADA	01.316	3
428	British-Poultry-Science	ENGLAND	00.796	3
429	Biotechniques-	UNITED STATES	01.913	3
430	Biopolymers-	UNITED STATES	02.425	3
431	Biomedical-Research-Aligarh	INDIA		3

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
432	Biomedical-Chromatography	ENGLAND	01.171	3
433	Biochemical-Systematics-and-Ecology	ENGLAND	00.568	3
434	Biochemical-Archives	UNITED STATES	00.288	3
435	Atmospheric-Environment	ENGLAND	01.535	3
436	Arzneimittel-Forschung	GERMANY	00.627	3
437	Aquatic-Botany	NETHERLANDS	00.788	3
438	Applied-and-Environmental-Microbiology	UNITED STATES	03.336	3
439	Applied-Biochemistry-and-Biotechnology	UNITED STATES	00.747	3
440	Animal-Reproduction-Science	NETHERLANDS	00.930	3
441	Anatomical-Record	UNITED STATES	01.208	3
442	American-Journal-of-Reproductive-Immunology	UNITED STATES	01.858	3
443	American-Journal-of-Medical-Genetics	UNITED STATES	01.977	3
444	American-Journal-of-Clinical-Oncology	UNITED STATES	00.769	3
445	Acta-Pharmaceutica-Zagreb	CROATIA		3
446	Acta-Parasitologica	POLAND		3
447	Acta-Medica-Auxologica-Milan	ITALY		3
448	Acta-Biotechnologica	GERMANY	00.463	3
449	Acta-Alimentaria	HUNGARY	00.220	3
450	Vox-Sanguinis	SWITZERLAND	01.598	2
451	Veterinary-Immunology-and-Immunopathology	NETHERLANDS	00.867	2
452	Urologia-Internationalis	SWITZERLAND	00.348	2
453	Tubercle-and-Lung-Disease	ENGLAND		2
454	Thrombosis-Research	UNITED STATES	01.461	2
455	Taxon-	NETHERLANDS	01.149	2
456	Taiwania-	TAIWAN		2
457	Systematic-Parasitology	NETHERLANDS	00.645	2
458	Starch-	GERMANY	00.647	2
459	Soil-Use-and-Management	ENGLAND	00.595	2
460	Social-Biology	UNITED STATES		2
461	Skin-Pharmacology-and-Applied-Skin-Physiology	SWITZERLAND		2
462	Silvae-Genetica	GERMANY	00.463	2
463	Sexually-Transmitted-Infections	UNITED STATES		2
464	Sexually-Transmitted-Diseases	UNITED STATES	02.037	2
465	Scandinavian-Journal-of-Rheumatology	SWEDEN	00.855	2
466	Saudi-Medical-Journal	SAUDI ARABIA	00.162	2
467	Revista-Brasileira-de-Biologia	BRAZIL		2

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
468	Resources-Conservation-and-Recycling	NETHERLANDS	00.203	2
469	Research-in-Veterinary-Science	ENGLAND	00.983	2
470	Reproductive-Toxicology	UNITED STATES	00.829	2
471	Rapid-Communications-in-Mass-Spectrometry	ENGLAND	02.390	2
472	Radiotherapy-and-Oncology	NETHERLANDS	01.924	2
473	Radiation-and-Environmental-Biophysics	GERMANY	00.776	2
474	QJM-	ENGLAND	02.242	2
475	Prostate-	UNITED STATES	02.382	2
476	Proceedings-of-the-National-Academy-of-Sciences-of-the-United-States-of-America	UNITED STATES	09.040	2
477	Primates-	JAPAN	00.755	2
478	Preparative-Biochemistry-and-Biotechnology	UNITED STATES	00.472	2
479	Phytochemical-Analysis	ENGLAND	01.198	2
480	Physiological-Chemistry-and-Physics-and-Medical-NMR	UNITED STATES	00.279	2
481	Pharmacology-Biochemistry-and-Behavior	ENGLAND	01.480	2
482	Pharmacology-Basel	SWITZERLAND	01.148	2
483	Pesticide-Biochemistry-and-Physiology	UNITED STATES	01.058	2
484	Peptides-New-York	UNITED STATES	01.738	2
485	Pediatric-Cardiology	UNITED STATES	00.390	2
486	Pathology-	UNITED STATES	02.300	2
487	Parasitology-	ENGLAND	02.206	2
488	Parasitologia-Hungarica	HUNGARY		2
489	Outlook-on-Agriculture	ENGLAND	00.266	2
490	Otolaryngology - Head-and-Neck-Surgery	UNITED STATES		2
491	Oryx-	ENGLAND		2
492	Oecologia-Berlin	GERMANY	01.854	2
493	Nutrition-and-Health-Bicester	ENGLAND		2
494	Neurosurgical-Review	GERMANY	00.161	2
495	Neuroreport-	ENGLAND	02.262	2
496	Neuropeptides-	SCOTLAND	00.905	2
497	Neurologia-Medico-Chirurgica	JAPAN		2
498	Nematologica-	NETHERLANDS	00.537	2
499	Naturwissenschaften-	GERMANY	01.171	2
500	Nature-London	ENGLAND	27.368	2
501	Natural-Toxins	UNITED STATES		2

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
502	Nahrung-	GERMANY	00.449	2
503	Mountain-Research-and-Development	UNITED STATES	00.317	2
504	Molecular-Breeding	NETHERLANDS	02.819	2
505	Molecular-Biology-Reports	NETHERLANDS	01.565	2
506	Microbiology-and-Immunology	JAPAN	01.083	2
507	Metal-Based-Drugs	ISRAEL		2
508	Medical-Oncology-Basingstoke	ENGLAND		2
509	Mathematical-Biosciences	UNITED STATES	00.791	2
510	Lupus-	ENGLAND	01.611	2
511	Lipids-	UNITED STATES	01.947	2
512	Laser-Therapy	ENGLAND		2
513	Journal-of-the-American-College-of-Nutrition	UNITED STATES	01.466	2
514	Journal-of-Zoological-Systematics-and-Evolutionary-Research	GERMANY	00.682	2
515	Journal-of-Virological-Methods	NETHERLANDS	01.623	2
516	Journal-of-Veterinary-Medicine-Series-B	GERMANY	00.662	2
517	Journal-of-Trauma-Injury-Infection-and-Critical-Care	UNITED STATES	01.339	2
518	Journal-of-South-Asian-Natural-History	UNKNOWN		2
519	Journal-of-Reproduction-and-Fertility	ENGLAND	02.038	2
520	Journal-of-Protein-Chemistry	UNITED STATES	01.060	2
521	Journal-of-Parasitology	UNITED STATES	01.188	2
522	Journal-of-Nutritional-Science-and-Vitaminology	JAPAN	00.680	2
523	Journal-of-Nutritional-Biochemistry	UNITED STATES	01.337	2
524	Journal-of-Neurology	GERMANY	01.976	2
525	Journal-of-Neurochemistry	UNITED STATES	04.234	2
526	Journal-of-Neural-Transmission	AUSTRIA	01.303	2
527	Journal-of-Microencapsulation	ENGLAND	00.775	2
528	Journal-of-Medical-Microbiology	SCOTLAND	01.525	2
529	Journal-of-Medical-Engineering-and-Technology	ENGLAND	00.533	2
530	Journal-of-Mass-Spectrometry	ENGLAND	02.403	2
531	Journal-of-Marine-Biotechnology	GERMANY		2
532	Journal-of-Interferon-and-Cytokine-Research	UNITED STATES	01.471	2
533	Journal-of-Hospital-Infection	ENGLAND	01.652	2
534	Journal-of-Hazardous-Materials	NETHERLANDS	00.608	2
535	Journal-of-General-Virology	ENGLAND	02.863	2
536	Journal-of-Food-Science	UNITED STATES	01.249	2

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
537	Journal-of-Fish-Biology	ENGLAND	00.918	2
538	Journal-of-Experimental-Zoology	UNITED STATES	00.960	2
539	Journal-of-Experimental-Botany	ENGLAND	01.988	2
540	Journal-of-Environmental-Science-and-Health-Part-A-Toxic-Hazardous-Substances-and-Environmental-Engineering	UNITED STATES	00.443	2
541	Journal-of-Environmental-Radioactivity	ENGLAND	00.638	2
542	Journal-of-Electrocardiology	UNITED STATES	00.223	2
543	Journal-of-Dispersion-Science-and-Technology	UNITED STATES	00.382	2
544	Journal-of-Clinical-Ultrasound	UNITED STATES	00.620	2
545	Journal-of-Child-Neurology	UNITED STATES	00.918	2
546	Journal-of-Chemical-Neuroanatomy	NETHERLANDS	01.667	2
547	Journal-of-Cardiovascular-Pharmacology	UNITED STATES	01.537	2
548	Journal-of-Cardiovascular-Electrophysiology	UNITED STATES	01.781	2
549	Journal-of-Carbohydrate-Chemistry	UNITED STATES	01.079	2
550	Journal-of-Biochemistry-Tokyo	JAPAN	01.875	2
551	Journal-of-Biochemical-and-Biophysical-Methods	NETHERLANDS	00.648	2
552	Journal-of-Asthma	UNITED STATES	00.791	2
553	Journal-of-Assisted-Reproduction-and-Genetics	UNITED STATES	00.820	2
554	Journal-of-Antimicrobial-Chemotherapy	ENGLAND	02.330	2
555	Journal-of-Analytical-Atomic-Spectrometry	ENGLAND	03.595	2
556	Journal-of-Affective-Disorders	NETHERLANDS	01.813	2
557	Journal-of-AOAC-International	UNITED STATES	01.138	2
558	Journal-de-Mycologie-Medicale	FRANCE	00.571	2
559	Japanese-Journal-of-Physiology	JAPAN	01.007	2
560	Japanese-Journal-of-Medical-Science-and-Biology	JAPAN	00.190	2
561	International-Urology-and-Nephrology	HUNGARY		2
562	International-Journal-of-Oral-and-Maxillofacial-Surgery	DENMARK	00.721	2
563	International-Journal-of-Immunopharmacology	ENGLAND	01.053	2
564	International-Journal-of-Dairy-Technology	ENGLAND		2

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
565	International-Journal-of-Acarology	UNITED STATES		2
566	International-Archives-of-Allergy-and-Immunology	SWITZERLAND	01.721	2
567	Immunopharmacology-and-Immunotoxicology	UNITED STATES	00.506	2
568	Immunology-	UNITED STATES	00.600	2
569	Human-and-Experimental-Toxicology	ENGLAND	00.716	2
570	Human-Biology	UNITED STATES	00.982	2
571	Hereditas-Lund	SWEDEN	00.400	2
572	Gynecologic-and-Obstetric-Investigation	SWITZERLAND	00.432	2
573	Genetic-Analysis-Biomolecular-Engineering	NETHERLANDS	00.696	2
574	General-Pharmacology	ENGLAND	01.056	2
575	Food-Microbiology-London	ENGLAND	01.085	2
576	Fett-	GERMANY	00.542	2
577	Experimental-and-Molecular-Medicine	SOUTH KOREA		2
578	Experimental-Neurology	UNITED STATES	03.450	2
579	Experimental-Agriculture	ENGLAND	00.538	2
580	European-Urology	SWITZERLAND	00.997	2
581	European-Journal-of-Immunology	UNITED STATES	05.256	2
582	European-Journal-of-Gynaecological-Oncology	ITALY		2
583	European-Journal-of-Clinical-Pharmacology	GERMANY	01.219	2
584	Epilepsia-	UNITED STATES	02.928	2
585	Environmental-and-Experimental-Botany	ENGLAND	00.545	2
586	Environmental-Monitoring-and-Assessment	NETHERLANDS	00.519	2
587	Environmental-Health-Perspectives	UNITED STATES	02.119	2
588	Environmental-Geochemistry-and-Health	NETHERLANDS	00.340	2
589	Entomologist's-Monthly-Magazine	ENGLAND		2
590	Energy-Sources	UNITED STATES	00.209	2
591	Ecoscience-	CANADA	00.917	2
592	Cytogenetics-and-Cell-Genetics	SWITZERLAND	02.466	2
593	Current-Genetics	UNITED STATES	01.924	2
594	Cryobiology-	UNITED STATES	01.250	2
595	Clinical-and-Experimental-Pharmacology-and-Physiology	AUSTRALIA	00.938	2
596	Clinical-and-Experimental-Dermatology	ENGLAND	00.587	2

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
597	Clinical-and-Experimental-Allergy	ENGLAND	02.559	2
598	Clinical-Pharmacology-and-Therapeutics	UNITED STATES	04.751	2
599	Clinical-Neuropathology	GERMANY	00.636	2
600	Climatic-Change	NETHERLANDS	01.532	2
601	Chemotherapy-	SWITZERLAND	00.709	2
602	Chemico-Biological-Interactions	NETHERLANDS	01.619	2
603	Chemical-and-Pharmaceutical-Bulletin-Tokyo	JAPAN	01.156	2
604	Cereal-Research-Communications	HUNGARY	00.207	2
605	Cellular-and-Molecular-Biology-Letters	POLAND		2
606	Cell-Biochemistry-and-Function	ENGLAND	00.882	2
607	Carcinogenesis-Oxford	ENGLAND	03.336	2
608	Cancer-Detection-and-Prevention	UNITED STATES	00.838	2
609	Cancer-Causes-and-Control	NETHERLANDS	03.562	2
610	British-Journal-of-Dermatology	ENGLAND	01.838	2
611	British-Journal-of-Cancer	ENGLAND	02.938	2
612	Brazilian-Journal-of-Medical-and-Biological-Research	BRAZIL	00.468	2
613	Biological-Research	CHILI		2
614	Biological-Psychiatry	UNITED STATES	02.254	2
615	Biological-Chemistry	GERMANY	02.551	2
616	Biological-Agriculture-and-Horticulture	ENGLAND	00.325	2
617	Bioinformatics-Oxford	ENGLAND		2
618	Behavioural-Processes	NETHERLANDS	00.607	2
619	Bangladesh-Journal-of-Zoology	BANGLADESH		2
620	BMJ-	ENGLAND	04.994	2
621	Australian-and-New-Zealand-Journal-of-Medicine	AUSTRALIA	00.556	2
622	Australian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	AUSTRALIA	00.851	2
623	Asian-Pacific-Journal-of-Allergy-and-Immunology	THAILAND	00.100	2
624	Artificial-Organs	UNITED STATES	00.893	2
625	Archives-of-Otolaryngology-Head-and-Neck-Surgery	UNITED STATES	01.054	2
626	Archives-of-Ophthalmology	UNITED STATES	02.476	2
627	Archives-of-Insect-Biochemistry-and-Physiology	UNITED STATES	01.246	2
628	Archives-of-Gynecology-and-Obstetrics	GERMANY	00.190	2
629	Archives-of-Environmental-Contamin	UNITED STATES	01.102	2

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
	ation-and-Toxicology			
630	Aquaculture-Nutrition	ENGLAND		2
631	Aqua-Oxford	ENGLAND		2
632	Applied-Organometallic-Chemistry	ENGLAND	01.130	2
633	Applied-Animal-Behaviour-Science	NETHERLANDS	00.920	2
634	Antimicrobial-Agents-and-Chemother apy	UNITED STATES	03.560	2
635	Anticancer-Research	GREECE	01.045	2
636	Annals-of-Hematology	GERMANY	01.475	2
637	Annals-Academy-of-Medicine-Singapo re	SINGAPORE		2
638	Annali-di-Chimica	ITALY	00.500	2
639	Anatomia-Histologia-Embryologia	GERMANY	00.117	2
640	Analytical-and-Quantitative-Cytology- and-Histology	UNITED STATES	00.964	2
641	American-Journal-of-Human-Biology	UNITED STATES	00.728	2
642	American-Fern-Journal	UNITED STATES	00.640	2
643	Allergy-Copenhagen	DENMARK	02.015	2
644	Alcohol-	ENGLAND	01.264	2
645	Agriculture-Ecosystems-and-Environ ment	NETHERLANDS	00.661	2
646	Agricultural-and-Forest-Meteorology	NETHERLANDS	01.570	2
647	Advances-in-Food-Sciences	GERMANY		2
648	Acta-Veterinaria-Hungarica	HUNGARY	00.321	2
649	Acta-Protozoologica	POLAND	00.500	2
650	Acta-Oncologica-Stockholm	SWEDEN	00.776	2
651	Acta-Neurochirurgica	AUSTRIA	00.623	2
652	Acta-Hydrochimica-et-Hydrobiologica	GERMANY		2
653	Acta-Haematologica-Basel	SWITZERLAND		2
654	Acta-Anatomica	SWITZERLAND	00.840	2
655	APMIS-	DENMARK	01.015	2
656	AJNR-	UNITED STATES	01.707	2
657	Zoological-Science-Tokyo	JAPAN	00.754	1
658	Zeitschrift-fuer-Pflanzenernaehrung-u nd-Bodenkunde	GERMANY		1
659	Zeitschrift-fuer-Morphologie-und-Anth ropologie	GERMANY		1
660	Xenobiotica-	ENGLAND	01.473	1
661	World-Animal-Review-Multilingual-E dition	ITALY		1
662	Weed-Technology	UNITED STATES	00.588	1
663	Weed-Research	ENGLAND	00.766	1
664	Water-Science-and-Technology	ENGLAND	00.775	1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
665	Water-Environment-Research	UNITED STATES	01.212	1
666	Virus-Research	NETHERLANDS	01.757	1
667	Virus-Genes	UNITED STATES	01.159	1
668	Virology-	UNITED STATES	03.540	1
669	Veterinary-Journal	ENGLAND		1
670	Tropical-Grasslands	AUSTRALIA	00.157	1
671	Trends-in-Ecology-and-Evolution	ENGLAND	06.678	1
672	Trees-Berlin	GERMANY		1
673	Transplantation-Baltimore	UNITED STATES	03.441	1
674	Toxicology-and-Industrial-Health	ENGLAND		1
675	Toxicology-	UNITED STATES	02.184	1
676	Tissue-Antigens	DENMARK	04.339	1
677	Thrombosis-and-Haemostasis	GERMANY	04.582	1
678	Teratogenesis-Carcinogenesis-and-Mu tagenesis	UNITED STATES	00.441	1
679	Tellus-Series-B-Chemical-and-Physica l-Meteorology	SWEDEN	02.011	1
680	Sydowia-	AUSTRIA		1
681	Surgery-St-Louis	UNITED STATES	02.109	1
682	Strahlentherapie-und-Onkologie	GERMANY		1
683	Steroids-	UNITED STATES	01.480	1
684	South-African-Journal-of-Science	SOUTH AFRICA	00.485	1
685	Somatosensory-and-Motor-Research	UNITED STATES	00.717	1
686	Senckenbergiana-Biologica	GERMANY		1
687	Schizophrenia-Bulletin	UNITED STATES	03.509	1
688	Scandinavian-Journal-of-Infectious-Di seases	SWEDEN	01.173	1
689	Scandinavian-Journal-of-Immunology	NORWAY	01.749	1
690	SMJ-	UNITED STATES		1
691	SIDA-Contributions-to-Botany	SWEDEN		1
692	Rheumatology-International	UNITED STATES	00.821	1
693	Revue-de-Stomatologie-et-de-Chirurgi e-Maxillo-Faciale	FRANCE		1
694	Revue-Scientifique-et-Technique-Offic e-International-des-Epizooties.	FRANCE		1
695	Revista-de-Microbiologia	BRAZIL	00.074	1
696	Revista-Iberoamericana-de-Micologia	SPAIN		1
697	Revista-Argentina-de-Microbiologia	ARGENTINA		1
698	Review-of-Palaeobotany-and-Palynolo gy	NETHERLANDS	00.623	1
699	Reproduction-in-Domestic-Animals	GERMANY	00.357	1
700	Reproduction-Fertility-and-Developme nt	AUSTRALIA	01.055	1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
701	Reichenbachia-	GERMANY		1
702	Quaternary-Research-Orlando	UNITED STATES	02.331	1
703	Progress-in-Neuro-Psychopharmacology-and-Biological-Psychiatry	UNITED STATES		1
704	Polish-Journal-of-Food-and-Nutrition-Sciences	POLAND		1
705	Platelets-Abingdon	SCOTLAND	00.659	1
706	Plant-and-Cell-Physiology	JAPAN	01.792	1
707	Plant-Systematics-and-Evolution	AUSTRIA	00.824	1
708	Plant-Species-Biology	JAPAN		1
709	Plant-Ecology	NETHERLANDS		1
710	Physiologia-Plantarum	DENMARK	01.797	1
711	Phycologia-	ENGLAND		1
712	Photochemistry-and-Photobiology	UNITED STATES	02.426	1
713	Philosophical-Transactions-of-the-Royal-Society-of-London-B-Biological-Sciences	ENGLAND	02.512	1
714	Pharmaceutical-and-Pharmacological-Letters	GERMANY		1
715	Pertanika-Journal-of-Tropical-Agricultural-Science	MALASIA		1
716	Persoonia-	NETHERLANDS	00.313	1
717	Pediatric-Research	UNITED STATES	02.661	1
718	Pediatric-Infectious-Disease-Journal	UNITED STATES	01.866	1
719	Pattern-Recognition	ENGLAND	00.781	1
720	Pathology-Research-and-Practice	GERMANY	00.753	1
721	Pathobiology-	SWITZERLAND	00.652	1
722	Parasitology-Today	NETHERLANDS	05.189	1
723	Parasitology-Research	GERMANY	00.948	1
724	Parasitology-International	NETHERLANDS		1
725	Palaeogeography-Palaeoclimatology-Palaeoecology	NETHERLANDS	01.319	1
726	Pakistan-Journal-of-Zoology	PAKISTAN		1
727	Pakistan-Journal-of-Scientific-and-Industrial-Research	PAKISTAN		1
728	Pakistan-Journal-of-Nematology	PAKISTAN		1
729	Ophthalmic-Research	SWITZERLAND	00.627	1
730	Oncology-Reports	GREECE	00.407	1
731	Odonatologica-	NETHERLANDS		1
732	Nuclear-Medicine-Communications	ENGLAND	01.011	1
733	Novon-	UNITED STATES		1
734	Nova-Hedwigia	GERMANY	00.392	1
735	Nitric-Oxide	UNKNOWN		1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
736	New-Zealand-Journal-of-Crop-and-Horticultural-Science	NEW ZEALAND	00.297	1
737	Neurotoxicology-and-Teratology	UNITED STATES		1
738	Neuroscience-	ENGLAND	02.786	1
739	Neurology-	UNITED STATES	04.526	1
740	Neuroepidemiology-	SWITZERLAND	01.397	1
741	Neural-Networks	ENGLAND	01.019	1
742	Netherlands-Journal-of-Zoology	NETHERLANDS	00.630	1
743	Mycologist-	ENGLAND		1
744	Mosquito-Borne-Diseases-Bulletin	THAILAND		1
745	Molecular-and-Cellular-Biology	UNITED STATES	10.025	1
746	Molecular-and-Biochemical-Parasitology	NETHERLANDS	02.123	1
747	Molecular-Pharmacology	UNITED STATES	04.921	1
748	Molecular-Immunology	ENGLAND	01.800	1
749	Middle-East-Journal-of-Anesthesiology	UNKNOWN		1
750	Micropaleontology-New-York	UNITED STATES	00.449	1
751	Microbios-	ENGLAND	00.400	1
752	Microbiologica-Pavia	UNKNOWN		1
753	Microbial-Pathogenesis	ENGLAND	01.307	1
754	Metabolism-Clinical-and-Experimental	UNITED STATES	01.681	1
755	Memorias-do-Instituto-Oswaldo-Cruz	BRAZIL	00.440	1
756	Melanoma-Research	ENGLAND	01.596	1
757	Medicine-Baltimore	UNITED STATES		1
758	Medical-and-Pediatric-Oncology	UNITED STATES	01.693	1
759	Medical-Mycology	ENGLAND		1
760	Medical-Microbiology-and-Immunology	GERMANY	02.000	1
761	Meat-Science	ENGLAND	00.861	1
762	Material-und-Organismen-Berlin	GERMANY	00.280	1
763	Marine-and-Freshwater-Research	AUSTRALIA	00.617	1
764	Marine-Ecology	GERMANY	01.923	1
765	Marine-Chemistry	NETHERLANDS	02.277	1
766	Mammalia-	UNITED STATES	02.069	1
767	Magnesium-Research	ENGLAND		1
768	Letters-in-Peptide-Science	NETHERLANDS		1
769	Lebensmittel-Wissenschaft-and-Technologie	ENGLAND		1
770	Kybernetes-	ENGLAND	00.172	1
771	Kidney-International	UNITED STATES	04.071	1
772	Journal-of-the-World-Aquaculture-Society	UNITED STATES		1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
773	Journal-of-the-Hattori-Botanical-Laboratory	JAPAN		1
774	Journal-of-the-American-College-of-Cardiology	UNITED STATES	06.704	1
775	Journal-of-the-American-Academy-of-Dermatology	UNITED STATES	01.891	1
776	Journal-of-Zoology-London	ENGLAND	00.852	1
777	Journal-of-Virology	UNITED STATES	05.821	1
778	Journal-of-Veterinary-Pharmacology-and-Therapeutics	ENGLAND	00.756	1
779	Journal-of-Veterinary-Medicine-Series-A	GERMANY	00.408	1
780	Journal-of-Vertebrate-Paleontology	UNITED STATES	01.036	1
781	Journal-of-UOEH	JAPAN		1
782	Journal-of-Trauma	UNITED STATES	01.339	1
783	Journal-of-Toxicology-Cutaneous-and-Ocular-Toxicology	UNITED STATES	00.368	1
784	Journal-of-Toxicology-Clinical-Toxicology	UNITED STATES	00.934	1
785	Journal-of-Toxicological-Sciences	JAPAN		1
786	Journal-of-Thoracic-and-Cardiovascular-Surgery	UNITED STATES	03.068	1
787	Journal-of-Thermal-Biology	ENGLAND	00.780	1
788	Journal-of-Taiwan-Museum	TAIWAN		1
789	Journal-of-Structural-Biology	UNITED STATES	03.036	1
790	Journal-of-Rheumatology	CANADA	02.172	1
791	Journal-of-Plant-Research	JAPAN	00.862	1
792	Journal-of-Plant-Pathology	ITALY		1
793	Journal-of-Phytopathology-Berlin	GERMANY	00.516	1
794	Journal-of-Pharmacological-and-Toxicological-Methods	UNITED STATES	00.802	1
795	Journal-of-Periodontology	UNITED STATES	01.976	1
796	Journal-of-Pediatrics	UNITED STATES	02.836	1
797	Journal-of-Paediatrics-and-Child-Health	AUSTRALIA	00.398	1
798	Journal-of-Otolaryngology	CANADA	00.279	1
799	Journal-of-Nuclear-Medicine	UNITED STATES	03.491	1
800	Journal-of-Neuroscience	UNITED STATES	07.915	1
801	Journal-of-Molluscan-Studies	ENGLAND	00.339	1
802	Journal-of-Molecular-Catalysis-B-Enzymatic	NETHERLANDS	01.132	1
803	Journal-of-Microbiological-Methods	NETHERLANDS	00.958	1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
804	Journal-of-Medicinal-Chemistry	UNITED STATES	03.615	1
805	Journal-of-Medical-Primatology	SWITZERLAND	00.892	1
806	Journal-of-Insect-Physiology	UNITED STATES	01.662	1
807	Journal-of-Hydrology-Amsterdam	NETHERLANDS	00.940	1
808	Journal-of-Horticultural-Science-and-Biotechnology	ENGLAND	00.416	1
809	Journal-of-Food-Protection	UNITED STATES	01.288	1
810	Journal-of-Fish-Diseases	ENGLAND	01.158	1
811	Journal-of-Eukaryotic-Microbiology	UNITED STATES	01.232	1
812	Journal-of-Environmental-Pathology-Toxicology-and-Oncology	UNITED STATES		1
813	Journal-of-Endourology	UNITED STATES	00.774	1
814	Journal-of-Cutaneous-Pathology	DENMARK	01.220	1
815	Journal-of-Clinical-Pathology-London	ENGLAND	01.427	1
816	Journal-of-Clinical-Immunology	UNITED STATES	02.078	1
817	Journal-of-Chromatographic-Science	UNITED STATES	01.696	1
818	Journal-of-Chemotherapy	ITALY	00.319	1
819	Journal-of-Chemical-Ecology	UNITED STATES	01.284	1
820	Journal-of-Cellular-Biochemistry	UNITED STATES	02.686	1
821	Journal-of-Cell-Biology	UNITED STATES	12.005	1
822	Journal-of-Cancer-Research-and-Clinical-Oncology	GERMANY	01.154	1
823	Journal-of-Biomechanics	ENGLAND	01.461	1
824	Journal-of-Biological-Systems	SINGAPORE		1
825	Journal-of-Biological-Education	UNITED STATES	00.230	1
826	Journal-of-Basic-Microbiology	GERMANY	00.519	1
827	Journal-of-Autoimmunity	ENGLAND	01.777	1
828	Journal-of-Applied-Ecology	ENGLAND	01.335	1
829	Journal-of-Animal-Breeding-and-Genetics	GERMANY	00.437	1
830	Journal-of-Andrology	UNITED STATES	01.780	1
831	Journal-of-Anatomy	ENGLAND	01.172	1
832	Journal-of-Acquired-Immune-Deficiency-Syndromes-and-Human-Retrovirology	UNITED STATES	02.573	1
833	Japanese-Journal-of-Pharmacology	JAPAN	01.201	1
834	JN-Journal-of-Nephrology	ITALY	00.490	1
835	Israel-Journal-of-Zoology	ISRAEL	00.510	1
836	Israel-Journal-of-Veterinary-Medicine	ISRAEL		1
837	Interviurology-	SWITZERLAND	00.787	1
838	International-Journal-of-Toxicology	ENGLAND		1
839	International-Journal-of-Systematic-Bacteriology	ENGLAND	03.724	1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
840	International-Journal-of-Radiation-On cology-Biology-Physics	UNITED STATES	02.636	1
841	International-Journal-of-Radiation-Bi ology	ENGLAND	01.915	1
842	International-Journal-of-Insect-Morph ology-and-Embryology	ENGLAND	00.400	1
843	International-Journal-of-Epidemiology	ENGLAND	01.630	1
844	International-Journal-of-Environment al-Health-Research	ENGLAND		1
845	International-Journal-of-Andrology	DENMARK	00.984	1
846	International-Journal-for-Vitamin-and -Nutrition-Research	SWITZERLAND	00.594	1
847	International-Clinical-Psychopharmac ology	ENGLAND	01.926	1
848	Internal-Medicine-Tokyo	JAPAN		1
849	Insectes-Sociaux	FRANCE	00.759	1
850	Insect-Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Bi ology	ENGLAND	02.094	1
851	In-Vivo-Attiki	GREECE		1
852	Immunopharmacology-	UNITED STATES	01.173	1
853	Immunological-Investigations	UNITED STATES	00.787	1
854	Immunologic-Research	UNITED STATES	01.935	1
855	Hybridoma-	UNITED STATES	00.458	1
856	Human-Reproduction-Update	ENGLAND	02.642	1
857	Human-Pathology	UNITED STATES	03.052	1
858	Human-Immunology	UNITED STATES	02.991	1
859	Hong-Kong-Medical-Journal	HONGKONG		1
860	Hikobia-	JAPAN		1
861	Hepatology-	IRELAND		1
862	Hematological-Oncology	ENGLAND	00.711	1
863	Helminthologia-Bratislava	SLOVAKIA	00.447	1
864	Heart-London	ENGLAND	01.443	1
865	Haematologia-	HUNGARY	00.098	1
866	Gynecologic-Oncology	UNITED STATES	01.542	1
867	Gut-	ENGLAND	04.546	1
868	Glycoconjugate-Journal	NETHERLANDS	01.786	1
869	Glycobiology-	ENGLAND	02.927	1
870	Geobios-Lyon	FRANCE		1
871	Genomics-	UNITED STATES	03.424	1
872	Genome-	CANADA	01.876	1
873	General-Physiology-and-Biophysics	SLOVAKIA	00.259	1
874	Gastroenterology-	UNITED STATES	01.266	1
875	Gartenbauwissenschaft-	GERMANY	00.245	1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
876	Fundamental-and-Clinical-Pharmacology	FRANCE	01.226	1
877	Functional-Ecology	ENGLAND	01.818	1
878	Fruit-Varieties-Journal	UNITED STATES	00.233	1
879	Food-and-Nutrition-Bulletin	YUGOSLAVIA		1
880	Food-and-Agricultural-Immunology	ENGLAND	00.966	1
881	Food-Hydrocolloids	ENGLAND	01.063	1
882	Food-Biotechnology-New-York	UNITED STATES	00.655	1
883	Folia-Biologica-Prague	CZECH REPUBLIC	00.522	1
884	Fluoride-	UNITED STATES	00.519	1
885	Fish-Physiology-and-Biochemistry	NETHERLANDS	01.105	1
886	Fish-Pathology	JAPAN	00.667	1
887	Fertility-and-Sterility	UNITED STATES	02.612	1
888	FEMS-Microbiology-Ecology	NETHERLANDS	02.266	1
889	FASEB-Journal	UNITED STATES	14.629	1
890	FAO-Food-and-Agriculture-Organization-of-the-United-Nations-Fisheries-Technical-Paper	ITALY		1
891	Extremophiles-	UNITED STATES		1
892	Experimental-Parasitology	UNITED STATES	01.512	1
893	Experimental-Eye-Research	UNITED STATES	02.108	1
894	European-Neuropsychopharmacology	NETHERLANDS	01.852	1
895	European-Journal-of-Surgery	SWEDEN	00.677	1
896	European-Journal-of-Plant-Pathology	NETHERLANDS	01.027	1
897	European-Journal-of-Oral-Sciences	DENMARK	00.827	1
898	European-Journal-of-Medicinal-Chemistry	FRANCE	00.809	1
899	European-Journal-of-Haematology	DENMARK	01.626	1
900	European-Journal-of-Endocrinology	NORWAY	01.968	1
901	European-Journal-of-Clinical-Nutrition	ENGLAND	01.261	1
902	European-Journal-of-Clinical-Microbiology-and-Infectious-Diseases	GERMANY	01.935	1
903	European-Journal-of-Agronomy	FRANCE	00.513	1
904	Ethology-Ecology-and-Evolution	ITALY	00.651	1
905	Ethology-	GERMANY	01.178	1
906	Ergonomics-	ENGLAND	00.749	1
907	Environmental-and-Molecular-Mutagenesis	UNITED STATES	02.469	1
908	Environmental-Science-and-Technology	UNITED STATES	03.623	1
909	Environmental-Engineering-Science	UNITED STATES		1
910	Environment-International	UNITED STATES	00.341	1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
911	Entomotaxonomia-	CHINA		1
912	Entomologist's-Record-and-Journal-of-Variation	ENGLAND		1
913	Entomologische-Berichten-Amsterdam	NETHERLANDS		1
914	Entomological-News	UNITED STATES	00.311	1
915	Entomologia-Experimentalis-et-Applicata	NETHERLANDS	00.847	1
916	Electrophoresis-	GERMANY	02.848	1
917	Electroanalysis-	UNITED STATES	01.833	1
918	Ekspertimental'naya-Onkologiya	UKRAINE		1
919	Ecosystem-Health	UNITED STATES		1
920	Ecology-Washington-D-C	UNITED STATES	03.139	1
921	Ecological-Entomology	ENGLAND	01.200	1
922	Ecological-Applications	UNITED STATES	02.180	1
923	Ecography-	DENMARK	01.228	1
924	EMBO-European-Molecular-Biology-Organization-Journal	ENGLAND	12.643	1
925	Drugs-of-the-Future	SPAIN		1
926	Doriana-	ITALY		1
927	Diseases-of-Aquatic-Organisms	GERMANY	01.183	1
928	Digestion-	SWITZERLAND	01.315	1
929	Diagnostic-Microbiology-and-Infectious-Disease	UNITED STATES	01.356	1
930	Diabetologia-Croatica	GERMANY	05.347	1
931	Developmental-and-Comparative-Immunology	UNITED STATES	01.318	1
932	Developmental-Brain-Research	NETHERLANDS	01.823	1
933	Developmental-Biology	UNITED STATES	05.289	1
934	Development-Growth-and-Differentiation	JAPAN	01.443	1
935	Development-Genes-and-Evolution	GERMANY	01.231	1
936	Development-Cambridge	ENGLAND	09.781	1
937	Czech-Mycology	CZECH REPUBLIC		1
938	Cytokines-Cellular-and-Molecular-Therapy	ENGLAND	A	1
939	Cybernetica-	BELGIUM	00.075	1
940	Cryptogamie-Bryologie-Lichenologie	FRANCE	00.148	1
941	Cryptogamie-Algologie	FRANCE	00.145	1
942	Crustaceana-Leiden	NETHERLANDS	00.259	1
943	Coronary-Artery-Disease	UNITED STATES	00.653	1
944	Computers-in-Biology-and-Medicine	UNITED STATES	00.630	1
945	Computerized-Medical-Imaging-and-Graphics	UNITED STATES	00.343	1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
946	Comptes-Rendus-de-l'Academie-des-Sciences-Serie-II-A-Sciences-de-la-Terre-et-des-Planetes	FRANCE		1
947	Comparative-Immunology-Microbiology-and-Infectious-Diseases	ENGLAND	00.391	1
948	Comparative-Biochemistry-and-Physiology-B	ENGLAND	00.948	1
949	Clinical-and-Experimental-Hypertension	UNITED STATES	01.185	1
950	Clinical-Infectious-Diseases	UNITED STATES	02.803	1
951	Clinical-Immunology-and-Immunopathology	UNITED STATES	01.891	1
952	Clinical-Endocrinology	ENGLAND	02.447	1
953	Clinical-Drug-Investigation	NEW ZEALAND	00.913	1
954	Clinical-Cardiology	UNITED STATES	00.818	1
955	Circulation-	UNITED STATES	08.438	1
956	Chronobiology-International	UNITED STATES	00.824	1
957	Chromosome-Science	JAPAN		1
958	Chromosoma-Berlin	GERMANY	02.669	1
959	Chemistry-and-Physics-of-Lipids	NETHERLANDS	01.775	1
960	Chelonian-Conservation-and-Biology	SWITZERLAND		1
961	Cellular-and-Molecular-Neurobiology	UNITED STATES	01.968	1
962	Cellular-and-Molecular-Biology-Noisy-Le-Grand	FRANCE		1
963	Cellular-Signalling	UNITED STATES	02.174	1
964	Cellular-Immunology	UNITED STATES	01.830	1
965	Cell-and-Tissue-Research	GERMANY	01.740	1
966	Cell-Transplantation	UNITED STATES	01.744	1
967	Cell-Biology-and-Toxicology	UNITED STATES	00.492	1
968	Cardiovascular-Drugs-and-Therapy	UNITED STATES	01.098	1
969	Cardiology-	UNITED STATES	00.196	1
970	Candollea-	SWITZERLAND		1
971	Cancer-Investigation	UNITED STATES	01.570	1
972	Cancer-Immunology-Immunotherapy	UNITED STATES	01.269	1
973	Canadian-Journal-of-Soil-Science	CANADA	00.613	1
974	Canadian-Journal-of-Ophthalmology	CANADA	00.333	1
975	Canadian-Journal-of-Botany	CANADA	00.980	1
976	CLAO-Journal	UNITED STATES		1
977	CATENA-	GERMANY	00.639	1
978	Bulletin-of-Marine-Science	UNITED STATES	00.512	1
979	Bryologist-	UNITED STATES	00.618	1
980	British-Journal-of-Rheumatology	ENGLAND	02.309	1
981	British-Journal-of-Psychiatry	ENGLAND	03.265	1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
982	British-Journal-of-Oral-and-Maxillofacial-Surgery	ENGLAND		1
983	British-Journal-of-Ophthalmology	ENGLAND	01.826	1
984	British-Journal-of-Clinical-Pharmacology	ENGLAND	01.809	1
985	British-Journal-of-Biomedical-Science	ENGLAND	00.635	1
986	British-Journal-of-Anaesthesia	ENGLAND	02.241	1
987	Breeding-Science	JAPAN	00.358	1
988	Breast-Cancer-Research-and-Treatment	UNITED STATES	02.430	1
989	Breast-	SCOTLAND	00.555	1
990	Brain-and-Development	JAPAN	00.570	1
991	Brain-	ENGLAND	05.381	1
992	Botanical-Bulletin-of-Academia-Sinica-Taipei	TAIWAN	00.397	1
993	Bone-Marrow-Transplantation	ENGLAND	02.184	1
994	Blumea-	NETHERLANDS	00.089	1
995	Blood-Pressure	NORWAY		1
996	Bird-Conservation-International	ENGLAND		1
997	Biotropica-	UNITED STATES	00.542	1
998	Biotechnology-and-Bioengineering	UNITED STATES	01.979	1
999	Biosystems-	NETHERLANDS	00.591	1
1000	Bioseparation-	NETHERLANDS		1
1001	Bioscience-Reports	UNITED STATES	01.057	1
1002	Bioscience-Biotechnology-and-Biochemistry	JAPAN	00.919	1
1003	Bioorganic-Chemistry	UNITED STATES	00.797	1
1004	Biometrika-	ENGLAND	01.446	1
1005	Biomedicine-and-Pharmacotherapy	FRANCE	00.664	1
1006	Biomedical-Research-Tokyo	JAPAN	00.817	1
1007	Biomaterials-	ENGLAND	01.284	1
1008	Biomarkers-	UNITED STATES	01.303	1
1009	Biology-International	FRANCE		1
1010	Biologicals-	ENGLAND	00.598	1
1011	Biological-Control	UNITED STATES	01.075	1
1012	Biological-Conservation	ENGLAND	01.108	1
1013	Biogeographica-Paris	FRANCE		1
1014	Biodiversity-and-Conservation	NETHERLANDS	01.091	1
1015	Biodegradation-	NETHERLANDS	01.571	1
1016	Biocontrol-Science-and-Technology	ENGLAND	01.255	1
1017	Biocontrol-Science	ENGLAND	01.255	1
1018	Biochimie-Paris	FRANCE	01.441	1
1019	Biochemistry-Moscow	RUSSIA	00.436	1
1020	Biochemical-Genetics	UNITED STATES	00.757	1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
1021	Behavioral-Neuroscience	UNITED STATES	02.665	1
1022	Behavioral-Ecology-and-Sociobiology	UNITED STATES	02.327	1
1023	Bangladesh-Journal-of-Botany	BANGLADESH	00.035	1
1024	Avian-Pathology	ENGLAND	00.769	1
1025	Avian-Diseases	UNITED STATES	00.848	1
1026	Auris-Nasus-Larynx	JAPAN		1
1027	Artificial-Cells-Blood-Substitutes-and-Immobilization-Biotechnology	UNITED STATES	01.010	1
1028	Archives-of-Sexual-Behavior	UNITED STATES		1
1029	Archives-of-Physiology-and-Biochemistry	NETHERLANDS	00.113	1
1030	Archives-of-Pharmacal-Research-Seoul	SOUTH KOREA	00.254	1
1031	Archives-of-Orthopaedic-and-Trauma-Surgery	GERMANY	00.429	1
1032	Archives-of-Neurology	UNITED STATES	03.779	1
1033	Archives-of-Microbiology	GERMANY	02.351	1
1034	Archives-of-Gerontology-and-Geriatrics	IRELAND	00.233	1
1035	Archives-of-Disease-in-Childhood	ENGLAND	01.701	1
1036	Archiv-fuer-Hydrobiologie-Supplement	GERMANY	01.363	1
1037	Archiv-fuer-Gefluegelkunde	GERMANY		1
1038	Aquatic-Toxicology-Amsterdam	NETHERLANDS	01.421	1
1039	Aquatic-Microbial-Ecology	GERMANY	01.474	1
1040	Aquatic-Conservation	ENGLAND		1
1041	Aquacultural-Engineering	ENGLAND	00.441	1
1042	Antonie-van-Leeuwenhoek	NETHERLANDS	01.810	1
1043	Annals-of-the-Rheumatic-Diseases	ENGLAND	01.984	1
1044	Annals-of-the-Entomological-Society-of-America	UNITED STATES	00.686	1
1045	Annals-of-Saudi-Medicine	SAUDI ARABIA	00.179	1
1046	Annals-of-Otology-Rhinology-and-Laryngology	UNITED STATES	01.206	1
1047	Annals-of-Nutrition-and-Metabolism	SWITZERLAND	00.750	1
1048	Annals-of-Neurology	UNITED STATES	09.513	1
1049	Annales-de-Limnologie	FRANCE		1
1050	Annales-Zoologici-Warsaw	POLAND		1
1051	Annales-Botanici-Fennici	FINLAND	00.393	1
1052	Animal-Biotechnology	UNITED STATES	01.148	1
1053	Animal-Biology	ITALY		1
1054	Animal-Behaviour	ENGLAND	01.897	1
1055	Anesthesiology-Hagerstown	UNKNOWN		1
1056	Analisis-	FRANCE	00.439	1

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
1057	Anales-de-la-Real-Academia-de-Farmacia	SPAIN		1
1058	American-Journal-of-Surgical-Pathology	UNITED STATES	03.894	1
1059	American-Journal-of-Respiratory-and-Critical-Care-Medicine	UNITED STATES	04.705	1
1060	American-Journal-of-Public-Health	UNITED STATES	03.453	1
1061	American-Journal-of-Physiology	UNITED STATES	03.116	1
1062	American-Journal-of-Hematology	UNITED STATES	01.649	1
1063	American-Journal-of-Clinical-Nutrition	UNITED STATES	03.980	1
1064	American-Journal-of-Botany	UNITED STATES	01.715	1
1065	Allergology-International	GERMANY	00.557	1
1066	Alimentary-Pharmacology-and-Therapeutics	ENGLAND	03.004	1
1067	Alimentaria-	SPAIN		1
1068	Agronomie-Paris	FRANCE	00.325	1
1069	Advances-in-Therapy	UNITED STATES	00.408	1
1070	Actinomycetes-	ITALY		1
1071	Acta-Theriologica	POLAND	00.549	1
1072	Acta-Paediatrica-Sinica	TAIWAN		1
1073	Acta-Oecologica	FRANCE	00.564	1
1074	Acta-Obstetricia-et-Gynecologica-Scandinavica	DENMARK	00.783	1
1075	Acta-Neuropathologica	GERMANY	02.299	1
1076	Acta-Microbiologica-et-Immunologica-Hungarica	HUNGARY		1
1077	Acta-Microbiologica-Polonica	POLAND		1
1078	Acta-Medica-et-Biologica	JAPAN		1
1079	Acta-Botanica-Yunnanica	CHINA		1
1080	Acta-Biologica-Hungarica	HUNGARY		1
1081	Acta-Anaesthesiologica-Scandinavica	DENMARK	01.180	1
1082	Acta-Agriculturae-Scandinavica-Section-B-Soil-and-Plant-Science	SWEDEN	00.342	1
1083	Acarologia-Paris	FRANCE	00.178	1
1084	AIDS-Research-and-Human-Retroviruses	UNITED STATES	03.069	1
1085	AIDS-London	ENGLAND	05.050	1
Total				8352

Table 4. Letters and communication journals used by Indian researchers as seen from BIOSIS

No.	Journal title	Publishing country	IF-1997	Number of papers
1	Tetrahedron-Letters	ENGLAND	02.500	62
2	Cancer-Letters	NETHERLANDS	01.440	24
3	FEMS-Microbiology-Letters	NETHERLANDS	01.560	17
4	FEBS-Letters	NETHERLANDS	03.504	16
5	Pharmacy-and-Pharmacology-Communications	ENGLAND		14
6	Veterinary-Research-Communications	NETHERLANDS	00.613	13
7	Biotechnology-Letters	NETHERLANDS	00.848	12
8	Bioorganic-and-Medicinal-Chemistry-Letters	ENGLAND	01.628	10
9	Analytical-Letters	UNITED STATES	01.000	10
10	Protein-and-Peptide-Letters	UNKNOWN		6
11	immunology-Letters	NETHERLANDS	01.096	6
12	Neuroscience-Letters	NETHERLANDS	01.768	5
13	Letters-in-Applied-Microbiology	ENGLAND	01.008	5
14	Communications-in-Soil-Science-and-Plant-Analysis	UNITED STATES	00.430	5
15	Biomedical-Letters	ENGLAND		5
16	Toxicology-Letters-Shannon	IRELAND	01.128	4
17	Drug-and-Chemical-Toxicology-an-International-Journal-for-Rapid-Communication	UNITED STATES	00.526	3
18	Rapid-Communications-in-Mass-Spectrometry	ENGLAND	02.390	2
19	Cereal-Research-Communications	HUNGARY	00.207	2
20	Cellular-and-Molecular-Biology-Letters	POLAND		2
21	Pharmaceutical-and-Pharmacological-Letters	GERMANY		1
22	Nuclear-Medicine-Communications	ENGLAND	01.011	1
23	Letters-in-Peptide-Science	NETHERLANDS		1
Total				226

Table 5. Indian research papers covered by BIOSIS 1998 classified by subfield [arranged by number of papers]

No.	Subfield*	Number of journals	Number of papers
1	Agronomy- (Agriculture-)	93	978
2	Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biophysics	226	646
3	Horticulture- (Agriculture-)	62	336
4	Animal-Husbandry (Agriculture-)	29	315
5	Infection-	102	276
6	Enzymology- (Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biophysics)	142	257
7	Foods-	60	254
8	Pharmacology-	75	235
9	Methods-and-Techniques	90	224
10	Development-	88	187
11	Genetics-	64	183
12	Epidemiology- (Population-Studies)	75	165
13	Biogeography- (Population-Studies)	29	160
14	Economic-Entomology	30	147
15	Bioprocess-Engineering	51	146
16	Forestry-	31	133
17	Parasitology-	42	124
18	Molecular-Genetics (Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biophysics)	61	121
19	Systematics-and-Taxonomy	46	117
20	Immune-System (Chemical-Coordination-and-Homeostasis)	65	111
21	Reproductive-System (Reproduction-)	34	111
22	Behavior-	54	107
23	Endocrine-System (Chemical-Coordination-and-Homeostasis)	57	105
24	Pharmacognosy- (Pharmacology-)	35	97
25	Cardiovascular-Medicine (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	52	92
26	Toxicology-	44	87
27	Metabolism-	55	85
28	Nervous-System (Neural-Coordination)	45	82
29	Chemical-Coordination-and-Homeostasis	41	80
30	Nutrition-	45	80
31	Pest-Assessment-Control-and-Management	43	80
32	Pollution-Assessment-Control-and-Management	39	76
33	Neurology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	36	70
34	Cell-Biology	47	67
35	Cardiovascular-System (Transport-and-Circulation)	35	66
36	Aquaculture-	21	65

No.	Subfield	Number of journals	Number of papers
37	Gastroenterology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	40	64
38	Blood-and-Lymphatics (Transport-and-Circulation)	37	58
39	Dental-and-Oral-System (Ingestion-and-Assimilation)	35	57
40	Ecology- (Environmental-Sciences)	33	52
41	Anthropology-	13	51
42	Dermatology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	19	49
43	Bacteriology-	32	46
44	Agriculture-	29	45
45	Chemistry-	18	45
46	Climatology- (Environmental-Sciences)	26	45
47	Oncology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	31	45
48	Soil-Science	22	45
49	Clinical-Immunology (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	31	44
50	Veterinary-Medicine (Medical-Sciences)	7	44
51	Conservation-	23	42
52	Digestive-System	24	42
53	Pesticides-	28	42
54	Morphology-	18	37
55	Terrestrial-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental-Sciences)	24	36
56	Marine-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental-Sciences)	11	34
57	Ophthalmology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	12	34
58	Agrichemicals-	14	33
59	Gynecology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	19	33
60	Tumor-Biology	19	33
61	Bioenergetics- (Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biophysics)	21	32
62	Hematology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	22	31
63	Clinical-Endocrinology (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	25	27
64	Biodiversity-	14	25
65	Integumentary-System (Chemical-Coordination and-Homeostasis)	18	25
66	Wildlife-Management (Conservation-)	6	23
67	Biosynchronization-	19	22
68	Skeletal-System (Movement-and-Support)	9	22
69	Digestive-System (Ingestion-and-Assimilation)	13	21
70	Population-Studies	15	21
71	Waste-Management (Sanitation-)	13	20

No.	Subfield	Number of journals	Number of papers
72	Paleobiology-	8	19
73	Clinical-Chemistry (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	16	18
74	Dental-Medicine (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	15	18
75	Evolution-and-Adaptation	13	18
76	Freshwater-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental-Sciences)	12	18
77	Pharmaceuticals- (Pharmacology-)	8	17
78	Reproduction-	14	17
79	Physiology-	12	16
80	Aging-	11	15
81	Human-Ecology (Anthropology-)	4	15
82	Medical-Genetics (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	12	14
83	Models-and-Simulations (Computational-Biology)	14	14
84	Public-Health (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	12	14
85	Membranes- (Cell-Biology)	11	13
86	Radiation-Biology	12	13
87	Psychiatry- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	7	12
88	Sense-Organs (Sensory-Reception)	9	12
89	Allergy- (Clinical-Immunology, Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	9	11
90	Botany-	6	11
91	Equipment-, Apparatus-, Devices-and-Instrumentation	9	11
92	Estuarine-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental-Sciences)	4	11
93	Anesthesiology- (Medical-Sciences)	4	10
94	Microbiology-	9	10
95	Obstetrics- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	4	10
96	Orthopedics- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	8	10
97	Pediatrics- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	8	10
98	Urinary-System (Chemical-Coordination-and-Homeostasis)	7	10
99	Urology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	4	10
100	Computer-Applications (Computational-Biology)	8	9
101	Nephrology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	5	9
102	Biomaterials-	8	8
103	Human-Medicine (Medical-Sciences)	5	8
104	Occupational-Health (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	5	8
105	Mathematical-Biology (Computational-Biology)	6	7
106	Population-Genetics (Population-Studies)	7	7
107	Economics-	6	6
108	Education-	6	6

No.	Subfield	Number of journals	Number of papers
109	Respiratory-System (Respiration-)	6	6
110	Forensics-	1	5
111	Muscular-System (Movement-and-Support)	4	5
112	Otolaryngology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	3	5
113	Pulmonary-Medicine (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	5	5
114	Sanitation-	5	5
115	Surgery- (Medical-Sciences)	5	5
116	Biomedical-Engineering (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	4	4
117	Dental-and-Oral-System (Oral-System)	4	4
118	Geology- (Environmental-Sciences)	4	4
119	Groundwater-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental Sciences)	4	4
120	Information-Studies	3	4
121	Radiology- (Medical-Sciences)	4	4
122	Pathology-	3	3
123	Sociology- (Population-Studies)	3	3
124	Sports-Medicine (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	2	3
125	Audiology- (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	2	2
126	Government-and-Law	2	2
127	History-	2	2
128	Hospital-Administration (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	2	2
129	Mycology-	2	2
130	Physics-	1	2
131	Rheumatology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	2	2
132	Subterranean-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental-Sciences)	2	2
133	Transport-and-Circulation	2	2
134	Zoology-	2	2
135	Allied-Medical-Sciences	1	1
136	Animal-Care	1	1
137	Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biophysics	1	1
138	Biography- (History-)	1	1
139	Biography- (History-)	1	1
140	Biography- (History-)	1	1
141	Botany-	1	1
142	Communication-	1	1
143	Computational-Biology	1	1
144	Conservation-	1	1
145	Cosmetics-	1	1
146	Ecology- (Environmental-Sciences)	1	1

No.	Subfield	Number of journals	Number of papers
147	Environmental-Sciences	1	1
148	Foods-	1	1
149	General-Life-Studies	1	1
150	Geriatrics- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	1	1
151	Horticulture- (Agriculture-)	1	1
152	Human-Geography (Population-Studies)	1	1
153	Infection-	1	1
154	Medical-Sciences	1	1
155	Ophthalmology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	1	1
156	Pharmacology-	1	1
157	Philosophy-and-Ethics	1	1
158	Pollution-Assessment-Control-and-Management	1	1
159	Sensory-Reception	1	1
160	Tumor-Biology	1	1
161	Vector-Biology	1	1
162	Virology-	1	1
Total		1848	8352

*Some papers are classified under more than one subfield

Table 6. Distribution of Indian research papers indexed in BIOSIS-1998 by journal country [arranged by number of papers]

No.	Journal country	Number of journals	Number of papers
1	INDIA	75	4,630
2	UNITED KINGDOM	232	1,006
3	UNITED STATES	294	844
4	NETHERLANDS	127	657
5	GERMANY	86	311
6	SWITZERLAND	33	101
7	JAPAN	34	92
8	ITALY	18	92
9	PHILIPPINES	1	73
10	AUSTRALIA	10	67
11	DENMARK	20	54
12	CZECH REPUBLIC	6	51
13	FRANCE	24	41
14	HUNGARY	11	33
15	CANADA	10	30
16	IRELAND	5	29
17	SWEDEN	11	27
18	POLAND	8	26
19	SOUTH KOREA	4	25
20	ISRAEL	6	14
21	SINGAPORE	4	14
22	THAILAND	3	14
23	SLOVAKIA	4	11
24	AUSTRIA	5	10
25	SPAIN	5	8
26	NORWAY	4	8
27	BANGLADESH	3	8

No.	Journal country	Number of journals	Number of papers
28	CROATIA	2	7
29	MALAYSIA	2	7
30	BRAZIL	4	6
31	TAIWAN	4	5
32	GREECE	3	4
33	KENYA	1	4
34	PAKISTAN	3	3
35	SAUDI ARABIA	2	3
36	CHINA	2	2
37	NEW ZEALAND	2	2
38	CHILE	1	2
39	ARGENTINA	1	1
40	BELGIUM	1	1
41	FINLAND	1	1
42	HONG-KONG	1	1
43	RUSSIA	1	1
44	SOUTH AFRICA	1	1
45	UKRAINE	1	1
46	YUGOSLAVIA	1	1
47	UNKNOWN	8	23
Total		1085	8352

**Table 7. Indian journals covered by BIOSIS-1998
[arranged by number of papers]**

No.	Journal	Number of papers
1	Indian-Veterinary-Journal	369
2	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Sciences	322
3	Indian-Journal-of-Experimental-Biology	232
4	Current-Science-Bangalore	228
5	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Sciences	185
6	Journal-of-the-Bombay-Natural-History-Society	153
7	Crop-Research-Hisar	152
8	Indian-Forester	139
9	Advances-in-Plant-Sciences	123
10	Indian-Journal-of-Agronomy	118
11	Journal-of-Food-Science-and-Technology	111
12	Indian-Veterinary-Medical-Journal	103
13	Journal-of-Medicinal-and-Aromatic-Plant-Sciences	93
14	Journal-of-Maharashtra-Agricultural-Universities	93
15	Indian-Journal-of-Pharmaceutical-Sciences	90
16	Agricultural-Science-Digest	90
17	Journal-of-Mycology-and-Plant-Pathology	81
18	Indian-Journal-of-Plant-Physiology	78
19	Journal-of-Human-Ecology	77
20	Indian-Journal-of-Genetics-and-Plant-	77

No.	Journal	Number of papers
	Breeding	
21	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Nutrition	73
22	Indian-Journal-of-Medical-Research	72
23	Journal-of-Entomological-Research-New-Delhi	65
24	Journal-of-Economic-and-Taxonomic-Botany	65
25	Indian-Journal-of-Marine-Sciences	64
26	Journal-of-Biosciences-Bangalore	61
27	Indian-Journal-of-Pharmacology	60
28	Geobios-Jodhpur	60
29	Indian-Journal-of-Physiology-and-Pharmacology	58
30	Journal-of-Environmental-Biology	53
31	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	52
32	Entomon-	51
33	Seed-Research-New-Delhi	47
34	Journal-of-Phytological-Research	46
35	Annals-of-Biology-Hissar	46
36	Indian-Journal-of-Sericulture	41
37	Phytomorphology-	39
38	Journal-of-Nuclear-Agriculture-and-Biology	38
39	Journal-of-Communicable-Diseases	38
40	Indian-Journal-of-Ophthalmology	37
41	National-Medical-Journal-of-India	33
42	Indian-Journal-of-Physiology-and-Allied-Sciences	32
43	Indian-Journal-of-Cancer	28
44	Crop-Improvement	28
45	PKV-Research-Journal	27
46	Journal-of-Biological-Control	27
47	Indian-Journal-of-Pediatrics	27
48	Journal-of-Veterinary-and-Animal-Sciences	25

No.	Journal	Number of papers
49	Journal-of-Advanced-Zoology	25
50	Uttar-Pradesh-Journal-of-Zoology	24
51	Indian-Journal-of-Poultry-Science	24
52	International-Journal-of-Tropical-Agriculture	22
53	Journal-of-Plant-Biochemistry-and-Biotechnology	21
54	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Surgery	21
55	Rheedeia-	20
56	Journal-of-the-Indian-Potato-Association	20
57	Indian-Journal-of-Environmental-Health	20
58	Fishery-Technology	20
59	Proceedings-of-the-Zoological-Society-Calcutta	19
60	Proceedings-of-the-National-Academy-of-Sciences-India-Section-B-Biological-Sciences	19
61	Indian-Fern-Journal	19
62	Indian-Journal-of-Malariology	17
63	Journal-of-Aquaculture-in-the-Tropics	15
64	Indian-Journal-of-Natural-Rubber-Research	15
65	Bionature-	15
66	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-National-Science-Academy-Part-B-Biological-Sciences	14
67	Biological-Memoirs	14
68	Research-Bulletin-of-the-Panjab-University-Science	12
69	Tropical-Ecology	10
70	Agricultural-and-Biological-Research	9
71	Oriental-Insects	7
72	Journal-of-Applied-Animal-Research	7
73	Indian-Journal-of-Natural-Products	6

No.	Journal	Number of papers
74	Journal-of-Genetics	5
75	Biomedical-Research-Aligarh	3
Total		4630

**Table 8. Distribution of Indian life sciences papers
by impact factor range of journals**

IF range (JCR 1997)	Number of journals	Number of papers
0	241	3565
0.0 <0.5	164	2260
0.5 <1.0	247	1056
1.0 <1.5	164	642
1.5 <2.0	107	313
2.0 <2.5	58	183
2.5 <3.0	31	158
3.0 <3.5	19	40
3.5 <4.0	17	62
4.0 <4.5	7	20
4.5 <5.0	8	13
5.0 <5.5	6	7
5.5 <6.0	2	6
6.0 <6.5	0	0
6.5 <7.0	3	8
>=7.0	11	19
Total	1085	8352

Table 9. Indian institutions publishing papers as seen from BIOSIS 1998 [arranged by number of papers]

No.	Institution	Number of papers
1	All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi	192
2	Indian Agric. Res. Inst., New Dehli	169
3	CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar	148
4	Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi	144
5	Indian Vet. Res. Inst., Izatnagar	139
6	Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana	133
7	Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore	131
8	Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, Chandigarh	107
9	Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow	74
10	Central Inst. Med. Aromatic Plants, Lucknow	73
11	Panjab University, Chandigarh	73
12	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore	68
13	Jawaharlal Nehru Univ., New Delhi	66
14	Christian Med. Coll. Hosp., Vellore	63
15	Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh	62
16	Central Food Technol. Res. Inst., Mysore	60
17	H. P. Krishi Vishvavidyalaya, Palampur	60
18	Bhabha Atomic Res. Cent., Mumbai	58
19	Govind Ballabh Pant Univ. of Agric. and Tech., Pant Nagar	58
20	Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri	57
21	University of Madras, Chennai	56
22	National Botanical Research Institute, Lucknow	55
23	National Chemical Laboratory, Pune	55
24	Sanjay Gandhi Postgrad. Inst. Med. Sci., Lucknow	51
25	Int. Crops Res. Inst. Semi-Arid Trop., Patancheru	48

No.	Institution	Number of papers
26	University of Calcutta, Calcutta	48
27	University of Delhi, Delhi	46
28	Natl. Dairy Res. Inst., Karnal	45
29	Indian Inst. Chem. Technol., Hyderabad	44
30	Kasturba Med. Coll., Manipal	44
31	Madras Vet. Coll., Chennai	44
32	Bose Inst. , Calcutta	42
33	Andhra University, Visakhapatnam	41
34	Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola	41
35	Indian Inst. Chemical Biol., Calcutta	41
36	University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore	40
37	Indian Inst. Technol., Delhi, New Delhi	39
38	University of Hyderabad, Hyderabad	39
39	Natl. Inst. Mental Health Neurosci., Bangalore	37
40	Jawaharlal Nehru KrishiVishwa Vidyalaya, Jabalpur	36
41	North Eastern Hill University, Shillong	36
42	Osmania Univeristy, Hyderabad	36
43	Punjabi University, Patiala	36
44	University of Rajasthan, Jaipur	36
45	Centre for Cellular and Molecular Biology, Hyderabad	34
46	IIHR, Bangalore	33
47	Annamalai Univ., Annamalainagar	32
48	Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar	32
49	Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi	32
50	Tata Memorial Hosp., Mumbai	32
51	Univ. Kerala, Thiruvantanthapuram	32
52	Coll. Vet. Sci., AAU, Khanapara, Guwahati	31
53	Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Mumbai	31
54	Jadavpur Univ., Calcutta	30
55	Assam Agricultural University, Jorhat	29

No.	Institution	Number of papers
56	Indian Inst. Technol. Madras, Chennai	29
57	National Inst. Immunology, New Delhi	29
58	Trop. Bot. Gard. Res. Inst., Thiruvananthapuram	29
59	Devi Ahilya Univ., Indore	27
60	Dr. A.L.M. Postgrad. Inst. Basic Med. Sci., Chennai	27
61	Madurai Kamaraj Univ., Madurai	27
62	Univ. Coll. Med. Sci. and GTB Hosp., Delhi	27
63	University of Mysore, Mysore	27
64	M. S. Univ. Baroda, Vadodara	26
65	Sri Venkateswara Univ., Tirupati	26
66	Cent. Potato Res. Inst., Shimla	25
67	Industrial Toxicology Research Centre, Lucknow	25
68	Natl. Inst. Nutr., Hyderabad	25
69	University of Burdwan, Burdwan	25
70	Agarkar Research Institute, Pune	24
71	Cent. Leather Res. Inst., Chennai	24
72	Marathwada Agric. Univ., Parbhani	24
73	Central Sheep Wood Res. Inst., Avikanagar, Rajasthan	23
74	University of Calicut, Thenhipalam	23
75	Visva-Bharati Univ., Santiniketan	23
76	Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad	22
77	Indian Inst. Technol., Kharagpur	22
78	Inst. Microbial Technol., Chandigarh	22
79	Univ. Bombay, Mumbai	22
80	University of Delhi South Campus, New Delhi	22
81	Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli	21
82	Coll. Vet. Sci. Anim. Husbandry, Durg	21
83	Dr. H.S. Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar	21
84	Indian Inst. Technol., Bombay, Mumbai	21
85	Int. Cent. Genet. Eng. and Biotechnol., New Delhi	21

No.	Institution	Number of papers
86	National Institute of Oceanography, Dona Paula	21
87	Cochin Univ. Sci. Technol., Cochin	20
88	National Institute of Cholera and Enteric Diseases, Calcutta	20
89	University of Kalyani, Kalyani	20
90	Vet. Coll., Univ. Agric. Sci., Hebbal, Bangalore	20
91	Indian Grassland and Fodder Research Institute, Jhansi	19
92	Indira Gandhi Agricultural University, Raipur	19
93	Univ. Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur	19
94	Coll. Vet. Sci. Anim. Husbandry, Jabalpur	18
95	College of Veterinary Science, Tirupati	18
96	Dr. Y. S. Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry, Nauni, Solan	18
97	Maulana Azad Med. Coll. Assoc. Hosp., New Delhi	18
98	Narèndra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology, Bahraich	18
99	Ranchi Vet. Coll., Ranchi	18
100	Sree Chitra Tirunal Inst. Med. Sci. Technol., Thiruvananthapuram	18
101	Univ. Pune, Pune	18
102	Univ. Roorkee, Roorkee	18
103	University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad	18
104	Vet. Coll., Mhow	18
105	Cancer Res. Inst., Mumbai	17
106	Cent. Avian Res. Inst., Izatnagar	17
107	Coll. Vet. Anim. Sci., Kerela Agricultural Univ., Mannuthy	17
108	Gujarat Univ., Ahmedabad	17
109	Gulbarga University, Gulbarga	17
110	J.N. Agric. Univ., Campus Coll. Agric., Gwalior	17
111	L. V. Prasad Eye Inst., Hyderabad	17
112	Manipur University, Canchipur	17
113	Regional Cancer Cent., Trivandrum	17

No.	Institution	Number of papers
114	Regional Plant Resource Centre, Bhubaneswar	17
115	Utkal Univ., Bhubaneswar	17
116	Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai	16
117	Central Rice Res. Inst., Cuttack	16
118	Central Sericultural Research and Training Institute, Mysore	16
119	Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun	16
120	Indian Statistical Inst., Calcutta	16
121	Jawaharlal Inst. Postgrad. Med. Educ. Res., Pondicherry	16
122	Karnataka State Sericulture Res. Dev. Inst., Bangalore	16
123	Medical and Vision Research Foundation, Chennai	16
124	St. John's Med. Coll., Bangalore	16
125	Assam Agricultural University, Khanapara	15
126	B.C. Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Mohanpur	15
127	Defence Res. Dev. Establishment, Gwalior	15
128	Kerala Forest Research Institute, Thrissur	15
129	Pt. Ravishankar Shukla Univ., Raipur	15
130	Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur	15
131	Tamil Nadu Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, Chennai	15
132	Bombay Veterinary College, Mumbai	14
133	Coll. Vet. Sci., GB Pant Univ. Agric. Technol., Pantnagar	14
134	Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra	14
135	Rajasthan College of Agriculture, Udaipur	14
136	Reg. Res. Lab., Jorhat	14
137	Tropical Forest Research Institute, Jabalpur	14
138	University College of Science and Technology, Calcutta	14
139	Central Agric. Res. Inst., Port Blair	13
140	Central Inst. Res. Goats, Mathura	13
141	Coll. Vet. Anim. Sci., Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishvavidyalaya, Palampur	13
142	King George's Medical College, Lucknow	13

No.	Institution	Number of papers
143	Loyola Coll., Chennai	13
144	Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar	13
145	Saurashtra University, Rajkot	13
146	Anna University, Chennai	12
147	Bharathiar University, Coimbatore	12
148	Birsa Agricultural University, Ranchi	12
149	Central Arid Zone Res. Inst., Jodhpur	12
150	Coll. Vet. Sci., Animal Husbandry, Gujarat Agric. Univ., Anand	12
151	Gujarat Agric. Univ., Anand	12
152	Indian Assoc. Cult. Sci., Calcutta	12
153	Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Mukteswar	12
154	Inst. Immunohaematol., KEM Hosp. Campus, Mumbai	12
155	Jawaharlal Nehru Cent. Adv. Sci. Res, Bangalore	12
156	Vet. Coll. Res. Inst., Namakkal	12
157	Arid Forest Research Institute, Jodhpur	11
158	Bot. Survey India, Port Blair	11
159	Ch. Charan Singh University, Meerut	11
160	College Fisheries, Mangalore	11
161	Institute for Research in Reproduction, Mumbai	11
162	Kakatiya Univ., Warangal	11
163	M. L. N. Med. Coll., Allahabad	11
164	Mangalore Univ., Mangalagangothri	11
165	National Inst. Virol., Pune	11
166	Reg. Res. Lab., Jammu-Tawi	11
167	Regional Med. Res. Centre, ICMR, Dibrugarh	11
168	Regional Res. Lab., Bhubanesar	11
169	Rubber Res. Inst. Kottayam	11
170	Saha Inst. Nucl. Physics., Calcutta	11
171	University of Jammu, Jammu	11

No.	Institution	Number of papers
172	Wildlife Inst. India, Dehradun	11
173	Bombay Natural History Society, Mumbai	10
174	C. S. Azad University of Agriculture and Technology, Kanpur	10
175	Central Inst. Fisheries Technol., Cochin	10
176	Central Sericultural Res. Training Inst., Berhampore	10
177	Central Soil Salinity Res. Inst., Karnal	10
178	College of Agriculture, Pune	10
179	Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Deemed University, Agra	10
180	Gauhati University, Guwahati	10
181	Hindustan Antibiotics Limited, Pune	10
182	Kasturba Med. Coll., Mangalore	10
183	Nagpur University Campus, Nagpur	10
184	Rajendra Agric. Univ., Pusa	10
185	Salim Ali Cent. Ornithol. Natural Hist., Coimbatore	10
186	University of Lucknow, Lucknow	10
187	Vector Control Res. Cent. Med. Pondicherry	10
188	C. B. Patel Res. Cent. Chem. Biol. Sci., Mumbai	9
189	College of Veterinary Science, Hyderabad	9
190	Defence Inst. Physiol. Allied Sci., Delhi	9
191	Karnatak University, Dharwad	9
192	KEM Hosp., Mumbai	9
193	Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli	9
194	Med. Hosp. Res. Cent., Moradabad	9
195	Nagpur Vet. Coll., Nagpur, Maharashtra	9
196	Peninsula Polymers Ltd., Thiruvananthapuram	9
197	Regional Res. Lab., Thiruvananthapuram	9
198	Sher-e-Kashmir Univ. Agric. Sci. Technol., Rajouri	9
199	St. Xavier's College, Palayamkottai	9
200	University of Allahabad, Allahabad	9
201	Vallabhbhai Patel Chest Inst., Delhi	9

No.	Institution	Number of papers
202	Coll. Vet. Anim. Sci., Bikaner	8
203	College of Veterinary Science, Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar	8
204	Defence Food Res. Lab., Mysore	8
205	Dibrugarh University, Assam	8
206	Dr. Reddy's Res. Found., Hyderabad	8
207	G.B. Pant Institute of Himalayan Environment and Development, Tadong	8
208	Hoechst Marion Roussel Ltd., Mumbai	8
209	Inst. Nucl. Med. Allied Sci., Delhi	8
210	J. N. Vyas University, Jodhpur	8
211	Kumaun University, Nainital	8
212	Malaria Res. Cent., Delhi	8
213	National Remote Sensing Agency, Hyderabad	8
214	Natl. Res. Cent. Camel, Bikaner	8
215	NIANP, NDRI, Bangalore	8
216	Nizam's Inst. Med. Sci., Hyderabad	8
217	Rajasthan Agricultural University, Udaipur	8
218	Sher-e-Kashmir Agric. Sci. Technol., Srinagar	8
219	Shri Govindram Seksaria Inst. Technol. Sci., Indore	8
220	Sugarcane Breed. Inst., Coimbatore	8
221	Tata Energy Res. Inst., New Delhi	8
222	Berhampur University, Berhampur	7
223	Birla Inst. Technol. and Sci., Pilani	7
224	Cent. Biochem. Technol., Univ. Campus, Delhi	7
225	Cent. Inst. Med. Aromatic Plants, Field Station, Bangalore	7
226	Coll. Vet. Sci. Anim. Husbandry, C.S.A.Univ. Agric. Technol., Mathura Campus	7
227	Gujarat Agric. Univ., Junagadh	7
228	H.N.B. Garhwal Univ., Srinagar-Garhwal	7
229	IGKV, Zonal Agricultural Research Station, Ambikapur	7

No.	Institution	Number of papers
230	Indian Inst. Sugarcane Res., Lucknow	7
231	Inst. Life Sci., Bhubaneswar	7
232	Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Indore	7
233	L. M. College of Pharmacy, Ahmedabad	7
234	Madras Crocodile Bank Trust, Mamallapuram	7
235	Maharshi Dayarand Univ., Rohtak	7
236	North Eastern Reg. Inst. Sci. Technol., Nirjuli	7
237	Pondicherry Univ., Pondicherry	7
238	Rani Durgavati Univ., Jabalpur	7
239	Reg. Agric. Res. Stn., Pattambi	7
240	Space Appl. Cent. (ISRO), Ahmedabad	7
241	TIFR Centre, Bangalore	7
242	Vet. Coll., Bidar	7
243	Zool. Survey India, Calcutta	7
244	Acharya N.G. Ranga Agricultural University, Rajendranagar	6
245	Acharya N.G. Ranga Agricultural University, Tirupati	6
246	Birbal Sahni Inst. Palaeobot., Lucknow	6
247	Cancer Inst. Annex, Guindy, Chennai	6
248	Central Potato Research Institute, Jalandhar	6
249	Central Res. Inst. Dryland Agric., Hyderabad	6
250	Chandra Sekhar Azad University of Agriculture and Technology, Kanpur	6
251	Coll. Agric., Gwalior	6
252	G.B. Pant Hosp., New Dehli	6
253	ICAR Res. Complex NEH Region, Barapani	6
254	Indian Inst. Soil Sci., Bhopal	6
255	Indian Vet. Res. Inst., Regional Stn., Palampur	6
256	Inst. Himalayan Bioresource Technol., Palampur	6
257	Inst. Pathol., New Delhi	6
258	M. S. Swaminathan Res. Found., Chennai	6

No.	Institution	Number of papers
259	Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Alwarkurichi	6
260	National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning, Nagpur	6
261	National Institute Communicable Diseases, Delhi	6
262	Natl. Bot. Res. Inst., Lucknow	6
263	Natl. Bureau Plant Genet. Resour., New Delhi	6
264	Natl. Inst. Pharm. Educ. Res., S.A.S. Nagar	6
265	Rhino Foundation for nature in NE India, Guwahati	6
266	Rohilkhand Univ., Bareilly	6
267	SKN College of Agriculture, Jobner	6
268	Univ. Coll. Women, Hyderabad	6
269	Vikram University, Ujjain	6
270	West Bengal Univ. Anim. Fish.Sci., Nadia	6
271	Agric. Coll., Rejendranagar	5
272	Agricultural College and Research Institute, (TNAU), Killikulam	5
273	Amala Cancer Res. Cent., Thrissur	5
274	Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur	5
275	Bombay Coll. Pharm., Mumbai	5
276	Bombay Hosp. , Mumbai	5
277	Bot. Survey India, Coimbatore	5
278	Bot. Survey India, Howrah	5
279	Central Inst. Freshwater Aquac., Bhubaneswar	5
280	Coll. Agric., Rajendranagar	5
281	Coll. Veteriary Animal Sciences, MAU, Parbhani	5
282	College of Horticulture, Kerala Agricultural University, Trichur	5
283	College Pharmaceutical Sciences, Manipal	5
284	CSWCRTI, Dehradun	5
285	Diabetes Res. Cent., Chennai	5
286	Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia Avadh University, Faizabad	5

No.	Institution	Number of papers
287	Gao Univ., Taleigao Plateau, Goa	5
288	Government Medical College and Hospital, Chandigarh	5
289	IG Med. Coll., Shimla	5
290	Indian Inst. Technol., Kanpur	5
291	Inst. Sci., Mumbai	5
292	Institute of Forest Genetics and Tree Breeding, Coimbatore	5
293	Institute of Microbiology and Biotechnology, Barkatullah University, Bhopal	5
294	Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi	5
295	JMDPL Mahila Coll., Madhubani	5
296	Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Chhindwara	5
297	L.T.M. Medical Coll., Mumbai	5
298	Malaria Research Centre (Field Station), Nadiad	5
299	Natl. Res. Cent. Yak, Dirang	5
300	Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru Coll. Agric. Res. Inst., Karaikal	5
301	Reg. Res. Stn., Orissa Univ. Agric. Technol., Chiplima	5
302	School of Tropical Medicine, Calcutta	5
303	SPIC Sci. Found., Chennai	5
304	Sri Ramachandra Med. Coll. Res. Inst., Chennai	5
305	Sugarcane Research Station, Sirugamani	5
306	Toklai Experimental Station, Tea Res. Association, Jorhat	5
307	Tripura University, Agartala	5
308	Vet. Coll., Udgir	5
309	Zool. Survey India, Chennai	5
310	Agric. Res. Stn., Acharya N.G. Ranga Agricultural University, Maruteru	4
311	Alagappa Coll. Technol., Anna Univ., Chennai	4
312	Anim. Health Centre, Vijayawada	4
313	Bangalore University, Bangalore	4
314	Bihar Vet. Coll., Patna	4
315	Bot. Survey India, Allahabad	4

No.	Institution	Number of papers
316	Bot. Survey India, Pune	4
317	CCS Haryana Agric. Univ., Regional Res. Station, Uchani	4
318	CCS Haryana Agricultural University Rice Res. Stn., Kaul	4
319	Cent. Inst. Med. Aromatic Plants, Field Stn., Boduppall	4
320	Cent. Res. Inst., Kasauli	4
321	Cent. Rice Res. Inst., Cuttack	4
322	Central Buffalo Res. Inst., Hisar	4
323	Central Inst. Medicinal Aromatic Plants, Field Stn. Pantnagar	4
324	Central Plantation Crops Res. Inst., Kayamkulam	4
325	Centre Biochem. Technol., Delhi	4
326	Centre for Logistical Research and Innovation, New Delhi	4
327	Chittaranjan National Cancer Inst., Calcutta	4
328	Christian Med. Coll., Ludhiana	4
329	Coll. Fish., Ratnagiri	4
330	Coll. Vet. Sci. Anim. Husb., Gujarat Agric. Univ., Sardar Krushinagar	4
331	College of Agriculture, Dhule	4
332	College of Veterinary Science, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana	4
333	Cropping Syst. Res., Meerut	4
334	Deccan Coll. Med. Sci. and Allied Hosp., Hyderabad	4
335	Ganga Ram Hospital Road, New Delhi	4
336	Government Med. Coll., Nagpur	4
337	Ind. Toxicol. Res. Cent., Lucknow	4
338	Indian Inst. Pulses Res., Kanpur	4
339	Indian Inst. Spices Res., Calicut	4
340	Indian Inst. Spices Res., Cardamon Re. Cent., Madikeri	4
341	Indian Lac Research Institute, Ranchi	4
342	Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Regional Agric. Res. Stn., Bilaspur	4

No.	Institution	Number of papers
343	Jiwaji University, Gwalior	4
344	Kidwai Memorial Inst. Oncol., Bangalore	4
345	Madras Med. College Government General Hospital, Chennai	4
346	Mahatma Gandhi Univ., Kottayam	4
347	Malaria Res. Cent., Med. Coll. Build., Jabalpur	4
348	Malaria Res. Cent., Sect. III, BHEL, Ranipur, Hardwar	4
349	Med. Coll., Calcutta	4
350	Nagarjuna Agric. Res. Dev. Inst., Secunderabad	4
351	National Center Cell Sci., Pune	4
352	Natl. Environ. Eng. Res. Inst., Naqpur	4
353	Natl. Inst. Oceanogr., Regional Cent., Cochin	4
354	Natl. Res. Cent. Citrus, Nagpur	4
355	Natl. Res. Centre Equines, Hisar	4
356	Natl. Res. Centre Soybean, Indore	4
357	New Arts, Commerce and Science College, Ahmednagar	4
358	PAU Regional Res. Station, Bathinda	4
359	Periyar Coll. Pharmaceutical Sci. Girls, Tiruchirappalli	4
360	PGIMS, Rohtak	4
361	Project Directorate of Biological Control, Bangalore	4
362	Rajiv Gandhi Cent. Biotechnol., Thiruvananthapuram	4
363	Rajiv Gandhi College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Pondicherry	4
364	Ramakrishna Mission Vivekananda College, Chennai	4
365	Reg. Med. Res. Cent., Bhubaneswar	4
366	Regional Agricultural Research Station, Assam Agricultural University, Diphu	4
367	Regional Med. Res. Cent., Port Blair	4
368	Regional Res. Stn., VC Farm, Mandya	4
369	Regional Research Station, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Keonjhar	4
370	Regional Research Station, PAU, Gurdaspur	4

No.	Institution	Number of papers
371	Rice Res. Stn., Chaudhary Charan Singh Haryana Agric. Univ., Kaul	4
372	S.S.V.P.S's L.K.Dr.P.R. Ghogrey Science College, Dhule	4
373	Sardar Patel Univ., Vallabh Vidyanagar	4
374	Sch. Life Sci., Sambalpur Univ., Burla	4
375	Shivaji University, Kolhapur	4
376	Sikkim Forest Dep. Gangtok	4
377	Sir J. J. Group Hospitals and Grant Med. Coll., Mumbai	4
378	SK Inst. Med. Sci., Srinagar	4
379	Tamil Nadu Rice Res. Inst., Aduthurai	4
380	Tamil Nadu Veterinary and Animal Science University, Namakkal	4
381	Tuberculosis Res. Centre, Chennai	4
382	University of Horticulture and Forestry, Kullu	4
383	Vet. Biol. Res. Inst., Hyderabad	4
384	Vet. Hosp., C. K. Palli	4
385	Vidyasagar Univ., Midnapore	4
386	West Bengal Univ. Anim. Fishery Sci., Calcutta	4
387	Agric. Coll., Bapatla	3
388	Agric. Res. Stn., Bidar	3
389	Agric. Res. Stn., Kerala Agric. Univ., Mannuthy	3
390	Agric. Res. Stn., Agronomy Section, Rajasthan Agriculture University, Sriganganagar	3
391	Agricultural Research Station, Rajasthan Agricultural University, Durgapura	3
392	Amravati University, Amravati	3
393	Anthropol. Survey India, North East Regional Centre, Shillong	3
394	Apollo Hosp., Hyderabad	3
395	Aravind Eye Hosp. Madurai	3
396	Astra Research Centre India, Bangalore	3
397	Bhavnagar Univ., Bhavnagar	3

No.	Institution	Number of papers
398	Bot. Survey India, Jodhpur	3
399	Burdwan Raj College, Burdwan	3
400	C C S R I, Bombay	3
401	C.S. Azad University of Agriculture and Technology, Mathura	3
402	Captain Srinivasa Murti Drug Res. Inst. Ayurveda, Chennai	3
403	Cent. JALMA Inst. Leprosy, Agra	3
404	Central Coll., Bangalore Univ., Bangalore	3
405	Central Food Technol. Res. Inst., Ludhiana	3
406	Central Institute for Cotton Research, Nagpur	3
407	Choithram Hosp. Res. Cent. Indore	3
408	Christ College, Irinjalakkuda	3
409	Coll. Agric. Eng., Kamulur	3
410	Coll. Agric., Indore	3
411	Coll. Agric., Orissa Univ. Agric. Technol., Bhubaneswar	3
412	Coll. Basic Sci. Humanities, O.U.A.T., Bhubaneswar	3
413	Coll. Forestry, Kerala Agric. Univ., Trissur	3
414	Coll. Home Sci., Punjab Agric. Univ., Ludhiana	3
415	College of Agriculture, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar	3
416	College of Agriculture, Indore	3
417	Conifers Res. Centre, Shimla	3
418	D.W.R. (ICAR), Karnal	3
419	DDU Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur	3
420	Directorate Oilseeds Res., Hyderabad	3
421	Dr. B.R. Ambedkar University, Agra	3
422	Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada Univ., Aurangabad	3
423	Eastern Regional Station, Indian Vet. Res. Inst., Calcutta	3
424	Environmental Resources Research Centre, Thiruvananthapuram	3
425	Forest Survey of India, Dehra Dun	3

No.	Institution	Number of papers
426	G. B. Pant Inst. Himalayan Environment Development, Garhwal Unit, Srinagar	3
427	Government Coll., Rourkela	3
428	Govt. Fruit Res. Centre, Pithoragarh	3
429	Gujarat Cancer Res. Inst. Ahmedabad	3
430	Gurukul Kangri University, Haridwar	3
431	HPKV, Reg. Res. Stn., Sirmour	3
432	Indian Agric. Statistics Res. Inst., New Delhi	3
433	Indian Cancer Society, Mumbai	3
434	Indian Council Agric. Res., NewDelhi	3
435	Indian Vet. Res. Inst., Bangalore Campus, Bangalore	3
436	Institute of Cytology and Preventive Oncology, Maulana Azad Medica College Campus, NewDelhi	3
437	J. V. College, Baraut, Meerut	3
438	J.N. Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Regional Agric. Res. Stn., Sagar	3
439	J.N.K.V.V. Coll. Agric., Rewa	3
440	J.N.K.V.V. Coll. Agric., Sehore	3
441	J.S.S. Coll. Pharmacy, Ootacamund	3
442	Janata Mahavidyalaya, Etawah	3
443	Kalawati Saran Children's Hosp., NewDelhi	3
444	Kanchi Mamunivar Centre Post-Graduate Studies, Pondicherry	3
445	KEM Hospital Research Centre, Pune	3
446	Kottayam Med. College, Kerala	3
447	Lady Hardinge Medical College, New Delhi	3
448	Lakshminarayan Inst. Technol. Campus, Nagpur Univ., Nagpur	3
449	M L Sukhadia Univ., Udaipur	3
450	M.S. Ramaiah Med. Coll., Bangalore	3
451	Maharashtra Hybrid Seeds Co. Ltd., Toopran Mandal	3
452	Nagarjuna Univ., Nagarjuna Naga	3

No.	Institution	Number of papers
453	Natl. Bur. Anim. Genet. Resources, Karnal	3
454	Natl. Environ. Eng. Res. Inst., CSIR-Complex, Chennai	3
455	Natl. Malaria Eradication Prog., New Delhi	3
456	Natl. Res. Cent. Groundnut, Junagadh	3
457	Orissa Remote Sensing Application Cent., Bhubaneswar	3
458	P.V.P. College, Pravaranagar	3
459	Parsee Gen. Masina Hosp., Bombay	3
460	Project Directorate Poultry, Hyderabad	3
461	Rafi Ahmed Kidwai College of Agriculture, Sehore	3
462	Regional Agric. Res. Stn., IGKV, Boirdadar, Raigarh	3
463	Regional Hort Rs. Station (UHF), Kulu	3
464	Regional Sericultural Research Station, Anantapur	3
465	S. M. M. Town Post-Graduate Coll., Ballia	3
466	Sri Padmavathi Mahila Visvavidyalayam, Tirupati	3
467	T.D. Med. Coll. Hosp., Alleppey	3
468	Tirhut College of Agriculture, Dholi (Muzaffarpur)	3
469	Vet. Coll., Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Anjora	3
470	Vet. Dispensary, Uthamapalayam	3
471	Veterinary Polyclinic, Guntur	3
472	Voluntary Health Serv., Chennai	3
473	Wadia Inst. Himalayan Geol., Dehra Dun	3
474	Zoological Survey of India, Calicut	3
475	22 Mob Fd Vet. Hosp., c/o 56 APO, Hamachal Pradesh KrishiVishvavidyalaya, Palampur	2
476	A.A.U. Reg. Agric. Res. Stn., Shillongani	2
477	Agric. Res. Stn., Rajasthan Agric. Univ., Mandor	2
478	Agric. Res. Stn., Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Kovilpatti	2
479	Agric. Res. Stn., Univ. Agric. Sci., Gulbarga	2
480	Agric. Res. Stn., Vadgaon	2
481	All India Co-ordinated Sorghum Improvement Project	2

No.	Institution	Number of papers
	Regional Research Station, Bijapur	
482	American Coll., Madurai	2
483	Anthropological Survey India, SRC, Mysore	2
484	Arunachal Field Station, Botanical Survey of India, Itanagar	2
485	B.N. Coll. Agric., Assam	2
486	B.V. Patel Pharm. Educ. Res. Dev. Centre, Ahmedabad	2
487	Baishnabchak M.C. High School, Midnapur	2
488	Bansilal Amrutlal College of Agriculture, Anand	2
489	Block Anim. Health Cent., Kamarpukur	2
490	BNHS Res. Station, Okkal	2
491	Breach Candy Hospital, Mumbai	2
492	Burdwan Med. Coll., Burdwan	2
493	C.C.S. H.A.U. Research Station, Rohtak	2
494	C.C.S. University, Meerut	2
495	Cadila Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Ahmedabad	2
496	Calcutta Sch. Tropical Med., Calcutta	2
497	Cent. Earth Sci. Studies, Trivandrum	2
498	Cent. Inst. Agric. Eng., Bhopal	2
499	Cent. Inst. Cotton Res., Nagpur	2
500	Central Inst. Brackishwater Aquaculture, Chennai	2
501	Central Inst. Fisheries Technol., Visakhapatnam	2
502	Central Pollution Control Board, Delhi	2
503	Central Res. Inst. Jute Allied Fibres, Barrackpore	2
504	Central Soil and Water Conservation Res. and Training Inst., Res. Centre, Chandigarh	2
505	Central Tasar Research and Training Institute, Ranchi	2
506	Central Tuber Crops Res. Inst., Trivandrum	2
507	Centre Advanced Technol., Indore	2
508	Centre DNA Finger Printing Diagnosis, Hyderabad	2
509	Centre for Development Studies, Trivandrum	2

No.	Institution	Number of papers
510	Centre for Ecological Research and Conservation, Mysore	2
511	Centre Forestry Res. and Human Resource Development, Chhindwara	2
512	Coll. Agric. Eng., Coimbatore	2
513	Coll. Agric., Kerala Agric. Univ., Trivandrum	2
514	Coll. Dairy Technology, I.G.A.U., Raipur	2
515	Coll. Home Sci., CCS Haryana Agric. Univ., Hisar	2
516	Coll. Home Sci., G. B. Pant Univ. Agric. Technol., Pantnagar	2
517	Coll. Home Sci., Parbhani	2
518	Coll. Pharm., Nashik	2
519	Coll. Pharm., Warangal	2
520	Coll. Technol. Agric. Eng., Udaipur	2
521	College of Agric., Kolhapure	2
522	College of Agriculture (HPKV), Palampur	2
523	College of Agriculture, Calcutta University, Calcutta	2
524	College of Agriculture, Nagpur	2
525	College of Agriculture, Raipur	2
526	Conservator of Forests, Research Circle, Calcutta	2
527	D. S. College, Aligarh	2
528	Dayanand Med. Coll., Ludhiana	2
529	Defence Agric. Res. Lab., Pithoragarh	2
530	Defense Research Laboratory, Tezpur	2
531	Dep. Anat. Forensic Med., Chandigarh	2
532	Dep. Dermatol., Chennai	2
533	Dep. Sci. and Technol., New Delhi	2
534	Dep. Veterinary Med., Fac. Vet. Sci. Anim. Husbandry, Srinagar	2
535	Dhempe Coll. Arts Sci., Panaji	2
536	Dhenkanal Govt. College, Dhenkanal	2
537	Dhoolpet Leprosy Res. Cent., Hyderabad	2
538	Dr. Sampurnand Med. Coll., Jodhpur	2

No.	Institution	Number of papers
539	Escorts Heart Inst. Res. Cent., New Delhi	2
540	FerozeGandhi College, Kanpur	2
541	Food Fermentation Technol. Div., Dep. Chemical Technology, Mumbai	2
542	Forensic Sci. Lab., Jagdalpur	2
543	Foundation Med. Res., Bombay	2
544	G. B. Pant Univ. Agric. and Technol., Tehri Garhwal	2
545	G.G.M. Science College, Jammu	2
546	Geol. Survey India, Calcutta	2
547	Geol. Survey India, Nagpur	2
548	Government Arts Coll., Coimbatore	2
549	Government Kolasib College, Kolasib	2
550	Govt. M.S.J. College, Bharatpur	2
551	Grant Medical Coll., Mumbai	2
552	Gujarat Cancer Society, Ahmedabad	2
553	Guru Jambheshwar Univ., Hisar	2
554	Himalaya Drug Company, Bangalore	2
555	Himalayan Inst. Med. Sci., Dehradun	2
556	Hindustan Lever Res. Centre, Mumbai	2
557	HPKV Reg. Res. Station, Kinnaur	2
558	I.C.F.R.E., Dehra Dun	2
559	ICAR Project Anim. Dis. Monitoring and Surveillance, Bangalore	2
560	IGFRI, RRS, UAS Campus, Dharwad	2
561	Indian Inst. Hortic. Res., Ranchi	2
562	Indian Petrochemicals Corp. Ltd., Baroda	2
563	Indira Gandhi Centre Atomic Res., Kalpakkam	2
564	Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Regional Agric. Res. Stn., Raigarh	2
565	Inst. Anim. Health Prod., Ranchi	2
566	Inst. Human Behavior Allied Sci., Delhi	2

No.	Institution	Number of papers
567	Inst. Med. Sci., Mumbai	2
568	Inst. Vet. Preventive Med., Ranipet	2
569	Institute of Pharmacy, Wardha	2
570	IVLP, Dr. PDKV, Akola	2
571	J.N.K.V.V. Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Aron	2
572	Jai Hind College of Arts, Science and Commerce, Dhule	2
573	Jaslok Hosp. Res. Centre, Bombay	2
574	JNKVV, Zonal Agric. Res. Stn., Tikamgarh	2
575	K.N.K. Coll. Agric., Mandasaur	2
576	Kongunadu Arts and Sci. Coll., Coimbatore	2
577	KVK, NDRI, Karnal	2
578	Livestock Res. Stn., Vallabnagar	2
579	Livestock Research Station, Gujarat Agric. University, Navsari	2
580	M. L. S. M. College, Sundernagar	2
581	M.D. (P.G.) College, Sriganaganagar	2
582	M.E.S.K.V.M. Coll., Valanchery	2
583	M.I.M.S.R. Med. Coll., Latur	2
584	Madras Christian Coll., Tambaram, Chennai	2
585	Madras Med. Mission, Chennai	2
586	Maharaja Bir Bikram Coll., Agartala	2
587	MahatmaGandhi Inst. Med. Sci., Sevagram	2
588	Malaria Research Centre (Field Station), Haldwani	2
589	Malaria Research Centre (Field Station), Panaji	2
590	Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal	2
591	Monsanto Enterprises Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi	2
592	Narendra Deva Univ. Agric. Technol., Ghazipur	2
593	National Agricultural Research Project, Mahabaleshwar	2
594	National Bureau of Fish Genetic Resources, Lucknow	2
595	National Centre Compositional Characterization Materials, Hyderabad	2

No.	Institution	Number of papers
596	Natl. Geophysical Res. Inst., Hyderabad	2
597	Natl. Inst. Hydrol., Roorkee	2
598	Natl. Inst. Occupational Health ICMR, Ahmedabad	2
599	Natl. Inst. Oceanogr., Regional Cent., Bombay	2
600	Natl. Res. Centre Agroforestry, Jhansi	2
601	New Coll., Kolhapur	2
602	Nizam Coll., Hyderabad	2
603	NRC Women Agric., Bhubaneshwar	2
604	NS Vet. Hosp., Pune	2
605	Office Deputy Director Agric., Raigarh	2
606	Office Intensive Cattle Dev. Project, Govt. Assam, Guiwahati	2
607	Orissa Vet. Coll., Orissa Univ. Agric. Technol., Bhubaneshwar	2
608	Pramukhswami Med. Coll., Karamsad	2
609	Presidency College, Calcutta	2
610	Project Directorate Cropping Syst. Res., Meerut	2
611	R.D. and D.J. Coll., Munger	2
612	Rajasthan Agric. Univ., Jaipur	2
613	Raman Centre for Applied and Interdisciplinary Sciences, Calcutta	2
614	Raman Res. Inst., Bangalore	2
615	Ranbaxy Res. Lab., New Delhi	2
616	RARS, Shillongani, Navgaon	2
617	Reg. Agric. Res. Stn., Orissa Univ. Agric. Technol., Sunabeda	2
618	Reg. Res. Stn., Punjab Agric. Univ., Nawan Shahar	2
619	Reg. Res. Stn., Tamil Nadu Agric Univ., Vriddhachalam	2
620	Regional Agric. Res. Stn., Assam Agric. Univ., Titabar	2
621	Regional Forensic Sci. Lab., Aurangabad	2
622	Regional Horticultural Research Station, Sirmour	2
623	Regional Res. Station, H.P. Krishi Vishvavidyalaya, Dhaulakuan	2

No.	Institution	Number of papers
624	Regional Res. Stn., Ghumsar Udayagiri	2
625	Regional Research Station, Raichur	2
626	Regional Station, Central Plantation Crops Research Institute, Kayangulam	2
627	Regional Station, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, Karnal	2
628	Regional STD Teaching Res. Cent. Safdarjung Hosp., New Delhi	2
629	Res. Stn., Govind Ballabh Pant Univ. Agric. Technol., Bulandshahar	2
630	Rice Research Station, Punjab Agricultural University, Kapurthala	2
631	Rubber Research Institute of India, North Eastern Research Complex, Agartala	2
632	S. G. N. Khalsa College, Sriganganagar	2
633	S.P. Medical College, Bikaner	2
634	Salim Ali Sch. Ecol. Environ. Sci., Pondicherry Univ., Pondicherry	2
635	Sankara Nethralaya, Vision Res. Found., Chennai	2
636	Seth G S Medical Coll., K E M Hosp., Mumbai	2
637	Shivdan Singh Coll., Aligarh	2
638	Soil Water Manage. Res. Inst., Tamil Nadu Agric. Univ., Thanjavur	2
639	St. John's Coll., Agra	2
640	St. Teresa's Coll., Ernakulam	2
641	St. Xavier's College, Mumbai	2
642	State Forest Res. Inst., Itanagar	2
643	State Inst. Anim. Health, Tanuku,	2
644	Sugarcane Breed. Inst. Reg. Cent., Karnal	2
645	Sugarcane Res. Station, Tamil Nadu Agric. Univ., Cuddalore	2
646	Survey Med. Plants Unit, Reg. Res. Inst. Unani Med., Bhadrak	2
647	Tata Meml. Cent., Mumbai	2

No.	Institution	Number of papers
648	Thapor Inst. Eng. Technol., Patiala	2
649	Tharpar Corporate R and D Cent., Patiala	2
650	U.P. College, Varanasi	2
651	U.P. Council of Sugarcane Research, Shahjahanpur	2
652	Univ. Agric. Sci. Technol., Srinagar	2
653	Univ. Agric. Sci., Coll. Fish., Mangalore	2
654	Univ. Agric. Sci., Dharwad Vet. Coll., Bidar	2
655	Vaccine Res. Centre, Centre Animal Health Studies, Chennai	2
656	Vet. Hosp., Pattan	2
657	Vigyan Bhavan, Devi Ahilya Univ., Indore	2
658	Vittal Mallya Sci. Res. Found., Bangalore	2
659	Voorhees Coll., Veilore	2
660	Willingdon Hosp., Chennai	2
661	130 GKNM Hosp., P. N. Palayam, Coimbatore	1
662	A P C Mahalaxmi Coll. Women, Tuticorin	1
663	A. A. U. Regional Agric. Res. Stn., North Lakhimpur	1
664	A. B. Shetty Memorial Inst. Dental Sci., Mangalore	1
665	A. K. Tibbiya Coll., Aligarh Muslim Univ., Aligarh	1
666	A. P. A. U. Rajendranagar, Hyderabad	1
667	A. R. Coll. Pharm, Vallabh Vidyanagar	1
668	A.H. Dep., Sasaram	1
669	A.H. Dept., Govt. of A.P., Hyderabad	1
670	A.N.G.R.A.U., Agric. Res. Stn., Podalakur	1
671	A.N.S. College, Barh	1
672	A.V. Baliga College Arts Sci., Kumta	1
673	A.V.C. Coll., Mannampandal	1
674	A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam Coll., Poondi	1
675	Achhruram Meml. Coll., Jhalda	1
676	Adaptive Trial Centre, Government of Rajasthan, Chittorgarh	1
677	Additional Block Anim. Health Cent., Joyrambati	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
678	Adiparasakthi Coll. Pharm., Melmaruvathur	1
679	Aditya Jyot Eye Hosp., Mumbai	1
680	Agra Coll., Agra	1
681	Agric. Coll. Res. Inst., Navalur Kuttappattu, Tiruchirappalli	1
682	Agric. Coll., Mahanandi	1
683	Agric. Coll., U. A. S. G. K. V. K., Bangalore	1
684	Agric. Res. Stn., Maruteru	1
685	Agric. Res. Stn., Navgaon, Alwar	1
686	Agric. Res. Stn., Niphad	1
687	Agric. Res. Stn., Tamil Nadu Agric. Univ., Paramakudi	1
688	Agric. Res. Stn., Univ. Agric. Sci., Sirsi	1
689	Agric. Sch. Compound, Solapur	1
690	Agricultural Res. Station, KADIRI, Anantapur	1
691	Agriculture Research Station, Rajasthan Agricultural University, Jodhpur	1
692	Agril. Research Station, K. Digraj	1
693	Agronomy, CS WCR TI, Res. Cent., Datia	1
694	Ajara Mahavidyalay, Ajara	1
695	Al Ameen Coll. Pharm., Bangalore	1
696	Al-Ameen Med. Coll., Bijapur	1
697	Alamelu Angappan Coll. Women, Komarapalayam	1
698	All India Coord. Res. Proj. Groundnut, NRCG, Junagadh	1
699	All India Shri Shivaji Meml. Soc. Coll. Pharm., Pune	1
700	Am. Coll., Madurai	1
701	Amar Eye Center, New Delhi	1
702	Amar Singh Coll., Lakhaoti	1
703	Amarnath Polyclinic, Balasore	1
704	Ambah P.G. Autonomous Coll., Ambah	1
705	Ambala Sarabhai Enterprises, Baroda	1
706	Andaman and Nicobar Islands Forest and Plantation Development Corp. Ltd., Port Blair	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
707	Andaman Nicobar Centre Ocean Dev., Dep. Ocean Dev., Port Blair	1
708	Andhra Univ., Waltair	1
709	Andhra Pradesh. Agric. Univ., Rajendranagar	1
710	Angrau Coll. Vet. Sci., Tirupati	1
711	ANGRAU, Agric. Res. Stn., Bacterial Inoculants Scheme, Amaravathi	1
712	Anim. Health Cent., Nellore	1
713	Anim. Health Cent., Ongole	1
714	Anim. Husbandry Dep., Himachal Pradesh	1
715	Anim. Husbandry Dep., Kurnool	1
716	Anim. Husbandry Dep., Vizianagaram	1
717	Anim. Husbandry Vet. Dep., Gov. Assam, Guwhati	1
718	Anim. Resour. Dev. Dep., Govt. West Bengal, Calcutta	1
719	Anim. Resources Animal Health, West Bengal, Calcutta	1
720	Animal Health Centre, Anantapur	1
721	Animal Husbandry Dep., Hyderabad	1
722	Animal Husbandry Department, Vijayawada	1
723	Animal Husbandry Vet. Dep., Government Nagaland, Assam Agric. Univ., Khanapara	1
724	Anthropol. Survey India, N.W. Regional Centre, Dehradun	1
725	Anthropol. Survey India, Sub Regional Centre, Jagdalpur	1
726	APAU Regional Agric. Res. Stn., Palem	1
727	APS Univ., Rewa	1
728	Aravalli Afforestation Project, Jhadol	1
729	Arignar Anna Govern. Arts Coll., Karaikal	1
730	Armed Forces Med. Coll., Pune	1
731	Arts Sci. Comm., Coll., Satana	1
732	Arunachal Pradesh Orchid Res. Cent., Bhalukpong	1
733	Arunachal Univ., Itanagar	1
734	Asopalov Eye Hosp., Ahmedabad	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
735	Assam Agric. Univ., Raha	1
736	Assam Inst. Res. Tribals Scheduled Cases, Guwahati	1
737	Assam Univ., Silchar	1
738	Avinashilingam Inst. Home Sci. Higher Educ. Women, Deemed Univ., Coimbatore	1
739	B. C. Roy Post Graduate Inst. Basic Med. Sci., Calcutta	1
740	B.D. Amin Hospital, Baroda	1
741	B.J. Wadia Hosp. Child., Parel	1
742	B.N. Bandodkar Coll. Sci., Thane	1
743	Baba Saheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow	1
744	Banasthali Vidyapith, Banasthali	1
745	Bangabasi Coll., Calcutta	1
746	BARC Facilities, Kalpakkram	1
747	Bareilly Coll., Bareilly	1
748	Bengal Eng. Coll., Deemed Univ., Howrah	1
749	Bhagavan Mahavir Med. Res. Cent., Hyderabad	1
750	Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalimpong	1
751	Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani	1
752	Bidhannagar State General Hosp., Calcutta	1
753	Biomed Hitech Industries Ltd., Chennai	1
754	Birla Inst. Technol., Mesra, Ranchi	1
755	Block Anim. Health Centre, Ranibandh	1
756	Block Office, Vettikavaia	1
757	Bombay Cancer Registry, Mumbai	1
758	Bombay Leprosy Project, Mumbai	1
759	Bot. Survey India, Calcutta	1
760	Branch Med., Schieffelin Lepr. Res. Train. Cent., Karigiri	1
761	BS Gov. P.G. Coll., Jaora	1
762	C. Abdul Hakeem Coll., Melvisharam	1
763	C.U. Shah Coll. Pharm., S.N.D.T. Women's Univ., Mumbai	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
764	Calcutta Med. Coll., Calcutta	1
765	Calcutta Municipal Corp., Calcutta	1
766	CCS Haryana Agricultural University Cotton Res. Stn., Sirsa	1
767	CDR Hosp., Visakhapatnam, India	1
768	Cent. Agric. Res. Inst., Izatnagar	1
769	Cent. Anim. Health Studies, Chennai	1
770	Cent. Coll. Campus, Bangalore Univ., Bangalore	1
771	Cent. Inst. Fish Education, Versova	1
772	Cent. Mar. Fish. Res. Inst., Bombay Res. Cent., Bombay	1
773	Cent. Mar. Fish. Res. Inst., Res. Cent., Minicoy, Lakshadweep	1
774	Cent. Plant. Crops Res. Inst., Krishnapuram	1
775	Cent. Post Graduate Studies, Pondicherry	1
776	Cent. Potato Res. Stn., Gwalior	1
777	Cent. Potato Res. Stn., Modipuram	1
778	Cent. Tuber Crops Res. Inst., Trivandrum	1
779	Cent. Univ. Lab., Madhavarani Milk Colony, Chennai	1
780	Cent. Water Resources Dev. Manage., Kozhikode	1
781	Central Agricultural Univ., Iroisemba	1
782	Central Coffee Res. Inst., Chikmagalur	1
783	Central Food Lab., Calcutta	1
784	Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Ministry Home Affairs, Hyderabad	1
785	Central Inland Capture Fisheries Res. Inst., Allahabad	1
786	Central Institute for Cotton Research Regional Station, Sirsa	1
787	Central Marine Fisheries Res. Inst., Mangalore	1
788	Central Mining Res. Inst., Dhanbad	1
789	Central Plantation Crops Res. Inst., Kasagod	1
790	Central Sheep and Wool Research Institute, Garsa	1
791	Central Sugarcane Research Station, Padegaon	1
792	Central Tobacco Res. Inst., Rajahmundry	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
793	Central Water Power Res. Station, Pune	1
794	Centre for Development Studies, U.P. Academy of Administration, Nainital	1
795	Centre for Research in Medical Entomology, Madurai	1
796	Centre Inter-disciplinary Studies Mountain Hill Environment, University Delhi South Campus, New Delhi	1
797	CFL Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Mumbai	1
798	Christ Church College, Kanpur	1
799	CIAMP Field Stn., Pulwama	1
800	CIFE, Versova, Mumbai	1
801	CIRB, Sirsa Road, Hisar	1
802	Civil Hosp., Ahmedabad	1
803	Civil Vet. Hosp., Gurdaspur	1
804	Coll. Vet. Sci., Punjab Agric. Univ., Ludhiana	1
805	Coll. Agric. Imphal, Manipur	1
806	Coll. Agric., GKVK, Bangalore	1
807	Coll. Agric., Raichur	1
808	Coll. Agric., Ratnagiri	1
809	Coll. Agric., Sehore	1
810	Coll. Anim. Sci. Livestock Production, Abeokuta	1
811	Coll. Anim. Sci., CCS Haryana Agric. Univ., Hisar	1
812	Coll. Applied Sci. Women, Delhi	1
813	Coll. Basic Sci. and Humanities, Punjab Agric. Univ., Ludhiana	1
814	Coll. Dental Surgery, Mangalore	1
815	Coll. Forestry, Univ. Agric. Sci., Sirsi	1
816	Coll. Home Sci., HPKV, Palampur	1
817	Coll. Pharm., New Delhi	1
818	Coll. Rural Home Sci., Dharwad	1
819	Coll. Science, M.L. Sukhadia Univ., Udaipur	1
820	Coll. Vet. Sci., Shen-e-Kashmir Univ. Agric. Sci. Technol.,	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
	Srinagar	
821	College Engineering, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam	1
822	College Home Sci., Marathwada Agricultural Univ., Parbhani	1
823	College of Agriculture, Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Rewa	1
824	College of Agriculture, Kerala Agricultural University, Nileshtar	1
825	College of Agriculture, Raichur	1
826	College of Agriculture, Vellayani	1
827	College of Home Science, Palampur	1
828	Command Hosp., Udampur	1
829	Conservation Nature Trust, Calicut	1
830	Cotton Rasearch Station, Nanded	1
831	Cotton Res. Scheme, MAU, Parbhani	1
832	COVAS, HPKV, Palampur	1
833	Crop Research Unit (Oilseeds), Dr. PDKV, Akola	1
834	CSIR Cent. Math. Modelling Computer Simulation, Bangalore	1
835	CSIR, Mall Rd., Delhi	1
836	D. A. V. College, Jalandhar	1
837	D. G. Ruparel Coll., Mahim, Mumbai	1
838	D. G. Vaishnav, College, Chennai	1
839	D.K. College, Mirza	1
840	D.M. Coll. Sci., Umphal	1
841	D.R. Coll., Golaghat	1
842	Dabur Res. Found., New Delhi	1
843	Dairy Sci. Coll., Univ. Agric. Sci., Bangalore	1
844	Darjeeling Govern. Coll., Darjeeling	1
845	DAV Coll. Women, Karnal	1
846	Dayanand Post-Grad. Coll., Hisar	1
847	Deccan Coll. Res. Inst., Pune	1
848	Defence Bioeng. Electromedical Lab., Bangalore	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
849	Defence Lab., Jodhpur	1
850	Dep. Anim. Breeding Genet., Vet. Sci., Jabalpur	1
851	Dep. Anim. Husbandry, Viskhapatnam	1
852	Dep. At. Energy, Hyderabad	1
853	Dep. Biochem., Chennai	1
854	Dep. Chem. Eng., Biochem. Eng. Div., Calcutta	1
855	Dep. Entomol. Apic., Dr. Y. S. Parmar Univ. Hortic. For., Solan	1
856	Dep. Entomol., Coll. Agric., Gwalior	1
857	Dep. Microbiol., J. J. Coll. Arts Sci., Pudukkottai	1
858	Dep. Microbiol., Sri Krishnadevaraya Univ., Anantapur	1
859	Dep. Neuroimmunol., New Delhi	1
860	Dep. Postharvest Technol., Univ. Horticulture Forestry, Solan	1
861	Dep. SAF, COF, UHF, Nauni, Solan	1
862	Dhanapalan Coll., Chennai	1
863	Diabetes Clinic and Research Centre, Nagpur	1
864	Diagn. Centre, Munger	1
865	Dibrugarh Hanumanbox Surajmal Kanoi Coll., Dibrugarh	1
866	Dibrugarh Univ., TRA Tocklai Exp. Stn., Jorhat	1
867	Directorate Anim. Health, Government of West Bengal, Calcutta	1
868	District Anim. Husbandry, Udaipur	1
869	Div. Gastroenterol., Hepatol. Nutr., Dep. Pediatr., ICMR Advanced Centre Diarrheal Dis. Res., All India Inst. Med. Sci., New Delhi	1
870	Div. Standardisation, Izatnagar	1
871	Div. Vet. Hospital, Bilaspur	1
872	Dr Vaishampayan Meml. Med. Coll., Solapur	1
873	Dr. B. C. Guha Cent. Genet. Eng. and Biotechnol., Univ. Coll. Sci., Calcutta	1
874	Dr. Balabhai Nanavati Hosp. and MRC, Mumbai	1
875	Dr. D.Y. Patil Medical Coll., Mumbai	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
876	Dr. V. M. Medical Coll., Solapur	1
877	Duliajan Coll., Duliajan, Assam, India	1
878	Dy. Conservator Forests, East Melghat Div., Amravati, Maharashtra, India	1
879	Dy. Conservator of Forests, Buldhana Forest Div., Buldhana, Maharashtra, India	1
880	Eastern Regional Forestry Office, Biratnagar, Morang, India	1
881	Environ. Appl. Training Educ., Dehradun	1
882	Environ. Control Development Consultants, Calcutta	1
883	EPC Irrigation Ltd., Nashik	1
884	Farmers Train Cent., Hosur	1
885	Fish. Coll. Res. Inst., Tuticorin	1
886	Ford Foundation, New Delhi	1
887	Forest Coll. Res. Inst., Mettupalayam	1
888	Forest College, Sirsi	1
889	Forest Dep., Govt. Sikkim, Gangtok	1
890	Foundation Res. Dev. Among Underprivileged Groups, New Delhi	1
891	Foundation Revitalisation Local Health Traditions, Bangalore	1
892	Fredrick Inst. Plant Prot. Toxicol., Padappal	1
893	G. B. Pant Inst. Himalayan Environ. Dev., Shamshi	1
894	G. S. Sugarcane Breeding and Res. Inst. Tamkuhi Raj	1
895	G.B. Pant Univ. Agric. and Technol., Tehri Garhwal	1
896	Garden City Coll. Sci. Management Studies, Bangalore	1
897	GBPUA and T Res. Stn., Ujhani	1
898	GBPUAT, Nagina, Bijnor	1
899	General Hosp., Tata Tea Ltd., Munnar	1
900	Geol. Survey India, Western Region, Jaipur	1
901	Geological Survey India, Visakhapatnam	1
902	Geo-Miller and Co. Ltd., New Delhi	1
903	Gitam Coll. Engineering, Visakhapatnam	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
904	Goa Med. Coll., Bambolim, Goa	1
905	Godrej Agrovvet Ltd., Chennai	1
906	Godrej and Boyce Mfg. Co. Ltd., Mumbai	1
907	Gokhale Eye Hosp., Mumbai	1
908	Gov. Eng. Coll., Jabalpur	1
909	Gov. Med. Sci. Coll., Raipur	1
910	Government Autoumous Science Post Graduate College, Bilaspur	1
911	Government Cattle Breeding Farm, Yavatmal	1
912	Government Coll., Nelakondapalli	1
913	Government Medical Coll., Aurangabad	1
914	Government P.G. Coll., Jind	1
915	Government Postgraduate College, Pithoragarh	1
916	Government College, Ajmer	1
917	Govt. Camp College for Kashmir Migrants, Jammu(Tawi)	1
918	Govt. Coll. Chachaura-Binaganj, Guna	1
919	Govt. Girls Coll., Tikamgarh	1
920	Govt. Inst. Sci., Aurangabad	1
921	Govt. of Karnataka, Bangalore	1
922	Govt. Victoria College, Palakkad	1
923	Govt. Women Coll., Gandhi Nagar	1
924	Gujarat Agricultural University, Arnej	1
925	Gujarat Agricultural University, Jamnagar	1
926	Gujarat Ecological Education and Research Foundation, Gandhinagar	1
927	Gujarat Institute of Desert Ecology, Bhuj-Kachchh	1
928	Gujarat Pollution Control Board, Gandhinagar	1
929	Gupta Inst., Jabalpur	1
930	Guru Ghasidas Univ., Bilaspur	1
931	Guru Nanak Coll., Chennai	1
932	Gurudas College, Calcutta	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
933	Haffkine Inst., Mumbai	1
934	Haryana Forest Dev. Corp. Ltd., Panchkula	1
935	High Altitude Plant Physiology Research Centre, HNB Garhwal University, Srinagar Garhwal	1
936	Himalayan Forest Res. Inst., Shimla	1
937	Himalayan Inst. Hosp. Trust, Dehra Dun	1
938	Hind Kusht Nivaran Sangh-Maharashtra State Branch, Mumbai	1
939	Hinduja Natl. Hosp., Med. Res. Cent., Bombay	1
940	Hindustan Insecticides Ltd., R and D Centre, Gurgaon	1
941	Holkar Sci. Coll., Indore	1
942	Home Sci. Coll. Res. Inst., Tamil Nadu Agric. Univ., Madurai	1
943	Hooghly Mohsin College, Hooghly	1
944	Horticultural Res. Stn., Dr. Y.S. Parmar Univ. Horticul. For., Dhaulakuan	1
945	Horticultural Res. Stn., Tamil Nadu Agric. Univ., Thadiyankudisai	1
946	HPKV, Res. Sub-Stn., Salooni	1
947	I A R I, Regional Station, Shimla	1
948	I.C.M.R. Cent. Advanced Res. Enteric Dis., Dep. Gastrointestinal Sci., Vellore	1
949	I/C Civil Vet. Hosp., Ludhiana	1
950	ICAR Res. Complex N.E.H. Region, Manipur Centre, Imphal	1
951	ICAR Res. Complex, Jharnapani	1
952	ICAR Research Complex for Goa, Ela, Old Goa	1
953	ICAR, Sikkim Centre, Sikkim	1
954	Indian Agric. Res. Inst., Regional Station, Karnal	1
955	Indian Agric. Res. Inst., Regional Station, Katrain	1
956	Indian Assoc. Leprol., Maharashtra Branch, Bombay	1
957	Indian Bureau Mines, Nagpur	1
958	Indian Council Agric. Res., Inst. Anim. Health Vet. Biol. Campus, Bangalore	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
959	Indian Council Med. Res. Madurai	1
960	Indian Inst. Health Management Res., Jaipur	1
961	Indian Inst. Petroleum, Dehradun	1
962	Indian Inst. Spices Res., Madikeri	1
963	Indian Inst. Tropical Meteorol., Pune	1
964	Indian Institute Technology, Guwahati	1
965	Indian Petrochem. Corp. Ltd., Vadodara	1
966	Indian Railways Cancer Inst. Res. Cent., Varanasi	1
967	Indian Rare Earths Limited, Udyogamandal	1
968	Indian Sch. Mines, Dhanbad	1
969	Indian Vet. Res. Inst., Nainital	1
970	Indira Ghandi Agric. Univ., Durg	1
971	Inland Capture Fish. Res. Inst., ICAR, Malda	1
972	Inst. Advanced Study Sci. Technol., Guwahati	1
973	Inst. Anim. Health Vet. Biol., Calcutta	1
974	Inst. Animal Health Vet. Biol., Trivandrum	1
975	Inst. Biol. Prod., Mhow	1
976	Inst. Francais Pondichery, Pondicherry	1
977	Inst. Pediatric Gastroenterology, S.M.S. Med. Coll., Jaipur	1
978	Inst. Pharmacol., Chennai Med. College, Chennai	1
979	Inst. Postgraduate Med. Education Res., Calcutta	1
980	Inst. Psychiatry Human Behaviour, Goa	1
981	Inst. Res. Medical Statistics ICMR, Chennai	1
982	Inst. Social Economic Change, Bangalore	1
983	Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Varanasi	1
984	Institute of Forest Productivity, Ranchi	1
985	International Institute for Population Sciences, Mumbai	1
986	J. N. K. V. V. Kailash Nath Katju Coll. Agric., Mandsaur	1
987	J.K. Univ. Agric. Sci. Technol., Srinagar	1
988	J.L.N. Med. Coll., Ajmer	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
989	J.S.S. Coll. Pharm., Mysore	1
990	Jamal Mohamed Coll., Tiruchirappalli	1
991	Jawaharlal Nehru Ayurvedic Med. Plants Garden Herbarium, Pune	1
992	Jawaharlal Nehru Hosp. Res. Cent., Bhilainagar	1
993	Jhargram Raj Coll., Jhargram	1
994	JNKVV Res. Stn., Badnawar, India	1
995	JNKVV Zonal Agric. Res. Stn., Powarkheda	1
996	JSS Inst. Econ. Res., Dharwad	1
997	K. B. Inst. Pharm. Educ. and Res., Gandhinagar	1
998	Kamdheni Vet. Cent., Rudrapur	1
999	Kancor Flavours Extracts Ltd., Angamally	1
1000	Kanha Tiger Reserve, Mandla	1
1001	Karimganj College, Karimganj	1
1002	Karnataka Assoc. Advancement Sci., Bangalore	1
1003	Kempegowda Inst. Med. Sci., Bangalore	1
1004	Kerala Agric. Univ., Aromatic and Medicinal Plants Res. Station, Asmannoor	1
1005	Kerala Agric. Univ., Coll. Agric., Nileshwar	1
1006	Kerala Agric. Univ., Mannuthy	1
1007	Khallikote Coll., Berhampur	1
1008	Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Palghar	1
1009	Kothari Med. Cent. Res. Inst., Calcutta	1
1010	Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Baran	1
1011	Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Tezpur	1
1012	Kuvempu Univ., Jnana Sahyadri, B RProject Shimoga	1
1013	Kuvempu Univ., Shankaraghatta	1
1014	L.L.R.M. Medical College, Meerut	1
1015	Lady Shri Ram Coll., New Delhi	1
1016	Lakhimpur Coll. Vet. Sci., Assam Agric. Univ., North Lakhimpur	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
1017	Livestock Prod. Res., Izatnagar	1
1018	Livestock Res. Stn., GAU, Anand	1
1019	Livestock Res. Stn., Kattupakkam	1
1020	Livestock Unit, Vedurakuppam	1
1021	Lohia Govt. College, Churu	1
1022	M. D. S. University, Ajmer	1
1023	M. P. Shah Med. Coll., Jamnagar	1
1024	M.C. Coll. Barpeta	1
1025	M.D. Coll., Bombay	1
1026	M.G.M. College, Udupi	1
1027	M.L.B. Med. Coll., Jhansi	1
1028	M.R. Coll., Vizianagaram	1
1029	M.S. Coll., Saharanpur	1
1030	M.V.P. Samaj's Coll. Pharm., Nashik	1
1031	Madras Diabetes Res. Found., Chennai	1
1032	Madras Vet. Coll., Namakkal	1
1033	Magadh Mahila College, Patna University, Patna	1
1034	Magadh University, Bodh Gaya	1
1035	Maharaja Coll. Women, Perundurai	1
1036	Maharaja Coll., Ara	1
1037	Maharaja Manindra Chandra Coll., Calcutta	1
1038	Maharashtra Van Sanshodhan Sanstha, Chandrapur	1
1039	Mahatma Gandhi Gramodaya Vishwavidyalays, Chitrakoot	1
1040	Majalgaon Coll., Majalgaon Beed	1
1041	Malaria Research Centre (Field Station), Chennai	1
1042	Malaria Research Centre (Field Station), Malacca	1
1043	Malladi Res. Centre, Chennai	1
1044	Mangrove Res. Cent., Regional Plant Resource Cent., Bhubaneswar	1
1045	Manipur College, Imphal	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
1046	Mar. Biol. Res. Stn. (Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth), Ratnagiri	1
1047	Marwari Coll., Ranchi	1
1048	Med. Coll., Baroda	1
1049	Med. Coll., Trivandrum	1
1050	Med. Collge, Allahabad	1
1051	Med. Serv., Khandelwal Lab. Ltd., Mumbai	1
1052	Medwin Hospitals, Hyderabad	1
1053	Meenakshi Mission Hosp. Res. Cent., Madurai	1
1054	Meerut Government of Uttar Pradesh, Meerut	1
1055	Midnapore Coll., Midnapore	1
1056	MIMER Med. Coll., Pune	1
1057	MKCG Med. Coll., Berhampur	1
1058	Monilek Hosp. Res. Cent., Jaipur	1
1059	Moolchand K.R. Hosp., New Delhi	1
1060	MRI, Bombay Hospital, Bombay	1
1061	Mysore Paper Mills Ltd., Shimogan	1
1062	N.A.R.P., Igatpuri	1
1063	N.N.S. Coll., Titabor	1
1064	Nagaland University, Mokokchung	1
1065	Naik Hospital, Pune	1
1066	Naoroji Godrej Cent. Plant Res., Khandala Taluka	1
1067	National Dairy Res. Inst., Eastern Regional Station, Kalyani	1
1068	National Dairy Research Institute, Bangalore	1
1069	National Inst. Pharmaceutical Education and Res., S.A.S.Nagar	1
1070	National Research Centre for Sorghum, Hyderabad	1
1071	National Seed Project, Hyderabad	1
1072	Natl. AIDS Control Organization, NewDelhi	1
1073	Natl. Bureau Plant Genet. Resour., Regional Stn., Bhowali	1
1074	Natl. Bureau Plant Genetic Resources, Regional Stn., Shillong	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
1075	Natl. Centre Medium Range Weather Forecasting, Mausam Bhavan, New Delhi	1
1076	Natl. Inst. Res. Jute Allied Fibre Technol., ICAR, Calcutta	1
1077	Natl. Metallurgical Lab., Jamshedpur	1
1078	Natl. Physical Lab., New Delhi	1
1079	Natl. Res. Cent. Cashew, Puttur	1
1080	Natl. Res. Cent. Coldwater Fish., Pithoragarh	1
1081	Natl. Res. Centre Rapeseed-Mustard, Bharatpur	1
1082	NEERI Zonal Laboratory, IICT Campus, Hyderabad	1
1083	Nehru Meml. Mus. and Library, New Delhi	1
1084	Netaji Nagar Day Coll., Calcutta	1
1085	New Coll., Chennai	1
1086	Niku Bio-Research Lab, Pune	1
1087	North Lakhimpur Coll., North Lakhimpur	1
1088	North Maharashtra Univ., Jalgaon	1
1089	O. U. Coll. Women, Hyderabad	1
1090	O.U.A.T. Agric. Res. Stn., Berhampur	1
1091	Office Project Director, Agri. Soil Survey, Bikaner	1
1092	Oilseeds Research Station, Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Kangra	1
1093	Oilseeds Research Station, Jalgaon	1
1094	Omega Ag-Seeds Ltd., Hyderabad	1
1095	Oriental Coll., Imphal	1
1096	Orissa Forest Dev. Corpn. Ltd., Bhubaneswar	1
1097	P. D. Hinduja Natl. Hosp., Bombay	1
1098	P.K. Roy Memorial Coll., Dhanbad	1
1099	P.M.B. Gujarati Sci. Coll., Indore	1
1100	Panskura Banamali Coll., Midnapore	1
1101	Patna Univ., Patna	1
1102	PAU Kandi Res. Stn. Balachaur	1
1103	Peripheral Vet. Hosp., Chennai	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
1104	Periyar EVR Coll., Tiruchirappalli	1
1105	Pet Clin., Haldwani	1
1106	Pharmacol. Clin. Pharmacol., Vellore	1
1107	Police Forensic Sci. Lab., Jaipur	1
1108	Poona Coll. Pharm., Pune	1
1109	Post Graduate Inst. Basic Med. Sci., Univ. Madras, Chennai	1
1110	Potato Res. Stn., Deesa	1
1111	Prima Agro Prod. Ltd., Kochi	1
1112	Priyadarsini Inst. Paramed. Sci., Medical Coll., Thiruvananthapuram	1
1113	Project Wetland Birds, Biocontrol Lab., Gujarat Agric. Univ., Anand	1
1114	PSG Coll. Arts Sciences, Coimbatore	1
1115	PSS Central Inst. Vocational Educ., Bhopal	1
1116	Pt. B.D. Sharma Post Grad. Inst. Med. Sci., Rohtak	1
1117	Punjab Agric. Univ., Regional Res. Station, Ropar	1
1118	Punjab State Council Sci. Technol. Chandigarh	1
1119	R.G. Stone Clin., New Delhi	1
1120	R.L.S.Y. Coll., Aurangabad	1
1121	R.N.T. Memorial Clinic, Muzaffarpur	1
1122	Raja Balwant Singh Coll., Agra	1
1123	Raja Balwant Singh College, Bichpuri	1
1124	Rajah Muthiah Med. Coll. Hosp., Annamalai Univ., Annamalai Nagar	1
1125	Rajasthan Agric. Univ., S. K. N. Coll. Agric., Jobner	1
1126	Ramakrishna Mission Vivekenanada Centenary College, Rahara	1
1127	Ranchi Univ., Ranchi	1
1128	Range Forest Officer, Aravalli Afforestation Project, Rajasthan	1
1129	RD Lab., Indian Herbs, Saharanpur	1
1130	Reg. Agric. Res. Stn., IGKV, Bilaspur	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
1131	Reg. Hortic. Res. Stn., Dr. Y. S. Parmar Univ. Hortic. Forest., Shimla	1
1132	Reg. Res. Lab., Bhubaneswar	1
1133	Reg. Seric. Res. Station, Kathua	1
1134	Regional Agric. Res. Station, Waraseoni	1
1135	Regional Agric. Res. Stn., Acharya N.G. Ranga Agric. Univ., Anakapalle	1
1136	Regional Agric. Res. Stn., Sher-e Kashmir Univ. Agric. Sci. Technol., Rajouri	1
1137	Regional Agric. Res. Stn., Tirupati	1
1138	Regional Agricultural Research Sub-Station, Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology, Bahraich	1
1139	Regional Cent., Natl. Bureau Soil Survey Land Use Planning, Bangalore	1
1140	Regional Centre, Natl. Bur. Soil Survey Land Use Planning, New Delhi	1
1141	Regional Forest Res. Cent., Rajahmundry	1
1142	Regional Fruit Research Station, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Pune	1
1143	Regional Horticultural Research Station, University of Horticulture and Forestry, Jachh	1
1144	Regional Inst. Med. Sci., Imphal	1
1145	Regional Institute of Education, Bhopal	1
1146	Regional Occupational Health Cent., Calcutta	1
1147	Regional Res. Cent., Central Inst. Freshwater Aquaculture, Akola	1
1148	Regional Res. Station Kandi Area, Punjab Agric. Univ., Hoshiarpur	1
1149	Regional Res. Stn., Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishvavidyalaya, Kukumseri	1
1150	Regional Res. Stn., Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Ujjan	1
1151	Regional Res. Sub-Stn., Orissa Univ. Agric. Technol., Baripada	1
1152	Regional Research Station, CCS, Haryana Agricultural	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
	University, Karnal	
1153	Regional Research Station, Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishvavidyalaya, Kullu	1
1154	Regional Research Station, Indian Grassland and Fodder Research Institute, UAS Campus, Dharwad	1
1155	Regional Research Station, OUAT, Sambalpur	1
1156	Regional Research Station, Rubber Research Institute of India, Guwahati	1
1157	Regional Research Station, Rubber Research Institute of India, Kannur	1
1158	Regional Research Station, Rubber Research Institute of India, Kolasib	1
1159	Regional Research Station, Rubber Research Institute of India, Tura	1
1160	Regional Research Station, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Aruppukottai	1
1161	Regional Research Station, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Paiyur	1
1162	Regional Research Station, UAS Campus, Dharwad	1
1163	Regional Research Station, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bijapur	1
1164	Regional Sericultural Res. Stn., Central Silk Board, Gov. India, Sahaspur	1
1165	Regional Sericultural Research Station, Central Silk Board - Govt. of India, Coonoor	1
1166	Regional Sericultural Research Station, Ranchi	1
1167	Regional Station, CICR, Sirsa	1
1168	Regional Station, Rubber Research Institute of India, Agartala	1
1169	Regional Stn., Cent. Soil Salinity Res. Inst., Canning Town	1
1170	Regional Sugarcane Rice Res. Stn. Nizamabad	1
1171	Regional Wheat Rust Research Station, Mahabaleshwar.	1
1172	Res and Dev., Calcutta	1
1173	Res. Dev. Cent., T. Stanes and Co. Ltd., Coimbatore	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
1174	Res. Sub-station, Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishvavidyalaya, Leo	1
1175	Research Circle, Calcutta	1
1176	Rice Res. Stn., HPKV, Malan	1
1177	Roland Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Berhampur	1
1178	Rubber Research Institute of India, Kanyakumari	1
1179	S. S. Engrg. Coll., Bhavnagar	1
1180	S. V. R. R. G. Gen. Hosp., Tirupati	1
1181	S.B.P. Government Coll., M.L. Sukhadia Univ., Dungarpur	1
1182	S.D. Coll., Alappuzha	1
1183	S.D.S.M.'s College, Palghar	1
1184	S.G. Inst. Dairy Technol., Patna	1
1185	S.G.R. Post Graduate College, Jaunpur	1
1186	S.J. Coll. Eng., Mysore	1
1187	S.K. Government Coll., Sikar	1
1188	S.N. Coll., Rajkanika	1
1189	S.N. Med. College, Agra	1
1190	S.P. Mandali's Therapeutic Drug Monitoring Lab. Mumbai	1
1191	S.R.R. Government Coll., Karimnagar	1
1192	S.S.V. Coll., Kahalgaon	1
1193	S.S.V. P.G. Coll., Hapur	1
1194	Safdarjang Hosp., New Delhi	1
1195	Saifa Coll. Sci. Educ., Bhopal	1
1196	Samastipur Coll., Samastipur	1
1197	Sandoc Ltd., Bombay	1
1198	Sangath Centre Child Dev. Family Guidance, Alto-Porvorim	1
1199	Sarojini Naidu Girls P.G. Coll., Bhopal	1
1200	Schell Eye Hospital, Vellore	1
1201	Sci. Coll., Nagpur	1
1202	SDM Coll. Dent. Sci. and Hosp., Dharwad	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
1203	SDM Coll., Ijire	1
1204	Seed Technology Research Unit, UAS, GKVK, Bangalore	1
1205	SGRD Inst. Med. Sci. Res., Amritsar	1
1206	Sheep Breeding Farm, Jeory	1
1207	Sher-i-Kashmir Inst., Srinagar	1
1208	Shibli Natl. Coll., Azamgarh	1
1209	Shri V. N. Medical College, Yavatmal	1
1210	Shriram Inst. Ind. Res., New Delhi	1
1211	Shroff Eye Cent., New Delhi	1
1212	Sir Ganga Ram Hosp., New Delhi	1
1213	Sir Theagaraya Coll., Chennai	1
1214	SKUAST, Srinagar	1
1215	SMC Coll. Dairy Sci., Gujarat Agric. Univ., Anand	1
1216	Soc. Bionaturalists, Bhopal	1
1217	Sorghum Research Unit, Punjabrao Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola	1
1218	South Calcutta Veterinary Clinic, Calcutta	1
1219	South Gujarat Univ., Surat	1
1220	Sree Narayana Coll., Cannanore	1
1221	Sri JCBM College, Sringeri	1
1222	Sri Sathya Sai Inst. High. Learning, Anantapur	1
1223	Sri Venkateswara Arts College, Tirupati	1
1224	Sri Venkateswara College, New Delhi	1
1225	SRM Arts Sci. Coll., Chennai	1
1226	SSG Pareek Coll., Jaipur	1
1227	SSV Coll., Haput	1
1228	St. Aloysius College, Mangalore	1
1229	St. Andrew's College, Gorakhpur	1
1230	St. Joseph's Coll., Tiruchirappalli	1
1231	St. Joseph's Hosp., Dindigul	1
1232	St. Stephen's Hosp. Delhi	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
1233	State Anim. Husbandry Dep., Haryana	1
1234	State Dis. Investigation Lab., Indore	1
1235	State Forest Serv. Coll., Dehra Dun	1
1236	State Planning Institute, Lucknow	1
1237	Steel Authority India Ltd., R and D Cent. Iron Stee., Ranchi	1
1238	Sterling Tree Magnum Ltd., Coimbatore	1
1239	Sugarcane Res. Inst., Shahjahanpur	1
1240	Sugarcane Res. Station, Assam Agril. Univ., Golaghat	1
1241	Sugarcane Res. Stn., Buralikson, Baruabamungaon	1
1242	Sugarcane Res. Stn., Dergaon	1
1243	Sugarcane Research Institute, Pusa (Samastipur)	1
1244	Sunnhemp Res. Stn., Indian Council Agric. Res., Pratapgarh	1
1245	SV Agric. Coll., Tirupati	1
1246	T. S. Coll., Hisua	1
1247	T.P. Verma Coll., Narkatia Ganj	1
1248	Tamil Nadu Hosp. Acad. Trust Res. Council, Channai	1
1249	Tamil Nadu Vet. Animal Sci. Univ., Tuticorin	1
1250	Thiagarajar Coll., Madurai	1
1251	Thoubal Coll., Manipur	1
1252	Trisea Shrimp Hatchery, Trichendur Marine Drive, Chettikulam	1
1253	Tuberculosis Chemotherapy Center, Chennai	1
1254	UAS, Reg. Res. Stn., Tiptur	1
1255	Univ. Agric. Technol., Ranichauri	1
1256	Univ. Campus, Bhopal	1
1257	Univ. Coll. Pharmaceutical Sciences, Kakatiya Univ., Waranagal	1
1258	Univ. Coll. Sci. Technol., Cacutta	1
1259	Univ. Kashmir, Srinagar	1
1260	Univ. Training and Res. Cent., Madurai	1
1261	Univ. Training Res. Cent., Tiruchirappalli	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
1262	University College, Trivandrum	1
1263	University Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Panjab University, Chandigarh	1
1264	University North Bengal, Siliguri	1
1265	UPASI Tea Res. Inst., Valparai	1
1266	Urological Res. Inst., Mumbai	1
1267	V. K. S. Univ., Ara	1
1268	V.A.S., Base Pig Breeding Farm, Guwahati	1
1269	V.O. Chidambaram Coll., Tuticorin	1
1270	V.S.J. Coll., Madhubani	1
1271	Vedic Girls P.G. Coll., Jaipur	1
1272	Vet. Biol. Res. Inst., Samalkot	1
1273	Vet. Clin., Dindigul	1
1274	Vet. Clin., Haldwani	1
1275	Vet. Coll. Udgri	1
1276	Vet. Coll., ANGR Agric. Univ., Hyderabad	1
1277	Vet. Dep., Silchar	1
1278	Vet. Dispensary, Challapalli Mandalam	1
1279	Vet. Dispensary, Krishnarayapuram	1
1280	Vet. Hosp., Eluru	1
1281	Vet. Hosp., Kotle-Bihar Kangra	1
1282	Vet. Hosp., New Delhi	1
1283	Vet. Physiol., ICAR, New Delhi	1
1284	Vet. Practitioners, Dindigul	1
1285	Veterinary Dispensary, Malkapur	1
1286	Veterinary Hospital, Ranawas	1
1287	Veterinary Polyclinic, Bathinda	1
1288	Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre, Trivandrum	1
1289	Vimala Dermatol. Cent., Bombay	1
1290	Visveswarapura Inst. Pharm. Sci., Bangalore	1

No.	Institution	Number of papers
1291	Vivekananda Coll., Calcutta	1
1292	Vivekananda Coll., Agasteeswaram	1
1293	Vivekananda Kendra Yoga Res. Foundation, Bangalore	1
1294	West. Regional Res. Stn., Avikanagar	1
1295	WIMCO Seedlings Ltd., R and D Centre, Rudrapur	1
1296	Winrock International, Dehra Dun	1
1297	Wockhardt Ltd., Bombay	1
1298	Z.S.I. Ministry of Env. and Forests, Calcutta	1
1299	Zonal Agric Res. Stn., JNKVV, Tikamgarh	1
1300	Zonal Agricultural Research Station IGAU, Jagdalpur	1
1301	Zonal Agricultural Research Station, Pune	1
1302	Zonal Res. Station, Univ. Agric. Sci., Tiptur	1
1303	Zool. Survey India, Midnapore	1
1304	Zoological Survey of India, Jodhpur	1
1305	Individuals and unknown	479
Total		8352

Table 10. Number of papers contributed by different types of organizations as seen from BIOSIS 1998

<u>Category</u>	<u>No. of papers</u>
<u>Academic</u>	
General universities	2024
Agricultural universities	1211
Medical colleges	350
Veterinary colleges	368
General colleges	321
Agricultural colleges	182
Medical universities	350
Pharmacy colleges	51
Engineering colleges	21
Engineering universities	1
Total	4879
<u>Research and other organizations</u>	
ICAR	760
CSIR	638
ICMR	145
Department of Atomic energy	116
Department of Science and Technology	116
DRDO	46
Department of Biotechnology	35
Department of Space	16
Total	1872
<u>Ministries</u>	
Ministry of Health and Family Welfare	94
Ministry of Environment Forests and Wildlife	138
Ministry of Textiles	28
Department of Commerce	25
Ministry of Mines	7
Ministry of Human Resouce Development Department of Culture	7
Department of Chemicals and Petrochemicals	4
Ministry of Urban Development	2
Ministry of Water Resources	1
Department of Agriculture and Cooperation	1
Total	307
<u>Others</u>	
Private address	482
State Government institutions	332
Private institutions	253
Hospitals	156
International institutions	71
Total	1294
Grand total	8352

Table 11. Indian cities contributing to the world literature of life sciences as seen from BIOSIS 1998

No.	City	State	No. of papers
1	New Dehli	DH	802
2	Bangalore	KA	378
3	Chennai	TN	336
4	Lucknow	UP	336
5	Bombay	MH	336
6	Hyderabad	AP	309
7	Calcutta	WB	301
8	Chandigarh	CH	213
9	Hisar	HN	171
10	Izatnagar	UP	159
11	Pune	MH	153
12	Ludhiana	PJ	152
13	Varanasi	UP	148
14	Coimbatore	TN	120
15	Mysore	KA	117
16	Thiruvananthapuram	KE	135
17	Palampur	HP	90
18	Bhubanesar	OS	88
19	Jabalpur	MP	82
20	Pant Nagar	UP	77
21	Karnal	HN	74
22	Guwahati	AS	69
23	Vallore	TN	69
24	Aligarh	UP	67
25	Indore	MP	62
26	Tirupati	AP	58
27	Rahuri	MH	57
28	Madurai	TN	54
29	Nagpur	MH	52
30	Manipal	KA	51
31	Jorhat	AS	49
32	Dehradun	UP	48
33	Jaipur	RJ	48
34	Patancheru	AP	48
35	Visakhapatnam	AP	48
36	Akola	MH	46
37	Ranchi	BR	46
38	Thrissur	KE	45
39	Ahmedabad	GJ	44
40	Gwalior	MP	44

No.	City	State	No. of papers
41	Pondicherry	PN	44
42	Patiala	PJ	40
43	Shillong	MG	40
44	Jodhpur	RJ	39
45	Mangalore	KA	38
46	Raipur	MP	38
47	Cochin	KE	37
48	Dharwad	KA	36
49	Jammu	KS	36
50	Shimla	HP	36
51	Annamalainagar	TN	33
52	Amritsar	PJ	33
53	Parbhani	MH	33
54	Calicut	KE	32
55	Baroda	GJ	31
56	Udaipur	RJ	31
57	Burdwan	WB	30
58	Port Blair	AN	30
59	Anand	GJ	29
60	Kanpur	UP	28
61	Allahabad	UP	26
62	Anantapur	AP	26
63	Meerut	UP	25
64	Anjora	MP	24
65	Avikanagar	RJ	24
66	Canchipur	MN	24
67	Sagar	MH	24
68	Tiruchirappalli	TN	30
69	Faizabad	UP	23
70	Gorakhpur	WB	23
71	Mathura	UP	23
72	Jhansi	UP	22
73	Kalyani	WB	22
74	Kharagpur	WB	22
75	Agra	UP	21
76	Dona Paula	GO	21
77	Srinagar	KS	21
78	Cuttack	OS	20
79	Dibrugarh,	AS	20
80	Roorkee	UP	20
81	Solan	HP	20
82	Bhopal	MP	19
83	Bikaner	RJ	19
84	Gulbarga	KA	19
85	Mhow	MP	19
86	Sriniketan	WB	19

No.	City	State	No. of papers
87	Kottayam	KE	18
88	Namakkal	TN	17
89	Mohanpur	WB	15
90	Naintal	UP	15
91	Ratnagiri	MH	15
92	Kurukshetra	HN	14
93	Rohtak	HN	14
94	Warangal	AP	14
95	Rajkot	GJ	13
96	Mukteswar	UP	12
97	Berhampur	OS	11
98	Junagadh	GJ	11
99	PUSA	BR	11
100	Rajendranagar	AP	11
101	Srinagar	UP	11
102	Agartala	TR	10
103	Bidar	KA	10
104	Berhampore	WB	10
105	Dhule	MH	10
106	Midnapur	WB	9
107	Moradabad	UP	9
108	Palayamkottai	TN	9
109	Almora	UP	8
110	Aurangabad	MH	8
111	Bilaspur	MP	8
112	Kaul	HN	8
113	Kolhapure	MH	8
114	Ujjain	MP	8
115	Pravaranagar	MH	7
116	Ambikapur	MP	7
117	Bareilly	UP	7
118	Chhindwara	MP	7
119	Haridwar	UP	7
120	Jalandhar	PJ	7
121	Jobner	RJ	7
122	Nirjuli	AR	7
123	Patna	BR	7
124	Pilani	RJ	7
125	Pattambi	KE	7
126	Raigarh	MP	7
127	Sehore	MP	7
128	Sriganganagar	RJ	7
129	Alwarkurichi	TN	6
130	Bhagalpur	BR	6
131	Barapani	MG	6
132	Howrah	WB	6

No.	City	State	No. of papers
133	Kayangulam	KE	6
134	Karaikal	PN	6
135	Madhubani	BR	6
136	Mohali	PJ	6
137	Nadia	WB	6
138	Amaravathi	AP	5
139	Chiplima	OS	5
140	Dirang	AR	5
141	Gangtok	SK	5
142	Gurdaspur	PJ	5
143	Itanagar	AR	5
144	Killikulam	TN	5
145	Kullu	HP	5
146	Maruteru	AP	5
147	Nadiad	GJ	5
148	Pithoragarh	UP	5
149	Rewa	MP	5
150	Sambalpur	OS	5
151	Sirugamani	TN	5
152	Sirmour	TN	5
153	Taleigao Plateau	GO	5
154	Udgir	MH	5
155	Vijayawada	AP	5
156	Vallabh Vidyanagar	GJ	5
157	Aduthurai	TN	4
158	Alappuzha	KE	4
159	Appangala	KA	4
160	Bathinda	PJ	4
161	Bhavnagar	GJ	4
162	Bijapur	KA	4
163	Bankura	OS	4
164	Dhaulakuan	HP	4
165	Diphu	AS	4
166	Haldwani	UP	4
167	Jagdapur	MP	4
168	Keonjhar	OS	4
169	Kasauli	HP	4
170	Mandya	KA	4
171	Mannuthy	KE	4
172	Muzaffarpur	BR	4
173	Nashik	MH	4
174	Panaji	GO	4
175	Raichur	KA	4
176	Shahjahanpur	UP	4
177	Secunderabad	AP	4
178	SardarKrushinagar	GJ	4

No.	City	State	No. of papers
179	Tikamgarh		4
180	Wardha	MH	4
181	Yavatmal		4
182	Ajmer	RJ	3
183	Ballia	UP	3
184	Bapatla	AP	3
185	Bharatpur	RJ	3
186	Dhanbad	BR	3
187	Dindigul	TN	3
188	Etawah	UP	3
189	Gandhinagar	GJ	3
190	Guntur	AP	3
191	Irinjalakkuda	KE	3
192	Kamulur	TN	3
193	Kalpakkram	TN	3
194	Latur	MH	3
195	Medak	AP	3
196	Mandsaur	MP	3
197	Munger	BR	3
198	Neoli	HP	3
199	North Lakhimpur	AS	3
200	Nagarjuna Nagar	AP	3
201	Ootacamund	TN	3
202	Ranichauri	UP	3
203	Rourkela	OS	3
204	Sirsa	HN	3
205	Sirsi	KA	3
206	Santinketan	WB	3
207	Solapur	MH	3
208	Tezpur	AS	3
209	Theni	TN	3
210	Titabor	AS	3
211	Tuticorin	TN	4
212	Izval	MZ	2
213	Aron	MP	2
214	Ara	BR	2
215	Assam	AS	2
216	Bhadrak	OS	2
217	Bulandshahar	UP	2
218	Barrackpore	WB	2
219	Cuddalore	TN	2
220	Dhenkanal	OS	2
221	Ernakulam	KE	2
222	Ghazipur	UP	2
223	Jalgoan	MH	2
224	Jamnagar	GJ	2

No.	City	State	No. of papers
225	Kovilpatti	TN	2
226	Kamarpukur	WB	2
227	Kapurthala	PJ	2
228	Karamsad	GJ	2
229	Mandor	RJ	2
230	Nagaon	AS	2
231	Nellore	AP	2
232	Nileshwar	KE	2
233	Navgaon	AS	2
234	Navsari	GJ	2
235	Old Goa	GO	2
236	Pattan	KS	2
237	Pithoragarh	UP	2
238	Ranipet	TN	2
239	Rudrapur	UP	2
240	Rajahmundry	AP	2
241	Shahar	PJ	2
242	Shimoga	KA	2
243	Silchar	AS	2
244	Sangla	HP	2
245	Tanuku	AP	2
246	Thane	MH	2
247	Thanjavur	TN	2
248	Tiptur	KA	2
249	Udayagiri	OS	2
250	Vadgaon	MH	2
251	Valanchery	KE	2
252	Vriddhachalam	TN	2
253	Abeokuta	-	1
254	Agasteeswaram	TN	1
255	Ajara	MH	1
256	Alto-Porvorim	GO	1
257	Alwar	RJ	1
258	Ambah	MP	1
259	Anakapalle	KA	1
260	Angamally	KE	1
261	Arnej	GJ	1
262	Aruppukottai	TN	1
263	Asmannoor	KE	1
264	Azamgarh	UP	1
265	Badnawar	MP	1
266	Bahraich	UP	1
267	Balachaur	PJ	1
268	Balasore	WB	1
269	Baran	RJ	1
270	Barh	AP	1

No.	City	State	No. of papers
271	Barpeta	AS	1
272	Bichpuri	UP	1
273	Bodh Gaya	BR	1
274	Bhilainagar	MP	1
275	Bhuj	GJ	1
276	Bijnor	UP	1
277	Bhalukpong	AR	1
278	Buldhana	MH	1
279	Bambolim	GO	1
280	Banasthali	RJ	1
281	Bhubaneswar	OS	1
282	Baruabamungaon	AS	1
283	Baripada	OS	1
284	Bathinda	PJ	1
285	Cannanore	KE	1
286	Chamba	HP	1
287	Chandrapur	MH	1
288	Chittoor	AP	1
289	Churu	-RJ	1
290	Chikmagalur	KA	1
291	Canning Town	WB	1
292	Coonoor	TN	1
293	Chittorgarh	RJ	1
294	Chitrakoot	**	1
295	Datia	MP	1
296	Deesa	GJ	1
297	Dungarpur	RJ	1
298	Duliajan	AS	1
299	Dergaon	**	1
300	Darjeeling	WB	1
301	Durg	MP	1
302	Garsa	HP	1
303	Godavari	AP	1
304	Golaghat	AS	2
305	Gurgaon	HN	1
306	Garhwal	UP	1
307	Guna	MP	1
308	Hapur	UP	1
309	Hapur	UP	1
310	Hooghly	WB	1
311	Hisua	BR	1
312	Himachal	HP	1
313	Hosur	KA	1
314	Hoshiarpur	PJ	1
315	Igatpuri	MH	1
316	Jachh (Nurpur)	HP	1

No.	City	State	No. of papers
317	Jaunpur	UP	1
318	Jaora	MH	1
319	Jeory	HP	1
320	Jhalda	WB	1
321	Jind	HN	1
322	Jamshedpur	BR	1
323	Jhargram	WB	1
324	Jhamapani	NG	1
325	Kangra	HP	1
326	Kannur	KE	1
327	Kotle-Behar	HP	1
328	Kukumseri	HP	1
329	Kalimpong	WB	1
330	Krishnapuram	KE	1
331	Kanyakumari	TN	1
332	Kancheepuram	TN	1
333	Kolasib	MZ	1
334	Karigiri	TN	1
335	Karimganj	AS	1
336	Karimnagar	KA	1
337	Kurnool	AP	1
338	Komarapalayam	TN	1
339	KrishnaDistrict	AP	1
340	Krishnarayapuram	TN	1
341	Kasagrod	KE	1
342	Kathua	KS	1
343	Katrain	HP	1
344	Kumta	KA	1
345	Leo	-HP	1
346	Ijire	KA	1
347	Lakhaoti	UP	1
348	Malan	HP	1
349	Malda	WB	1
350	Mandi	HP	1
351	Manipur	MN	1
352	Mahabaleshwar	MH	1
353	Madikeri	KA	1
354	Madhavaram	UP	1
355	Mahanandi	AP	1
356	Mirza	AS	1
357	Majalgaon Beed	MH	1
358	Mokokchung	NG	1
359	Malacca	AN	1
360	Malkapur	MH	1
361	Melmaruvathur	TN	1
362	Mandla	MP	1

No.	City	State	No. of papers
363	Minicoy	LD	1
364	Mannampandal	TN	1
365	Morang	*	1
366	Mettupalayam	TN	1
367	Munnar	KE	1
368	Nauni	HP	1
369	Narkatia Ganj	BR	1
370	Nelakondapalli	AP	1
371	Nanded	MH	1
372	Niphad	MH	1
373	Nizamabad	AP	1
374	Ongole	AP	1
375	Pali	RJ	1
376	Padappal	TN	1
377	Paiyur	TN	1
378	Palem	AP	1
379	Palakkad	KE	1
380	Parel	MH	1
381	Padegaon	MH	1
382	Pudukkottai	TN	1
383	Padrauna	UP	1
384	Paighar	MH	1
385	Paramakudi	TN	1
386	Panchkula	HN	1
387	Perundurai	TN	1
388	Pratapgarh	UP	1
389	Poondi	TN	1
390	Puttur	KA	1
391	Powarkheda	MP	1
392	Raha	AS	1
393	Rahara	WB	1
394	Rajkanika	OS	1
395	Ropar	PJ	1
396	S.A.S.Nagar	HP	1
397	Satana	MH	1
398	Satara	MH	1
399	Sundernagar	HP	1
400	Shamshi	HP	1
401	Sahaspur	UP	1
402	Sikar	RJ	1
403	Siliguri	WB	1
404	Samalkot	AP	1
405	Samastipur	BR	1
406	Sunabeda	OS	1
407	Sangli	MH	1
408	Sringeri	KA	1

No.	City	State	No. of papers
409	Shankaraghatta	KA	1
410	Saharanpur	UP	1
411	Sasaram	BR	1
412	Surat	GJ	1
413	Tadong	SK	1
414	Thadiyankudisai	TN	1
415	Tirunelveli	TN	1
416	Tura	MG	1
417	Udyogamandal	KE	1
418	Udhampur	KS	1
419	Udupi	KA	1
420	Vadodara	GJ	1
421	Vallabgarh	TN	1
422	Vellayani	KE	1
423	Vettikavaia	KE	1
424	Vizianagaram,	AP	2
425	Waltair	AP	1
426	Waraseoni	MP	1
427	Unknown		487
Total			8352

Table 12. Indian states contributing to the world literature of life sciences as seen from BIOSIS 1998

No.	State	State code	No. of papers
1	Uttar Pradesh	UP	1,135
2	Delhi	DH	802
3	Maharashtra	MH	796
4	Tamil Nadu	TN	746
5	Karnataka	KA	679
6	Andhra Pradesh	AP	554
7	West Bengal	WB	480
8	Madhya Pradesh	MP	355
9	Kerala	KE	312
10	Haryana	HN	289
11	Punjab	PJ	255
12	Chandigarh	CH	211
13	Rajasthan	RJ	199
14	Himachal Pradesh	HP	186
15	Assam	AS	167
16	Gujarat	GJ	159
17	Orissa	OS	148
18	Bihar	BR	94
19	Jammu & Kashmir	KS	61
20	Pondicherry	PN	49
21	Meghalaya	MG	47
22	Andaman Nicobar	AN	38
23	Goa	GO	34
24	Manipur	MN	25
25	Arunachal Pradesh	AR	18
26	Tripura	TR	9
27	Sikkim	SK	6
28	Mizoram	MZ	3
29	Nagaland	NG	2
30	Lakshadweep	LD	1
31	Unknown		492
Total			8352

Institution	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Total
National Chemical Laboratory, Pune	3	4	12	9	1	14	10	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	55
Sanjay Gandhi Postgrad. Inst. Med. Sci., Lucknow	7	10	15	7	7	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	51
University of Calcutta, Calcutta	20	6	4	15	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	48
ICRISAT Asia Cent., Patancheru	4	9	31	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	48
University of Delhi, Delhi	14	8	11	6	2	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	46
Natl. Dairy Res. Inst., Karnal	18	18	2	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	45
Kasturba Med. Coll., Manipal	16	7	7	6	7	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44
Madras Vet. Coll., Chennai	12	32	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44

A = 0.00 B = 0.00 < 0.50 C = 0.50 < 1.00
 D = 1.00 < 1.50 E = 1.50 < 2.00 F = 2.00 < 2.50
 G = 2.50 < 3.00 H = 3.00 < 3.50 I = 3.50 < 4.00
 J = 4.00 < 4.50 K = 4.50 < 5.00 L = 5.00 < 5.50
 M = 5.50 < 6.00 N = 6.00 < 6.50 O = 6.50 < 7.00
 P = > 7.00

Table 14. India's contribution to the world literature of life science categorized by subfields and impact factors [IF 1997] of journals used

Subfield	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Total
Agronomy- (Agriculture-)	627	267	59	12	4	8	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	978
Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biophysics	196	83	75	127	44	40	50	3	9	8	2	1	4	0	3	1	646
Horticulture- (Agriculture-)	234	77	19	5	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	336
Animal-Husbandry (Agriculture-)	125	175	13	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	315
Infection-	66	123	55	11	7	4	2	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	276
Enzymology- (Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biophysics)	51	44	44	43	22	17	12	5	8	6	2	0	0	0	3	0	257
Foods-	65	123	50	11	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	254
Pharmacology-	98	78	22	11	13	5	3	0	3	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	235
Methods-and-Techniques	52	35	31	57	24	10	11	1	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	224
Development-	94	41	26	14	4	2	1	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	2	187
Genetics-	104	46	11	11	3	2	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	183
Epidemiology- (Population-Studies)	62	46	19	9	14	2	2	2	4	0	1	1	0	0	0	3	165
Biogeography- (Population-Studies)	143	12	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	160
Economic-Entomology	121	23	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	147
Bioprocess-Engineering	21	26	73	20	3	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	146
Forestry-	109	9	12	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	133
Parasitology-	51	40	19	7	3	2	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	124
Molecular-Genetics (Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biophysics)	16	31	12	13	21	9	7	1	6	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	121
Systematics-and-Taxonomy	80	25	5	5	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	117
Immune-System (Chemical-Coordination-and-Homeostasis)	29	36	17	11	9	4	3	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	111
Reproductive-System (Reproduction-)	32	67	7	1	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	111
Behavior-	61	17	12	5	7	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	107
Endocrine-System (Chemical-Coordination-and-Homeostasis)	38	32	12	5	8	8	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	105
Pharmacognosy- (Pharmacology-)	61	16	5	14	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	97
Cardiovascular-Medicine (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	18	11	34	8	6	8	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	92
Toxicology-	27	36	13	6	3	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	87
Metabolism-	30	23	13	9	2	3	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	85
Nervous-System (Neural-Coordination)	31	18	4	10	7	4	3	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	82
Chemical-Coordination-and-Homeostasis	35	23	11	9	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	80
Nutrition-	39	26	11	2	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	80
Pest-Assessment-Control-and-Management	49	17	6	6	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	80
Pollution-Assessment-Control-and-Management	19	25	24	6	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	76
Neurology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	7	17	22	9	4	3	3	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	70

Subfield	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Total
Cell-Biology	20	15	9	10	6	2	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	67
Cardiovascular-System (Transport-and-Circulation)	27	17	7	9	3	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	66
Aquaculture-	38	22	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	65
Gastroenterology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	12	15	14	10	5	1	4	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	64
Blood-and-Lymphatics (Transport-and-Circulation)	15	21	8	7	3	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	58
Dental-and-Oral-System (Ingestion and-Assimilation)	20	15	6	7	5	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	57
Ecology- (Environmental-Sciences)	22	10	15	3	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	52
Anthropology-	43	3	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	51
Dermatology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	16	8	13	10	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	49
Bacteriology-	5	6	12	11	8	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	46
Agriculture-	16	16	8	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	45
Chemistry-	7	1	4	4	4	9	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	45
Climatology- (Environmental-Sciences)	14	18	5	1	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	45
Oncology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	12	4	15	5	1	0	2	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	45
Soil-Science	22	15	5	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	45
Clinical-Immunology (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	8	9	13	3	4	3	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44
Veterinary-Medicine (Medical-Sciences)	4	38	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44
Conservation-	18	13	9	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	42
Digestive-System	18	19	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	42
Pesticides-	10	11	14	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	42
Morphology-	30	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	37
Terrestrial-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental-Sciences)	23	6	3	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	36
Marine-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental-Sciences)	2	26	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	34
Ophthalmology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	18	5	4	1	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34
Agrichemicals-	14	15	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33
Gynecology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	13	9	6	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33
Tumor-Biology	6	13	1	6	3	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33
Bioenergetics- (Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biophysics)	13	4	7	2	1	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	32
Hematology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	14	6	4	4	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31
Clinical-Endocrinology (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	7	10	2	5	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27
Biodiversity-	21	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25
Integumentary-System (Chemical-Coordination-and-Homeostasis)	13	6	5	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25
Wildlife-Management (Conservation-)	18	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23
Biosynchronization-	9	5	6	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22
Skeletal-System (Movement-and-Support)	6	13	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22

Subfield	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Total
Digestive-System (Ingestion-and-Assimilation)	6	11	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21
Population-Studies	13	2	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21
Waste-Management (Sanitation-)	7	4	6	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20
Paleobiology-	7	9	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19
Clinical-Chemistry (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	4	2	7	3	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18
Dental-Medicine (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	6	1	6	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18
Evolution-and-Adaptation	7	5	3	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18
Freshwater-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental-Sciences)	5	6	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18
Pharmaceuticals- (Pharmacology-)	9	2	3	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17
Reproduction-	7	6	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	17
Physiology-	7	4	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	16
Aging-	3	4	1	4	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15
Human-Ecology (Anthropology-)	12	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15
Medical-Genetics (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	6	3	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	14
Models-and-Simulations (Computational-Biology)	1	6	3	3	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14
Public-Health (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	8	4	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14
Membranes- (Cell-Biology)	3	2	2	0	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	13
Radiation-Biology	4	2	5	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13
Psychiatry- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	2	0	2	0	7	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
Sense-Organs (Sensory-Reception)	2	8	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
Allergy- (Clinical-Immunology, Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	2	1	4	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
Botany-	6	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
Equipment-, Apparatus-, Devices-and-Instrumentation	5	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
Estuarine-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental-Sciences)	1	9	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
Anesthesiology- (Medical-Sciences)	0	2	0	2	0	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Microbiology-	5	2	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Obstetrics- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	1	8	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Orthopedics- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	1	4	1	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Pediatrics- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	3	4	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Urinary-System (Chemical-Coordination-and-Homeostasis)	1	8	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Urology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	7	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Computer-Applications (Computational-Biology)	4	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
Nephrology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	6	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
Biomaterials-	3	0	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8

Subfield	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Total
Human-Medicine (Medical-Sciences)	0	5	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
Occupational-Health (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	7	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
Mathematical-Biology (Computational-Biology)	1	3	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
Population-Genetics (Population-Studies)	2	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
Economics-	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	6
Education-	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
Respiratory-System (Respiration-)	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
Forensics-	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Muscular-System (Movement-and-Support)	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Otolaryngology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	0	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Pulmonary-Medicine (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Sanitation-	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Surgery- (Medical-Sciences)	2	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Biomedical-Engineering (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Dental-and-Oral-System (Oral-System)	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Geology- (Environmental-Sciences)	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Groundwater-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental-Sciences)	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Information-Studies	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Radiology- (Medical-Sciences)	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Pathology-	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Sociology- (Population-Studies)	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Sports-Medicine (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Audiology- (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Government-and-Law	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
History-	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Hospital-Administration (Allied-Medical-Sciences)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Mycology-	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Physics-	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Rheumatology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Subterranean-Ecology (Ecology-, Environmental-Sciences)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Transport-and-Circulation	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Zoology-	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Allied-Medical-Sciences	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Animal-Care	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biophysics	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Biography- (History-)	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Biography- (History-)	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Biography- (History-)	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Botany-	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

Subfield	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Total
Communication-	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Computational-Biology	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Conservation-	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Cosmetics-	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Ecology- (Environmental-Sciences)	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Environmental-Sciences	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Foods-	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
General-Life-Studies	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Geriatrics- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Horticulture- (Agriculture-)	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Human-Geography (Population- Studies)	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Infection-	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Medical-Sciences	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Ophthalmology- (Human-Medicine, Medical-Sciences)	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Pharmacology-	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Philosophy-and-Ethics	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Pollution-Assessment-Control-and- Management	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Sensory-Reception	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Tumor-Biology	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Vector-Biology	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Virology-	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

A = 0.0

B = 0.0 < 0.5

C = 0.5 < 1.0

D = 1.0 < 1.5

E = 1.5 < 2.0

F = 2.0 < 2.5

G = 2.5 < 3.0

H = 3.0 < 3.5

I = 3.5 < 4.0

J = 4.0 < 4.5

K = 4.5 < 5.0

L = 5.0 < 5.5

M = 5.5 < 6.0

N = 6.0 < 6.5

O = 6.5 < 7.0

P >= 7.0

Table 15. India's contribution to the world literature of life sciences categorized by major publishing institutions and journals used

Institution	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	AA	AB	Total
All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	1	2	14
Indian Agric. Res. Inst., New Delhi	0	1	8	9	9	0	4	1	0	8	3	0	2	0	5	0	2	12	12	0	0	4	0	0	8	0	2	0	90
CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar	7	10	5	0	3	0	8	0	0	6	4	2	0	2	7	2	4	2	2	0	4	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	70
Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi	0	0	11	6	1	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	4	0	33
Indian Vet. Res. Inst., izatnagar	29	34	7	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	17	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	1	0	0	0	0	100
Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana	13	21	2	0	4	3	0	2	1	3	4	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	3	1	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	66
Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore	0	0	2	12	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	9	0	28
Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, Chandigarh	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	9
Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow	1	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	12
Panjab University, Chandigarh	0	0	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	5	18
Central Inst. Med. Aromatic Plants, Lucknow	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	51
Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	3	4	0	0	0	0	12	0	3	2	0	0	0	7	0	0	2	0	0	0	37
Jawaharlal Nehru Univ., New Delhi	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	4
Christian Med. Coll. Hosp., Vellore	0	0	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	1	10
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	9
H. P. Krishi Vishvavidyalaya, Palampur	2	6	0	0	7	0	4	0	0	6	2	1	0	0	0	5	0	2	3	1	1	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	46
Central Food Technological Research Institute, Mysore	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	16
Govind Ballabh Pant Univ. of Agric. and Tech., Pant Nagar	2	8	1	0	3	0	4	0	0	5	4	1	0	1	5	0	0	0	3	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	44
Bhabha Atomic Res. Cent., Mumbai	0	0	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	10

Institution	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	AA	AB	Total	
Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri	3	0	1	0	2	0	3	0	7	0	3	0	31	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	52
University of Madras, Chennai	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	9	
National Botanical Research Institute, Lucknow	0	0	6	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	16	
National Chemical Laboratory, Pune	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	11	
Sanjay Gandhi Postgrad. Inst. Med. Sci., Lucknow	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	8	
University of Calcutta, Calcutta	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	3	12	
ICRISAT Asia Cent., Patancheru	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	
University of Delhi, Delhi	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	
Natl. Dairy Res. Inst., Karnal	1	13	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26	
Kasturba Med. Coll., Manipal	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	9	
Madras Vet. Coll., Chennai	28	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	36	
Total	86	98	88	45	36	9	27	5	15	33	41	26	35	55	34	21	15	20	22	13	21	22	20	4	19	9	24	18	859	

A = Indian-Veterinary-Journal
 B = Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Sciences
 C = Indian-Journal-of-Experimental-Biology
 D = Current-Science-Bangalore
 E = Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Sciences
 F = Journal-of-the-Bombay-Natural-History-Society
 G = Crop-Research-Hisar
 H = Indian-Forester
 I = Advances-in-Plant-Sciences
 J = Indian-Journal-of-Agronomy
 K = Journal-of-Food-Science-and-Technology
 L = Indian-Veterinary-Medical-Journal
 M = Journal-of-Maharashtra-Agricultural-Universities
 N = Journal-of-Medicinal-and-Aromatic-Plant-Sciences

O = Agricultural-Science-Digest
 P = Indian-Journal-of-Pharmaceutical-Sciences
 Q = Journal-of-Mycology-and-Plant-Pathology
 R = Indian-Journal-of-Plant-Physiology
 S = Indian-Journal-of-Genetics-and-Plant-Breeding
 T = Journal-of-Human-Ecology
 U = Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Nutrition
 V = International-Rice-Research-Notes
 W = Indian-Journal-of-Medical-Research
 X = Journal-of-Economic-and-Taxonomic-Botany
 Y = Journal-of-Entomological-Research-New-Delhi
 Z = Tetrahedron-Letters
 AA = Journal-of-Biosciences-Bangalore
 AB = Indian-Journal-of-Pharmacology

Journal of the Bombay Natural History Society carried 153 papers from India. Major contributors to this journal are Bombay Natural History Society, Mumbai (10 papers), Salim Ali Centre for Ornithology and Natural History, Coimbatore (6 papers), and Centre for Ecological Research and Conservation, Mysore (5 papers).

Indian Forester carried 139 papers from India. Major contributors are Forest Research Institute, Dehradun (11 papers), Tropical Forest Research Institute, Jabalpur (11 papers), and Arid Forest Research Institute, Jodhpur (6 papers).

**Table 16. Distribution of papers from selected institutions
by subfield [source BIOSIS 1998]**

Institution	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	AA	AB	AC	AD	Total
All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi	0	12	0	0	10	1	0	4	3	4	0	8	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	3	2	3	5	1	24	0	0	4	0	4	92
Indian Agric. Res. Inst., New Dehli	54	8	13	1	0	6	7	0	4	6	12	0	0	7	0	1	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	128
CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar	34	7	9	10	9	0	12	1	0	1	4	4	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	3	0	0	3	1	0	1	3	1	5	2	115
Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi	13	16	3	0	4	11	0	5	4	4	4	0	0	0	6	0	2	4	1	6	4	5	6	1	0	1	2	4	1	1	108
Indian Vet. Res. Inst., Izatnagar	2	6	0	35	11	1	7	11	2	0	3	2	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	9	9	0	2	3	1	1	0	1	0	2	114
Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana	34	3	5	6	14	7	7	5	1	3	1	2	0	1	2	1	3	0	1	2	6	0	0	0	0	2	3	0	1	1	111
Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore	1	45	3	0	2	15	0	2	10	1	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	1	5	6	0	0	1	1	1	4	0	111
Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, Chandigarh	0	4	0	0	6	4	0	5	1	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	2	0	1	0	0	10	0	1	2	0	1	43
Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow	0	18	0	0	4	4	0	8	7	2	1	0	2	0	0	0	6	0	0	5	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	59
Panjab University, Chandigarh	0	12	0	0	2	4	3	3	2	1	1	0	0	2	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	9	1	0	1	0	1	10	0	1	57
Central Inst. Med. Aromatic Plants, Lucknow	13	18	12	0	1	1	0	0	2	0	7	0	1	0	2	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	2	0	0	0	65
Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore	40	2	13	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	65
Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi	0	9	0	0	0	8	1	1	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	10	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	0	41
Christian Med. Coll. Hosp., Vellore	0	2	0	0	14	3	0	1	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	28
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh	4	11	7	0	1	1	1	0	3	0	3	0	2	0	1	0	1	1	1	7	0	2	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	49
H. P. Krishi Vishvavidyalaya, Palampur	19	0	7	3	2	1	4	3	0	0	2	1	0	5	2	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	57
Central Food Technological Research Institute, Mysore	2	12	0	0	0	6	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	57
Govind Ballabh Pant Univ. of Agric. and Tech., Pant Nagar	23	1	7	6	1	1	7	1	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	51
Bhabha Atomic Res. Cent., Mumbai	1	14	0	0	0	3	10	3	0	2	2	0	0	1	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	1	46

Institution	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	AA	AB	AC	AD	Total	
Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri	16	0	14	1	0	0	6	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	38
University of Madras, Chennai	2	6	1	0	1	2	1	4	0	3	0	0	1	0	4	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	3	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	33
National Botanical Research Institute, Lucknow	5	3	3	0	6	3	1	0	1	0	2	0	8	0	1	3	0	4	4	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	48	
National Chemical Laboratory, Pune	5	10	1	0	0	9	1	1	3	4	1	0	0	0	5	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	45	
Sanjay Gandhi Postgrad. Inst. Med. Sci., Lucknow.	0	1	0	0	4	1	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	20	
University of Calcutta, Calcutta	1	7	0	0	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	5	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	5	5	0	2	1	0	0	0	39	
ICRISAT Asia Cent., Patancheru	13	0	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21	
University of Delhi, Delhi	1	4	1	0	1	4	0	1	3	3	0	1	2	0	1	0	0	3	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	3	1	33	
Natl. Dairy Res. Inst., Karnal	0	4	0	12	0	2	3	1	2	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	42	
Kasturba Med. Coll., Manipal	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	1	0	4	0	1	2	0	1	0	20	
Madras Vet. Coll., Chennai	0	2	0	9	1	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	2	4	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	31		

A = Agronomy
 B = Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biophysics
 C = Horticulture
 D = Animal-Husbandry
 E = Infection
 F = Enzymology
 G = Foods
 H = Pharmacology
 I = Methods-and-Techniques
 J = Development
 K = Genetics
 L = Epidemiology
 M = Biogeography
 N = Economic-Entomology
 O = Bioprocess-Engineering

P = Forestry
 Q = Parasitology
 R = Molecular-Genetics
 S = Systematics-and-Taxonomy
 T = Immune-System
 U = Reproductive-System
 V = Behavior
 W = Endocrine-System
 X = Pharmacognosy
 Y = Cardiovascular-Medicine
 Z = Toxicology
 AA = Metabolism
 AB = Nervous-System
 AC = Chemical-Coordination-and-Homeostasis
 AD = Nutrition

FIGURES

Figure1. Number of journals vs. cumulative number of papers

Figure-1

Figure 2. Distribution of Indian research papers over subfields

Figure-2

Figure 3. Distribution of Indian research papers by journal country

Figure-3

Figure 4. Number of papers published in journals of different impact factor ranges

Figure-4

Figure 5. Number of journals in different impact factor ranges

Figure-5

Figure 6. Number of institutions vs. cumulative number of papers

Figure-6

Figure 7. Contributions made by different types of institutions as seen from BIOSIS

Figure-7